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Table of Contents

- 1| INTRODUCTION9**
- 1.1 OPENAIRE AND OPEN PEER REVIEW10**
- 1.2 RESEARCH AIMS11**
 - 1.2.1 SECTION 2: WHAT IS OPR? 11
 - 1.2.2 SECTION 3: ATTITUDES TO OPR..... 11
 - 1.2.3 SECTION 4: EXPERIMENTS IN OPR 12
- 2| DEFINING OPEN PEER REVIEW13**
- 2.1 INTRODUCTION13**
- 2.2 BACKGROUND.....14**
- 2.3 OPR DEFINITIONS16**
- 2.4 DEFINING OPEN PEER REVIEW18**
- 2.5 SEVEN TRAITS OF OPR21**
 - 2.5.1 OPEN IDENTITIES..... 24
 - 2.5.2 OPEN REPORTS..... 25
 - 2.5.3 OPEN PARTICIPATION..... 26
 - 2.5.4 OPEN INTERACTION 27
 - 2.5.5 OPEN PRE-REVIEW MANUSCRIPTS 28
 - 2.5.6 OPEN FINAL-VERSION COMMENTING 29
 - 2.5.7 OPEN PLATFORMS 30
- 2.6 TOWARDS A UNIFIED, COMMUNITY-ENDORSED DEFINITION OF OPR.....31**
- 2.7 CONCLUSION33**
- 3| ATTITUDES TO OPEN PEER REVIEW34**
- 3.1 INTRODUCTION34**
- 3.2 BACKGROUND.....34**
- 3.3 FOCUS GROUPS.....36**
 - 3.3.1 FOCUS GROUP 1: VARIETIES OF OPR 37
 - 3.3.2 FOCUS GROUP 2: STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN OPR 38

3.3.3 FOCUS GROUP 3: ETHICAL CHALLENGES OF OPR.....	40
3.3.4 FOCUS GROUP CONCLUSIONS	42
3.4 OPENAIRE OPR SURVEY.....	43
3.4.1 AIMS AND METHODOLOGY	43
3.4.2 DEMOGRAPHICS.....	44
3.4.3 RESULTS	49
3.4.4 DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS	64
3.4.5 SUMMARY AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS	68
<u>4 OPEN PEER REVIEW EXPERIMENTS.....</u>	<u>70</u>
4.1 INTRODUCTION	70
4.2 EXPERIMENT 1: OPEN PEER REVIEW MODULE (OPRM) FOR OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORIES	71
4.2.1 INTRODUCTION	71
4.2.2 OPEN PEER REVIEW MODULE	72
4.2.3 IMPLEMENTATION AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS	74
4.2.4 DELIVERABLES AND DISSEMINATION	78
4.3 EXPERIMENT 2: THE WINNOWER.....	80
4.3.1 OVERVIEW	80
4.3.2 ACTIVITIES.....	80
4.3.3 A BRIEF SURVEY ON PEER REVIEW IN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION.....	82
4.4 EXPERIMENT 3: OPENEDITION - EXPERIMENTING WITH OPEN PEER REVIEW AND OPEN PEER COMMENTARY.....	90
4.4.1 INTRODUCTION	90
4.4.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS	91
4.4.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS	92
4.4.4 OPEN PEER COMMENTARY WORKFLOW	94
4.4.5 TECHNICAL MODALITIES FOR REVIEW AND COMMENTARY.....	95
4.4.6 RESULTS	96
4.4.7 CONCLUSIONS	100
4.4.8 FINAL WORDS	103
4.5 EXPERIMENTS CONCLUSION.....	103

5| SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH 105

5.1 DEFINITION 105

5.2 ATTITUDES TO OPR..... 106

5.3 EXPERIMENTS WITH OPR 106

5.4 FUTURE WORK..... 108

6| REFERENCES 110

7| APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP REPORT: OPEN PEER REVIEW: MODELS, BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS, GÖTTINGEN, GERMANY 7 JUNE 2016..... 115

8| APPENDIX 2: OPR SURVEY INSTRUMENT 139

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1: Definitions of OPR in the Literature Per Year 20

FIGURE 2: Source Type of OPR Definition 20

FIGURE 3: Disciplinary Scope of Definition 21

FIGURE 4: Scope of Definition (What is Being Reviewed?) 21

FIGURE 5: Distribution of OPR Traits Amongst Definitions 22

FIGURE 6: Unique configurations of OPR Traits within Definitions 23

FIGURE 7: Responses to the survey over time (8th September to 7th October 2016) 44

FIGURE 8: Responses by discipline (HSS disciplines clustered) 46

FIGURE 9: Experiences with open peer review by role 47

FIGURE 10: Experiences with Open Peer Review - Science, Technology and Medicine (STM) vs. Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) 48

FIGURE 11: Levels of experience with OPR as author and/or reviewer 49

FIGURE 12: Overall satisfaction with peer review: Ware (2015, n=2004) vs. OpenAIRE study (2016, n=3001) 50

Figure 13: General attitudes towards aspects of Open Science 52

FIGURE 14: "Will "X" make peer review better, worse, or have no effect?" 55

FIGURE 15: Attitudes towards open identities 57

FIGURE 16: Attitudes to open reports 58

FIGURE 17: Attitudes to open participation 59

FIGURE 18: Attitudes towards other aspects 60

FIGURE 19: Degree of satisfaction with the peer review system across scientific disciplines 61

FIGURE 20: Views on open peer review by scientific discipline 62

FIGURE 21: Perception of reviewer's willingness to review for journals which make reviewer identities open 63

FIGURE 22: Open peer review as a common scholarly practice - views by age group 64

FIGURE 23: Employment level of 79 respondents 83

FIGURE 24: Employer/Organization of 79 respondents 84

FIGURE 25: Do you think the review would have been different if it had been published for people to see? 86

FIGURE 26: Assuming you wanted to: how much more time/effort do you think it would take to make your peer review something that could be posted publicly? 87

FIGURE 27: If published, researchers would largely consider reviews as professional service 87

FIGURE 28: Reasons that would incentivize scholars to make their peer reviews publicly available 88

FIGURE 29: A report published below a preprint94

FIGURE 30: A contributor annotates an initial draft.....95

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Publishable Summary

Open Peer Review (OPR) is a key component of Open Science, and OpenAIRE recognizes its potential to bring greater transparency, accountability and/or inclusivity to research evaluation. OPR is presently, however, a nascent concept with no consensus definition, a lack of information regarding stakeholders' attitudes to it, and a paucity of evidence for the effectiveness or not of its various traits. Through desk research, quantitative and qualitative stakeholder surveys and the research and development of OPR prototypes, this study aims to address these information gaps in order to foster the uptake and implementation of OPR where appropriate.

1 | INTRODUCTION

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Traditional, closed models of peer review have long been recognized sub-optimal, accused of being unreliable (Fang et al., 2012; Hames, 2014a; Jefferson et al., 2007; Kravitz et al., 2010; Schroter et al., 2008, 2004), taking too long (Armstrong, 1997; Benos et al., 2007; Ware, 2008a), being unaccountable and enabling bias (Kriegeskorte, 2012; Mahoney, 1977; Smith, 1999), lacking in incentive for reviewers (Armstrong, 1997; Ware, 2008a), and being wasteful of effort (Jubb, 2016).

“Open peer review” (OPR) is the label given to a group of overlapping methods that aim to resolve some of these issues. Although no longer an unknown quantity, OPR is far from well-understood. As with other areas of Open Science, OPR is typified by qualities such as transparency, flexibility, inclusivity and accountability. It is perhaps best defined in contradistinction to traditional or classical peer review, which is generally (1) anonymous, with either the reviewer unknown to the author (single-blind review) or both author and reviewer unknown to each other (double-blind review); (2) selective, with reviewers selected by editors; and (3) opaque, with neither the review process nor the reviews themselves made public.

The concept of OPR has been around since the early 1980s (Armstrong, 1982a). With the first implementations and trials to explicitly categorize themselves as such emerging in the late 20th Century (van Rooyen et al., 1999), some variation of OPR is now the established mode of peer review for many journals and publishers (Amsen, 2014). As has been consistently noted (Ford, 2013; Hames, 2014b; Ware, 2011), OPR has neither a standardized definition nor an agreed schema of its features and implementations. The literature reflects this with a myriad of overlapping and often contradictory definitions. While the term is used by some to refer to peer review where the identities of both author and reviewer are disclosed to each other, for others it signifies systems where reviewer reports are published alongside articles. For others it signifies both of these conditions, and for yet others it describes systems where not only “invited experts” are able to comment.

OPR has become a key component of Open Science (Pontika et al., 2015), and OpenAIRE recognizes its potential to bring greater transparency, accountability and/or inclusivity to research evaluation. As a nascent concept with no consensus definition, however, advocacy in favour of OPR is problematic. As Mark Ware notes, “it is not always clear in debates over the merits of open peer review exactly what is being referred to” (Ware, 2011). Differing flavours of OPR include independent factors (open identities, open reports, open participation, etc.) which have no necessary connection to each other, and very different benefits and drawbacks. Moreover, evaluation of the efficacy of these differing variables and hence comparison between differing systems is hence problematized and discussions potentially side-

tracked as claims are made for the efficacy or not of “open peer review” in general, despite critique usually being focussed on one element or distinct configuration of OPR. It can even be argued that this inability to define terms is to blame for the fact that, as Nicholas Kriegeskorte has pointed out, “we have yet to develop a coherent shared vision for “open evaluation” (OE), and an OE movement comparable to the OA movement” (Kriegeskorte, 2012, p. 176).

A second, related problem is a lack of research detailing stakeholders’ attitudes towards these different systems: What are current levels of awareness of various forms of OPR? What do editors, authors and reviewers actually want? What differences exist in attitudes between disciplines? What are the barriers to implementation? To date no systematic analysis of these questions has been undertaken.

A third problem lies in the relative scarcity of empirical evidence covering these matters, especially given that peer review plays such a crucial role in determining what does and does not become part of the scientific record.

1.1 OpenAIRE and Open Peer Review

OpenAIRE (<http://openaire.eu>) fosters the social and technical links that enable Open Science in Europe and beyond. Bridging infrastructures and publishing services, OpenAIRE is a sociotechnical digital infrastructure that brings together more than 50 institutions. In addition to operating an Open Access/Open Science support, outreach and advocacy network of 33 National Open Access Desks (NOADs) across Europe, OpenAIRE serves the public interest by increasing the visibility of research outputs and linking digital entities to enable navigation. This technical infrastructure assists in organizing the ‘records of science’, in particular through exposing and curating links between digital objects: authors, institutions, research outputs such as publications and research data, projects and public funding streams who funded the research. Publishing environments, digital infrastructures and tools for open science continue to converge. However, gaps between these environments remain, limiting seamless navigation and selective sharing across platforms. Hence in its latest project phase, OpenAIRE2020, OpenAIRE is conducting research and development to encourage the evolution of scholarly communications towards openness, transparency and interoperability.

A key aspect of Open Science is opening the research evaluation process. Accordingly, OPR is acknowledged to be a key component of Open Science (Pontika et al., 2015). Yet in the absence of a consensus on what OPR is, with a lack of knowledge regarding what researchers, editors and reviewers want from OPR, and a relative scarcity of empirical evidence to show what actually works in which contexts, the way ahead for OPR is currently unclear. To resolve these difficulties and foster uptake and implementation of OPR, OpenAIRE2020 has conducted the following study.

1.2 Research Aims

This study aims to answer three key open questions in OPR:

- What is OPR?
- What are stakeholders' attitudes to OPR?
- How can we foster experimentation with OPR?

These questions will be answered in the following sections:

1.2.1 Section 2: What is OPR?

As has been consistently noted (Ford, 2013; Hames, 2014b; Ware, 2011), OPR has neither a standardized definition nor an agreed schema of its features and implementations. The literature reflects this, with a myriad of overlapping and often contradictory definitions. While the term is used by some to refer to peer review where the identities of both author and reviewer are disclosed to each other, for others it signifies systems where reviewer reports are published alongside articles. For others it signifies both of these conditions, and for yet others it describes systems where not only “invited experts” are able to comment. For still others, it includes a variety of combinations of these and other novel methods. The major previous attempt to resolve these elements systematically to provide a unified definition (Ford, 2013), as we shall see, unfortunately ultimately confounds rather than resolves these issues.

Recognising the absence of a consensus view on what OPR is, OpenAIRE has undertaken a systematic review of definitions of “open peer review” or “open review”, to create a corpus of 122 definitions. These definitions have been systematically analysed to build a coherent typology of the many different innovations in peer review signified by the term and hence provide the precise technical definition currently lacking. This quantifiable data yields rich information on the range and extent of differing definitions over time and by broad subject area. Based on this work, we propose a pragmatic definition of OPR.

The data supporting this section is available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.438024>

1.2.2 Section 3: Attitudes to OPR

It is a truism that technological change is easy in comparison to cultural change, and the truism certainly holds for OPR. The diverse innovations represented by the term will remain mere niche possibilities unless accepted and taken up by the mainstream. Questions hence arise: What are scholars' current attitudes to peer review? Where do they believe it can be improved? What are their opinions on the various aspects of OPR? What are the cultural barriers that stand in the way of the uptake of such systems? What are the current levels of experience amongst stakeholders with OPR?

This section therefore addresses such questions via means qualitative and quantitative. Firstly, we undertake a review of relevant previous surveys of such attitudes and experiences (sec. 3.2). Secondly, we present the findings of a series of focus groups with key stakeholders (authors, reviewers, editors, publishers, librarians, etc.) on OPR conducted as part of an international workshop held in Goettingen, Germany in June 2016. Finally, we present the findings from an online survey of more than 3,000 respondents that took place in late 2016. Taken together, the results show that the population of authors, reviewers and editors is warming to OPR, with growing levels of experience and enthusiasm.

The data supporting this section is available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.439531>

1.2.3 Section 4: Experiments in OPR

As will be seen from Section 2, the evidential base for many of the claims for and arguments against OPR is largely thin and unconvincing. Hence, OpenAIRE has played host to three innovative experiments that aim at promoting OPR and studying its effects in the context of digital infrastructures for open scholarship. The main aims of these activities were to:

- Encourage experimentation in OPR.
- Investigate ways in which OPR technologies might integrate with OpenAIRE's infrastructure, including the repository [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org) as well as other content aggregated, inferred, and interlinked by OpenAIRE.
- Provide case studies for evaluation in OpenAIRE's wider investigation of OPR.

To achieve this, in mid-2015 OpenAIRE ran an open call for tenders for OPR prototypes/experiments, with two grants of up to 25,000 Euros each available. Twelve bids were received. After a thorough evaluation process, the awards were granted to (1) a consortium of organizations led by Open Scholar CIC (lead investigator Pandelis Perakakis), and (2) The Winnower (lead investigator Joshua Nicholson). In addition, a third experiment was already specified in the OpenAIRE2020 project proposal, led by (3) OpenEdition (lead investigator Julien Bordier). The three experiments, whose results are presented in the following sections of this report, were diverse in their aims and methods:

- Open Scholar** and their consortium aimed to turn repositories into functional evaluation platforms by building an OPR module for integration with Open Access repositories and then implementing this module in two high-profile institutional repositories.
- The Winnower** sought to integrate the Winnower platform with repositories like Zenodo via DOIs and APIs to facilitate OPR of repository objects, as well as offering financial incentives to encourage open participation in the sharing of 'journal club' reviews and documenting user experiences via survey.
- OpenEdition** aimed to use open services such as the annotation software hypotheses.org and OpenEdition's platform for academic blogs to model a workflow (selection, review and revision) that would develop blog articles into peer reviewed publications in the Humanities and Social Sciences.

2 | DEFINING OPEN PEER REVIEW

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At present there is neither a standardized definition of Open Peer Review nor an agreed schema of its features and implementations, which is highly problematic for discussion of OPR's potential benefits and drawbacks. This chapter seeks to resolve these difficulties by analysing the literature for available definitions of "open peer review" and "open review", which are then codified against an iteratively constructed typology of independent OPR traits. In order to build a coherent typology of the many different adaptations to the traditional peer review that have come to be signified by the term OPR. In defining each trait, we also define the differing problems with traditional peer review that each trait aims to overcome and offer an overview of the evidence available for their effectiveness in those regards.

2.1 Introduction

"OPEN REVIEW AND OPEN PEER REVIEW ARE NEW TERMS FOR EVOLVING PHENOMENA. THEY DON'T HAVE PRECISE OR TECHNICAL DEFINITIONS. NO MATTER HOW THEY'RE DEFINED, THERE'S A LARGE AREA OF OVERLAP BETWEEN THEM. IF THERE'S EVER A DIFFERENCE, SOME KINDS OF OPEN REVIEW ACCEPT EVALUATIVE COMMENTS FROM ANY READERS, EVEN ANONYMOUS READERS, WHILE OTHER KINDS TRY TO LIMIT EVALUATIVE COMMENTS TO THOSE FROM "PEERS" WITH EXPERTISE OR CREDENTIALS IN THE RELEVANT FIELD. BUT NEITHER KIND OF REVIEW HAS A SPECIAL NAME, AND I THINK EACH COULD FAIRLY BE CALLED "OPEN REVIEW" OR "OPEN PEER REVIEW". - PETER SUBER, EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE, 2007, CITED BY (P2P FOUNDATION, 2016)¹

As with other areas of "open science" (Pontika et al., 2015), "open peer review" (OPR) is a hot topic, with a rapidly growing literature. Yet, as has been consistently noted (Ford, 2013; Hames, 2014b; Ware, 2011), OPR has neither a standardized definition nor an agreed schema of its features and implementations. The literature reflects this, with a myriad of overlapping and often contradictory

¹ This provenance of this quote is uncertain, even to Suber himself, who recently advised (personal correspondence, 19.8.2016): "I might have said it in an email (as noted). But I can't confirm that, since all my emails from before 2009 are on an old computer in a different city. It sounds like something I could have said in 2007. If you want to use it and attribute it to me, please feel free to note my own uncertainty!"

definitions. While the term is used by some to refer to peer review where the identities of both author and reviewer are disclosed to each other, for others it signifies systems where reviewer reports are published alongside articles. For others it signifies both of these conditions, and for yet others it describes systems where not only “invited experts” are able to comment. For still others, it includes a variety of combinations of these and other novel methods. The major previous attempt to resolve these elements systematically to provide a unified definition (Ford, 2013), as we shall see, unfortunately ultimately confounds rather than resolves these issues.

In short, things have not improved much since Suber made his astute assessment. This continuing imprecision grows more problematic with time, however. As Mark Ware notes, “it is not always clear in debates over the merits of OPR exactly what is being referred to” (Ware, 2011). Differing flavours of OPR include independent factors (open identities, open reports, open participation, etc.) which have no necessary connection to each other, and very different benefits and drawbacks. Evaluation of the efficacy of these differing variables and hence comparison between differing systems is hence problematized and discussions potentially side-tracked as claims are made for the efficacy or not of “OPR” in general, despite critique usually being focussed on one element or distinct configuration of OPR. It can even be argued that this inability to define terms is to blame for the fact that, as Nicholas Kriegskorte has pointed out, “we have yet to develop a coherent shared vision for “open evaluation” (OE), and an OE movement comparable to the OA movement” (Kriegeskorte, 2012, p. 176).

To resolve this, OpenAIRE has undertaken a systematic review of existing definitions of “open peer review” or “open review”, based on a corpus of 122 definitions. These definitions have been systematically analysed to build a coherent typology of the many different innovations in peer review signified by the term and hence provide the precise technical definition currently lacking. This quantifiable data yields rich information on the range and extent of differing definitions over time and by broad subject area. Based on this work, we propose a pragmatic definition of OPR as an umbrella terms for various novel flavours of peer review that in differing ways all seek to loosen classical peer review’s bonds of control.

2.2 Background

Peer review is the formal quality assurance mechanism whereby scholarly manuscripts (e.g., journal articles, books, grant applications and conference papers) are made subject to the scrutiny of others, whose feedback and judgements are then used to improve works and make final decisions regarding selection (for publication, grant allocation or speaking time). This system is perhaps more recent than we might expect (Spier, 2002, advises that its main formal elements have only been in general use since the mid-twentieth century in scientific publishing, for example). Nonetheless, though, the main elements of “classical” or “traditional” peer review are remarkably prevalent across research domains and differing research outputs. These features include: the following of formal procedures, high

selectivity, the involvement of 2-3 selected “peers” or “experts”, concealment of reviewer names from authors (and sometimes vice versa) as standard, a lack of direct interaction amongst reviewers and between reviewers and authors, and that the process ends when a gatekeeper (editor, funder, conference organiser) makes a formal acceptance decision.

Researchers seem to agree that peer review *per se* is necessary, but most find the current model sub-optimal. Ware’s 2008 survey, for example, found that an overwhelming majority (85%) agreed that “peer review greatly helps scientific communication” and that even more (around 90%) said their own last published paper had been improved by peer review. Yet almost two thirds (64%) declared that they were satisfied with the current system of peer review, less than a third (32%) believed that this system is the best possible (Ware, 2008a). A recent follow-up study by the same author reported a slight increase in the desire for improvements in peer review (Ware, 2016).

Wide-spread beliefs that the current model is sub-optimal can be attributed to the various ways in which traditional peer review has been subject to criticism. Peer review has been variously accused of:

- **Unreliability and inconsistency:** Reliant upon the vagaries of human judgement, the objectivity, reliability, and consistency of peer review are subject to question. Studies show reviewers’ views tend to show very weak levels of agreement (Kravitz et al., 2010; Mahoney, 1977), at levels only slightly better than chance (Herron, 2012; Smith, 2006). Studies suggest decisions on rejection or acceptance are similarly inconsistent. For example Peters and Ceci’s classic (1982) study which found eight of twelve papers were rejected for methodological flaws when resubmitted to the same journals in which they had already been published. This inconsistency is mirrored in peer review’s inability to prevent errors and fraud from entering the scientific literature. Reviewers often fail to detect major methodological failings (Schroter et al., 2004), with eminent journals (whose higher rejection rates might suggest more stringent peer review processes) seeming to perform no better than others (Fang et al., 2012). Indeed Fang and Casadevall (2011) found that the frequency of retraction is strongly correlated with the journal impact factor. Whatever the cause, recent sharp rises in the number of retracted scientific publications (Steen et al., 2013) testify that peer review sometimes fails in its role as the gatekeeper of science, allowing errors to enter the literature. Peer review’s other role, of filtering the best work into the best journals, also seems to fail. Many articles in top journals remain poorly cited, while many of the most highly-cited articles in their fields are published in lower-tier journals (Jubb, 2016).
- **Delay and expense:** The period from submission to publication at many journals can often exceed one year, with much of this time taken up with peer review. This delay slows down the availability of results for further research and professional exploitation. The work undertaken in this period is also expensive, with the global costs of reviewers’ time estimated at £1.9bn in 2008 (Research Information Network, 2008), which figure does not take into account the coordinating costs of publishers or the time of authors in revising and resubmitting manuscripts (Jubb, 2016). These costs are greatly exacerbated by the current system in which peer review is

managed by each journal, such that the same manuscript may be peer reviewed many times over as it is successively rejected and resubmitted until it finds acceptance.

- **Unaccountability and risks of subversion:** The “black-box” nature of traditional peer review gives reviewers, editors and even authors a lot of power to potentially subvert the process. Lack of transparency means that editors can unilaterally reject submissions or shape review outcomes by selecting reviewers based on their known preference for or aversion to certain theories and methods (Travis and Collins, 1991). Reviewers, shielded by anonymity, may act unethically in their own interests by concealing conflicts of interest. Smith (2006), an experienced editor, for example, reports reviewers stealing ideas and passing them off as their own or blocking or delaying publication of competitors’ ideas through harsh reviews. Equally, they may simply favour their friends and target their enemies. Authors, meanwhile, can manipulate the system by writing reviews of their own work via fake or stolen identities (Kaplan, 2015).
- **Social and publication biases:** Although often idealized as impartial, objective assessors, in reality studies suggest that peer reviewers may be subject to social biases on the grounds of gender (Budden et al., 2008; Lloyd, 1990; Tregenza, 2002), nationality (Daniel, 1994; Ernst and Kienbacher, 1991; Link, 1998), institutional affiliation (Dall’Aglia, 2006; Gillespie et al., 1985; Peters and Ceci, 1982), language (Cronin, 2009; J. S. Ross et al., 2006; Tregenza, 2002) and discipline (Travis and Collins, 1991). Other studies suggest so-called “publication bias”, where prejudices against specific categories of works shape what is published. First is a preference for complexity over simplicity in methodology (even if inappropriate, c.f., Travis and Collins, 1991) and language (where content remained identical Armstrong, 1980, 1997). Next, “confirmatory bias” is theorized to lead to conservatism bias reviewers against innovative methods or results contrary to dominant theoretical perspectives (Chubin and Hackett, 1990; García et al., 2016; Mahoney, 1977). Finally, factors like the pursuit of “impact” and “excellence” (Moore et al., 2016) mean that editors and reviewers seem primed to prefer positive results over negative or neutral ones (Bardy, 1998; Dickersin et al., 1992; Fanelli, 2010; Ioannidis, 1998), and to disfavour replication studies (Campanario, 1998; Kerr et al., 1977)
- **Lack of incentives:** Traditional peer review provides little in the way of incentives for reviewers, whose work is almost exclusively unpaid and whose anonymous contributions cannot be recognised and hence rewarded (Armstrong, 1997; Ware, 2008a).
- **Wastefulness:** Reviewer comments often add context or point to areas for future work. Reviewer disagreements can expose areas of tension in a theory or argument. The behind-the-scenes discussions of reviewers and authors can also guide younger researchers in learning review processes. Readers may find such information helpful and yet at present, this potentially valuable additional information is wasted.

In response, a wide variety of changes to peer review have been suggested (see Walker and Rocha da Silva, 2015, for an excellent overview). Amongst these innovations, many have been labelled “open peer review” at one time or another.

2.3 OPR definitions

The diversity of these definitions can be seen by examining just two examples (the first of which is, as far as I know, the first recorded use of the phrase “open peer review”):

“[A]N OPEN REVIEWING SYSTEM WOULD BE PREFERABLE. IT WOULD BE MORE EQUITABLE AND MORE EFFICIENT. KNOWING THAT THEY WOULD HAVE TO DEFEND THEIR VIEWS BEFORE THEIR PEERS SHOULD PROVIDE REFEREES WITH THE MOTIVATION TO DO A GOOD JOB. ALSO, AS A SIDE BENEFIT, REFEREES WOULD BE RECOGNIZED FOR THE WORK THEY HAD DONE (AT LEAST FOR THOSE PAPERS THAT WERE PUBLISHED). OPEN PEER REVIEW WOULD ALSO IMPROVE COMMUNICATION. REFEREES AND AUTHORS COULD DISCUSS DIFFICULT ISSUES TO FIND WAYS TO IMPROVE A PAPER, RATHER THAN DISMISSING IT. FREQUENTLY, THE REVIEW ITSELF PROVIDES USEFUL INFORMATION. SHOULD NOT THESE CONTRIBUTIONS BE SHARED? INTERESTED READERS SHOULD HAVE ACCESS TO THE REVIEWS OF THE PUBLISHED PAPERS.” (ARMSTRONG, 1982A, P. 198)

“[O]PEN REVIEW MAKES SUBMISSIONS OA [OPEN ACCESS], BEFORE OR AFTER SOME PREPUBLICATION REVIEW, AND INVITES COMMUNITY COMMENTS. SOME OPEN-REVIEW JOURNALS WILL USE THOSE COMMENTS TO DECIDE WHETHER TO ACCEPT THE ARTICLE FOR FORMAL PUBLICATION, AND OTHERS WILL ALREADY HAVE ACCEPTED THE ARTICLE AND USE THE COMMUNITY COMMENTS TO COMPLEMENT OR CARRY FORWARD THE QUALITY EVALUATION STARTED BY THE JOURNAL. ” (SUBER, 2012, P. 104)

Within just these examples, there are already a multitude of factors at play, including the removal of anonymity, the publishing of review reports, interaction between participants, crowdsourcing of reviews, and making manuscripts public pre-review, amongst others. But these are each distinct factors, each presenting separate strategies for openness and targeting differing problems. For example, disclosure of identities aims usually at increasing accountability and minimizing bias, c.f., “referees should be more highly motivated to do a competent and fair review if they may have to defend their views to the authors and if they will be identified with the published papers” (Armstrong, 1982b). Publication of reports, on the other hand, also tackles problems of incentive (reviewers can get credit for their work) and wastefulness (reports can be consulted by readers). Moreover, these factors need not necessarily be linked, which is to say that can be employed separately: identities can be disclosed without reports being published, and reports published with reviewer names withheld, for example.

This diversity has led many authors to acknowledge the essential ambiguity of the term “open peer review” (Hames, 2014b; Sandewall, 2012; Ware, 2011). The major attempt thus far to bring coherence to this confusing landscape of competing and overlapping definitions, is Emily Ford’s (2013) paper “Defining and Characterizing Open Peer Review: A Review of the Literature”. Ford examined thirty-five articles to produce a schema of eight “common characteristics” of OPR: signed review, disclosed review, editor-mediated review, transparent review, crowdsourced review, prepublication review, synchronous review, and post-publication review. Unfortunately, however, Ford’s paper fails to offer a definitive definition of OPR, since despite distinguishing eight “common characteristics” of OPR, Ford

nevertheless tries to reduce it to merely one: open identities: “Despite the differing definitions and implementations of open peer review discussed in the literature, its general treatment suggests that the process incorporates disclosure of authors’ and reviewers’ identities at some point during an article’s review and publication” (Ford, 2013, p. 314). Summing her argument elsewhere, she says: “my previous definition ... broadly understands OPR as any scholarly review mechanism providing disclosure of author and referee identities to one another”. But the other elements of her schema do not reduce to this one factor. Many definitions do not include open identities at all. This hence means that although Ford claims to have identified several features of OPR, she in fact is asserting that there is only one *defining* factor (open identity), which leaves us where we started. Ford’s schema is elsewhere problematic: it lists “editor-mediated review” and “pre-publication review” as distinguishing characteristics, despite these being common traits of traditional peer review; it includes questionable elements such as the purely “theoretical” “synchronous review”; and some of its characteristics do not seem to be “base elements”, but complexes of other traits – for example, the definition of “transparent review” incorporates other characteristics such as open identities (which Ford terms “signed review”) and open reports (“disclosed review”).

2.4 Defining open peer review

To resolve this ambiguity, OpenAIRE performed a review of the English-language literature for articles discussing “open review” or “open peer review”, extracting a corpus of 122 definitions of OPR. We first searched Web of Science for “TOPIC: ("open review" OR "open peer review")”, with no limitation on date of publication, yielding a total of 137 results (searched on 12-7-2016). These records were then each individually examined for relevance and a total of 57 were excluded: 21 results (all BioMed Central publications) had been through an OPR process (which was mentioned in the abstract) but did not themselves touch on the subject of OPR; 12 results used the phrase “open review” to refer to a literature review with a flexible methodology, rather than in any connection with peer review; 12 results were for the review of objects classed as “out of scope” (i.e., review of things other than scientific research objects – academic articles, books, conference submissions, data – i.e., guidelines for clinical or therapeutic techniques, standardized terminologies, patent applications, and court judgements); 7 results were not in the English language; and 5 results were duplicate entries in WoS. This left a total of 80 relevant articles which mentioned either “open peer review” or “open review”. This set was then enriched with a further 42 definitions from sources found through searching for the same terms via other academic databases (e.g., Google Scholar, JSTOR, disciplinary databases), searching Google (for Blog articles) and Google Books (books), as well as following citations in relevant bibliographies and literature review articles.

Each source was then individually examined for its definition of OPR. Where no explicit definition (e.g., “OPR is ...”) was given, implicit definitions were gathered from contextual statements (e.g., “reviewers

can notify the editors if they want to opt-out of the open review system and stay anonymous” (Janowicz and Hitzler, 2012) is taken to endorse a definition of OPR as incorporating open identities). In a few cases, sources defined OPR in relation to the systems of specific publishers (e.g., F1000Research, BioMed Central and Nature), and so were taken to implicitly endorse those systems as definitive of OPR.

This data is available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.438024>

The number of definitions over time shows a clear upward trend, with the most definitions in a single year coming in 2015. The distribution shows that except for some outlying definitions in the early 1980s, the phrase “open peer review” did not really enter academic discussion until the early 1990s. At that time, the phrase seems to have been used largely to refer to non-blinded review (i.e., open identities). We then see a big upswing from the early-mid 2000s onwards, which perhaps correlates with the rise of the openness agenda (especially open access, but also open data and open science more generally) over that period.

FIGURE 1: DEFINITIONS OF OPR IN THE LIETERATURE PER YEAR

FIGURE 2: SOURCE TYPE OF OPR DEFINITION

As shown in Figure 2, most of the definitions 77.9% (n=95) come from peer-reviewed journal articles, with the second largest sources being books and blog posts. Other sources include letters to journals, news items, community reports and glossaries.

FIGURE 3: DISCIPLINARY SCOPE OF DEFINITION

As seen in Fig. 3, the majority of definitions (51.6%) were identified to be primarily concerned with peer-review of STEM-subject material, while 10.7% targeted SSH material and the remainder (37.7%) were interdisciplinary.

Meanwhile (per Fig. 4), regarding the target of peer-review, most definitions dealt with peer review of journal articles (80.7%), with the second largest group not specifying a target (16%). A small number of articles also dealt with review of

data, conference papers and grant proposals. Of the 122 definitions identified, 68% (n=83) were explicitly stated, 37.7% (n=46) implicitly stated, and 5.7% (n=7) contained both explicit and implicit information.

FIGURE 4: SCOPE OF DEFINITION (WHAT IS BEING REVIEWED?)

2.5 Seven traits of OPR

The extracted definitions were examined and classified against an iteratively constructed taxonomy of OPR traits. Nickerson et al. (2012) advise that development of a taxonomy should begin by identifying

the appropriate meta-characteristic. In this case the meta-characteristic was decided to be distinct individual innovations to the traditional peer review system. An iterative approach then followed, in which dimensions given in the literature were applied to the corpus of definitions and gaps/overlaps in the OPR taxonomy identified. Based on this, new traits or distinctions were introduced until in the end, a schema of seven OPR traits was produced:

- Open identities: Authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity.
- Open reports: Review reports are published alongside the relevant article.
- Open participation: The wider community to able to contribute to the review process.
- Open pre-review manuscripts: Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g., via pre-print servers like ArXiv) in advance of any formal peer review procedures.
- Open final-version commenting: Review or commenting on final “version of record” publications.
- Open interaction: Direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged.
- Open platforms: Review is de-coupled from publishing in that it is facilitated by a different organizational entity than the venue of publication.

FIGURE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF OPR TRAITS AMONGST DEFINITIONS

“open peer review” has been used thus far. For the literature offers a total of 22 distinct configurations of seven traits, effectively meaning that there are 22 different definitions of OPR in the literature.

A “power law” distribution can be observed in the distribution of these traits, with the most popular configuration (open identities) accounting for one third (33.6%, n=41) and the second-most popular configuration (open identities, open reports) accounting for almost a quarter (23.8%, n=29) of all definitions. There then follows a “long-tail” of less-frequently found configurations, with more than half of all configurations being unique to a single definition.

We next describe the scope of each of these traits.

2.5.1 Open Identities

Open identities peer review, also known as signed peer review (Ford, 2013; Nobarany and Booth, 2015) and “unblinded review” (Monsen and Horn, 2007), is review where authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identities. Traditional peer review operates as either “single-blind”, where authors do not know reviewers' identities, or “double-blind”, where both authors and reviewers remain anonymous. Double-blind reviewing is more common in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences than it is in STEM (science, technology, engineering and medicine) subjects (Walker and Rocha da Silva, 2015), but in all areas single-blind review is by far the most common model (Elsevier, 2016). A main reason for maintaining author anonymity is that it is assumed to tackle possible publication biases against authors with traditionally feminine names, from less prestigious institutions or non-English speaking regions (Budden et al., 2008; J. Ross et al., 2006). Reviewer anonymity, meanwhile, is presumed to protect reviewers from undue influence, allowing them to give candid feedback without fear of possible reprisals from aggrieved authors. Various studies have failed to show that such measures increase review quality, however (Fisher et al., 1994; Godlee et al., 1998; Justice et al., 1998; McNutt et al., 1990; van Rooyen et al., 1999). As Godlee and her colleagues have said, “Neither blinding reviewers to the authors and origin of the paper nor requiring them to sign their reports had any effect on rate of detection of errors. Such measures are unlikely to improve the quality of peer review reports” (Godlee et al., 1998). Moreover, factors such as close disciplinary communities and Internet search capabilities, mean that author anonymity is only partially effective, with reviewers shown to be able to identify authors in between 26 and 46 percent of cases (Fisher et al., 1994; Godlee et al., 1998).

Proponents of open identity peer review, on the other hand, argue that it will enhance accountability, further enable credit for peer reviewers, and simply make the system fairer: “most importantly, it seems unjust that authors should be “judged” by reviewers hiding behind anonymity” (van Rooyen et al., 1999). Open identity peer review is argued, moreover, to potentially increase review quality, as it is theorised that reviewers will be more highly motivated and invest more care in their reviews if their

names are attached to them, although opponents counter that signing will lead to poorer reviews, as reviewers temper their true opinions to avoid causing offence. To date studies have failed to show any great effect in either direction (McNutt et al., 1990; van Rooyen et al., 2010, 1999). However, as these studies derive from only one disciplinary area (Medicine), they cannot be said to be representative and hence further research is undoubtedly required.

2.5.2 Open Reports

Open reports peer review is where review reports (either full reports or summaries) are published alongside the relevant article. The main benefits of this measure is in the making available for re-use of currently invisible but potentially useful scholarly information, the increased transparency and accountability that comes with being able to examine normally behind-the-scenes discussions and processes of improvement and assessment, and the potential to further incentivize peer reviewers by making their peer review work a more visible part of their scholarly activities (thus enabling reputational credit).

Reviewing is hard work. Research Information Network reported in 2008 that a single peer review takes an average of four hours, at an estimated total annual global cost of around £1.9 billion (Research Information Network, 2008). Once an article is published, however, these reviews usually serve no further purpose except residing in a publisher's long-term archives. Yet those reviews contain information that remains potentially relevant and useful in the here-and-now. Often works are accepted despite the lingering reservations of reviewers. Published reports can enable readers to consider these criticisms themselves, and "have a chance to examine and appraise this process of "creative disagreement" and form their own opinions" (Peters and Ceci, 1982). Making reviews public in this way also adds another layer of quality assurance, as the reviews are open to the scrutiny of the wider scientific community. Moreover, publishing reports also aims at raising the recognition and reward of the work of peer reviewers. Adding review activities to the reviewer's professional record is common practice; author identification systems currently also add mechanisms to host such information (e.g. via ORCID) (Hanson et al., 2016). Finally, open reports give young researchers a guide (to tone, length, the formulation of criticisms) to help them as they begin to do peer review themselves.

The evidence-base against which to judge such arguments is not great enough to enable strong conclusions, however. Van Rooyen and her colleagues found that open reports correlate with higher refusal rates amongst potential reviewers, as well as an increase in time taken to write review but no concomitant effect on review quality (van Rooyen et al., 2010). Nicholson and Alperin's small survey, however, found generally positive attitudes "researchers ... believe that open review would generally

improve reviews, and that peer reviews should count for career advancement” (Nicholson and Alperin, 2016).

2.5.3 Open participation

Open participation peer review, also known as “crowdsourced peer review” (Ford, 2015, 2013), “community/public review” (Walker and Rocha da Silva, 2015) and “public peer review” (Bornmann et al., 2012), is review that allows the wider community to contribute to the review process. Whereas in traditional peer review editors identify and invite specific parties (peers) to review, open participation processes invite interested members of the scholarly community to participate in the review process, either by contributing full, structured reviews or shorter comments. It may be that comments are open to anybody (anonymous or registered), or some credentials might first be required (e.g., Science Open requires an ORCID profile with at least five published articles (ScienceOpen, 2014)). Open participation is often used as a complement to a parallel process of solicited peer reviews. It aims to resolve possible conflicts associated with editorial selection of reviewers (e.g., biases, closed-networks, elitism) and possibly improve the reliability of peer review by increasing the number of reviewers (Bornmann et al., 2012). Reviewers can come from the wider research community, as well as those traditionally under-represented in scientific assessment, including representatives from industry or members of special-interest groups, for example patients in the case of medical journals (c.f., Ware, 2011). This has the potential to open the pool of reviewers beyond those identified by editors to include all potentially interested reviewers (including those from outside academia), and hence potentially much increasing the number of reviewers for each publication (though in practice this is unlikely). Evidence suggests this could increase the accuracy of peer review. For example Herron (2012) produced a mathematical model of the peer review process which showed that “the accuracy of public reader-reviewers can surpass that of a small group of expert reviewers if the group of public reviewers is of sufficient size”, although only if the numbers of reader-reviewers exceeded 50.

Criticisms of open participation routinely focus on questions of reviewers’ qualifications to comment and the incentives for doing so. As Stevan Harnad has said: “it is not clear whether the self-appointed commentators will be qualified specialists (or how that is to be ascertained). The expert population in any given speciality is a scarce resource, already overharvested by classical peer review, so one wonders who would have the time or inclination to add journeyman commentary services to this load on their own initiative” (Harnad, 2000). Moreover, difficulties in motivating self-selecting commentators to take part and deliver useful critique have been reported. *Nature*, for example, ran an experiment from June to December 2006 inviting submitting authors to take part in an experiment where open participation would be used as a complement to a parallel process of solicited peer reviews. *Nature* judged the trial to have been unsuccessful due to the small number of authors wishing to take part (just 5% of submitting authors), the small number of overall comments (almost half of

articles received no comments) and the insubstantial nature of most of the comments that were received (Fitzpatrick, 2011). At the Open Access journal *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* (ACP), which publishes pre-review discussion papers for community comments, only about one in five papers is commented upon (Pöschl, 2012). Bornmann et al., conducted a comparative content analysis of the ACP's community comments and formal referee reviews and concluded that the latter – tending to focus more on formal qualities, conclusions and potential impact – better supported the selection and improvement of manuscripts (Bornmann et al., 2012). This all suggests that although open participation might be a worthwhile complement to traditional, invited peer review, it is unlikely to be able to fully replace it.

2.5.4 Open Interaction

Open interaction peer review allows and encourages direct reciprocal discussion between reviewers, and/or between author(s) and reviewers. In traditional peer review, reviewers and authors correspond only with editors. Reviewers have no contact with other reviewers, and authors usually have no opportunity to directly question or respond to reviewers' comments. Allowing interaction amongst reviewers or between authors and reviewers, or between reviewers themselves, is hence another way to “open up” the review process, enabling editors and reviewers to work with authors to improve their manuscript. The motivation for doing so, according to Armstrong (1982a), is to “improve communication. Referees and authors could discuss difficult issues to find ways to improve a paper, rather than dismissing it”.

Some journals enable pre-publication interaction between reviewers as standard (Hames, 2014b; Walker and Rocha da Silva, 2015). The *EMBO Journal*, for example, enables “cross-peer review,” where referees are “invited to comment on each other's reports, before the editor makes a decision, ensuring a balanced review process”(EMBO Journal, 2016). At *eLife*, reviewers and editor engage in an “online consultation session” where they come to a mutual decision before the editor compiles a single peer review summary letter for the author to give them a single, non-contradictory roadmap for revisions (Schekman et al., 2013). The publisher Frontiers has gone a step further, including an interactive collaboration stage that “unites authors, reviewers and the Associate Editor – and if need be the Specialty Chief Editor – in a direct online dialogue, enabling quick iterations and facilitating consensus” (Frontiers, 2016).

Perhaps even more so than other areas studied here, evidence to judge the effectiveness of interactive review is scarce. Based on anecdotal evidence, Walker and Rocha da Silva (2015) advise that “[r]eports from participants are generally but not universally positive”. To the knowledge of the author, the only experimental study that has specifically examined interaction among reviewers or between reviewers and authors is that of Jeffrey Leek and his colleagues, who performed a laboratory study of open and

closed peer review based on an online game and found that “improved cooperation does in fact lead to improved reviewing accuracy. These results suggest that in this era of increasing competition for publication and grants, cooperation is vital for accurate evaluation of scientific research” (Leek et al., 2011). Such results are encouraging, but hardly conclusive. There hence remains much scope for further research to determine the impact of interactivity upon the efficacy and cost of the review process.

2.5.5 Open pre-review manuscripts

Open pre-review manuscripts is review where manuscripts are immediately openly accessible (via the Internet) in advance, or in synchrony with, any formal peer review procedures. Subject specific “preprint servers” like arXiv.org and bioRxiv.org, institutional repositories, catch-all repositories like Zenodo.org or Figshare.com and some publisher-hosted repositories (like *PeerJ Preprints*) allow authors to short-cut the traditional publication process and make their manuscripts immediately available to everyone. This can be used as a complement to a more traditional publication process, with comments invited on preprints and then incorporated into redrafting as the manuscript goes through traditional peer review with a journal. Alternatively, services which overlay peer-review functionalities on repositories can produce functional publication platforms at reduced cost (Boldt, 2011; Perakakis et al., 2010). The mathematics journal *Discrete Analysis*, for example, is an overlay journal whose primary content is hosted on the arXiv (Gowers, 2015). The recently released Open Peer Review Module for repositories, developed by Open Scholar in association with OpenAIRE, is an open source software plug-in which adds overlay peer review functionalities to repositories using the DSpace software (Open Scholar, 2016). Another innovative model along these lines is that of *ScienceOpen*, which ingests articles metadata from preprint servers, contextualizes them by adding altmetrics and other relational information, before offering authors peer review.

In other cases manuscripts are submitted to publishers in the usual way, but made immediately available online (usually following some rapid preliminary review or “sanity check”) before the start of the peer review process. This approach was pioneered with the 1997 launch of the online journal *Electronic Transactions in Artificial Intelligence* (ETAI), where a two-stage review process was used. First, manuscripts were made available online for interactive community discussion, before later being subject to standard anonymous peer review. The journal stopped publishing in 2002 (Sandewall, 2012). *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* uses a similar system of multi-stage peer review, with manuscripts being made immediately available as “discussion papers” for community comments and peer review (Pöschl, 2012). Other prominent examples are *F1000Research* and the *Semantic Web Journal*.

The benefits to be gained from open pre-review manuscripts is that researchers can assert their priority in reporting findings – they needn’t wait for the sometimes seemingly endless peer review and

publishing process, during which they might fear being scooped. Moreover, getting research out earlier increases its visibility, enables open participation in peer review (where commentary is open to all), and perhaps even, according to Pöschl (2012), increases the quality of initial manuscript submissions.

2.5.6 Open final-version commenting

Open final-version commenting is review or commenting on final "version of record" publications. If the purpose of peer review is to assist in the selection and improvement of manuscripts for publication, then it seems illogical to suggest that peer review can continue once the final version-of-record is made public. Nonetheless, in a literal sense, even the declared fixed version-of-record continues to undergo a process of improvement (occasionally) and selection (perpetually).

As with most areas of communication, the Internet has hugely expanded the range of effective action available for readers to offer their feedback on scholarly works. Where before only formal routes like the letters to the journal or commentary articles offered readers a voice, now a multitude of channels exist. Journals are increasingly offering their own commentary sections. Walker and Rocha da Silva found that of 53 publishing venues reviewed, 24 provided facilities to enable user-comments on published articles – although these were typically not heavily used (Walker and Rocha da Silva, 2015). Researchers seem to see the worth of such functionalities, with almost half of respondents to a 2009 survey believing supplementing peer review with some form of post-publication commentary to be beneficial (Mulligan et al., 2013a). But users can “publish” their thoughts anywhere on the Web – via academic social networks like *Mendeley*, *ResearchGate* and *Academia.edu*, via *Twitter*, or on their own blogs. The reputation of a work hence undergoes continuous evolution as long as it remains the subject of discussion.

Improvements based on feedback happen most obviously in the case of so-called ‘living’ publications like the *Living Reviews* group of three disciplinary journals in the fields of relativity, solar physics and computational astrophysics, publishing invited review articles which allow authors to regularly update their articles to incorporate the latest developments in the field. But even where the published version is anticipated to be the final version, it remains open to future retraction or correction. These days such changes are fueled by social media, as in the 2010 case of #arseniclife, where social media critique over flaws in the methodology of a paper claiming to show a bacterium capable of growing on arsenic resulted in refutations being published in *Science*. The *Retraction Watch* blog is dedicated to publicizing such cases.

A major influence here has been the independent platform *Pubpeer*, which proclaims itself a “post-publication peer review platform”. When its users swarmed to critique a *Nature* paper on STAP (Stimulus-Triggered Acquisition of Pluripotency) cells, PubPeer argued that its “post-publication peer review easily outperformed even the most careful reviewing in the best journal. The papers’ comment

threads on PubPeer have attracted some 40000 viewers. It's hardly su[r]prising they caught issues that three overworked referees and a couple of editors did not. Science is now able to self-correct instantly. Post-publication peer review is here to stay" (PubPeer, 2014).

2.5.7 Open platforms

Open platforms peer review is review facilitated by a different organizational entity than the venue of publication. Recent years have seen the emergence of a group of dedicated platforms which aim to augment the traditional publishing ecosystem by de-coupling review functionalities from journals. Services like RUBRIQ (<http://www.rubriq.com>), Axios Review (<https://axiosreview.org>) and Peerage of Science (<https://www.peerageofscience.org/>) offer "portable" or "independent" peer review. Each platform invites authors to submit manuscripts directly to them, then organises review amongst their own community of reviewers and returns review reports. In the case of RUBRIQ and Peerage of Science, participating journals then have access to these scores and manuscripts and so can contact authors with a publishing offer or to suggest submission. Axios meanwhile, directly forwards the manuscript, along with reviews and reviewer identities, to the author's preferred target journal. The models vary in their details – RUBRIQ, for example, pays its authors, whereas Peerage of Science and Axios operate on a community model where reviewers earn discounts on having their own work reviewed – but all aim in their ways to reduce inefficiencies in the publication process, especially the problem of duplication of effort. Whereas in traditional peer review, a manuscript could undergo peer review at several journals, as it is submitted and rejected, then submitted elsewhere, such services need just one set of reviews which can be carried over to multiple journals until a manuscript finds a home (hence "portable" review).

Other decoupled platforms aim at solving different problems. Publons (<https://publons.com/>) seeks to address the problem of incentive in peer review by turning peer review into measurable research outputs. Publons collects information about peer review from reviewers and publishers to produce reviewer profiles which detail verified peer review contributions that researchers can add to their CVs. Overlay journals like *Discrete Mathematics*, discussed above, are another example of open platforms. Peter Suber (quoted in Cassella and Calvi, 2010) defines the overlay journal as "An open-access journal that takes submissions from the preprints deposited at an archive (perhaps at the author's initiative), and subjects them to peer review.... Because an overlay journal doesn't have its own apparatus for disseminating accepted papers, but uses the pre-existing system of interoperable archives, it is a minimalist journal that only performs peer review." Finally, there are the many venues through which readers can now comment on already-published works (see also "open final version commenting" above), including blogs and social networking sites, as well as dedicated platforms such as PubPeer (<https://pubpeer.com/>).

2.6 Towards a unified, community-endorsed definition of OPR

Based on this analysis, we constructed the following (provisional) definition of “open peer review”:

An umbrella term describing a variety of innovations which “open up” the traditional peer review process by modifying one or more aspects to make it more inclusive, transparent and/or accountable. Primary aspects are Open Identities, Open Reports and Open Participation (possession of one of these traits is usually sufficient to qualify a system as “Open Peer Review”). Secondary characteristics include Openness in Time,² Open Interaction, Open Platforms and others (these aspects are usually insufficient in themselves to qualify a system as “Open Peer Review”, but are often included in many definitions nonetheless).

Feedback on this provisional definition was then collected as part of an online survey of attitudes to OPR which OpenAIRE conducted from 8th September to 7th October 2016, and which received 3062 complete responses. The survey was open to all wishing to take part and distributed via social media, scholarly communications mailing lists, publisher newsletter and, in one case, a publisher internal mailing list (Copernicus publications).

Respondents were strongly in favour of this definition, with the overwhelming majority (84.5%, n= 2587) agreeing with it. Those who disagreed were invited to give feedback. Of these, many reported either feeling unqualified to judge (e.g., respondent 350: “I simply don't know enough to agree”) or that the matter was unimportant to them (e.g., r6079: “I just don't care about a definition. Won't spend time on it”). Within the remaining feedback, justified criticism tackled the style and language used:

- **Style:** Participants advised that the definition was “[t]oo lawyerly” (r4956), “[t]oo complex a definition to provide clarity” (r9111), that it was “confusing and covers too many aspects” (r1262) and reflective of “a long process of finding a compromise” (r2896).
- **Biased language:** Some respondents took issue with the lack of neutrality in the language used in the definition. As one respondent (r4530) said: “A definition should be objective/unbiased. Avoid terms like “innovation”, “inclusive”, “transparent” and “accountable”. This reads like the opinion of an open review supporter, not like a definition.”
- **Imprecision:** Others felt the definition, as an umbrella term covering distinct aspects, was too broad to prove meaningful, e.g., “the options ... are so broad, with various impact, that the definition becomes too hollow” (r7318). Some thought the differences between the various

² “Openness in Time” was presented as a unifying concept for the traits “open pre-review manuscripts” and “open final version commenting” – the key idea being that these are both elements which disrupt the standard temporal order of peer review (submission, review, publication. Based on feedback from users, it was decided that these two concepts were insufficiently similar to group together.

elements, and their varying implications, were too great to warrant their grouping under a common name (r3955). As one respondent put it “Your survey has (correctly in my view) separated out different concepts.... Lumping them together doesn't help” (r7975).

- **Disagreement on core aspects of OPR:** Others disagreed over which aspects should be included in the definition, e.g., “[t]he following is enough: “Open Identities, Open Reports and Open Participation”. Don't make it more complicated!!!” (r4325). Others took issue with distinct aspects. Interestingly, by far the most common trait respondents felt should be *excluded* was open identities (e.g., “I do not think that Open Identities is Open Peer Review as it doesn't “open up” the peer review process to the reader” (r1941)) – even though, as we have seen, this is by far the most common element in existing definitions of OPR. Others meanwhile, felt that OPR should be reserved for just one specific trait such as open participation, open reports or (most commonly) open identities, e.g., “For me, the term ‘open peer review’ means ‘open identity peer review’, but not ‘open reports’, ‘open participation’ and so on” (r5243).

Based on this feedback, the definition was revised to make it shorter, more concrete, less “lawyerly”, more natural and better specify its terms. However, given the very broad ways in which the term OPR is used and the need to find a unifying definition, the objections that the term OPR should be reserved for one specific trait and that an inclusive definition was too broad to be meaningful were both rejected. If we resort to just arguing that OPR identifies one particular trait then we become just another voice adding to the ambiguity of the term. Instead, we offer a unifying, community-endorsed definition which makes clear the essential ambiguity of the term and invites users to be clear about which aspects of OPR (open identities, open reports, open participation, etc.) are under discussion in each case.

OPR definition: Open peer review is an umbrella term for a number of overlapping ways that peer review models can be adapted in line with the ethos of Open Science, including making reviewer and author identities open, publishing review reports and enabling greater participation in the peer review process.

The full list of traits are:

- Open identities:** Authors and reviewers are aware of each other’s identity.
- Open reports:** Review reports are published alongside the relevant article.
- Open participation:** The wider community to able to contribute to the review process.
- Open interaction:** Direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged.
- Open pre-review manuscripts:** Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g., via pre-print servers like ArXiv) in advance of any formal peer review procedures.

- **Open final-version commenting:** Review or commenting on final “version of record” publications
- **Open platforms:** Review is de-coupled from publishing in that it is facilitated by a different organizational entity than the venue of publication.

2.7 Conclusion

We have seen that the term “open peer review” is contested ground. Our aim here has been to provide some clarity as to what is being referred to when we use this term. By analyzing 122 separate definitions from the literature we have identified seven different traits of OPR which all aim at resolving differing peer review problems. Amongst our corpus of definitions we have identified 22 unique configurations of these traits – literally 22 distinct definitions of OPR in the literature. Given such a contested concept, in our view the only sensible way forward is to acknowledge the ambiguity of this term, accepting that it is used as an umbrella concept for a diverse array of peer review innovations. The theme that unifies these diverse traits is Open Science. Factors like opening identities, reports and participation all bespeak the ethos of Open Science in trying, in their differing and overlapping ways, to bring greater transparency, accountability, inclusivity and flexibility to the restricted traditional model of peer review.

3 | ATTITUDES TO OPEN PEER REVIEW

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3.1 Introduction

It is a truism that technological change is easy in comparison to cultural change, and the truism certainly holds for open peer review (OPR). The diverse innovations represented by the term will remain mere niche possibilities unless accepted and taken up by the mainstream. Questions hence arise: What are scholars' current attitudes to peer review? Where do they believe it can be improved? What are their opinions on the various aspects of OPR? What are the cultural barriers that stand in the way of the uptake of such systems? What are the current levels of experience amongst stakeholders with OPR?

In this chapter we will address such questions via means qualitative and quantitative. Firstly, we undertake a review of relevant previous surveys of such attitudes and experiences (Sec. 3.2). Secondly, we present the findings of a series of focus groups with key stakeholders (authors, reviewers, editors, publishers, librarians, etc.) on OPR conducted as part of an international workshop held in Goettingen, Germany in June 2016. Finally, we present the findings from an online survey of more than 3,000 respondents that took place in late 2016. Taken together, the results show that the population of authors, reviewers and editors is warming to OPR, with growing levels of experience and enthusiasm.

3.2 Background

In the last decade, a few large-scale, largely publisher-led studies have gauged attitudes to peer review. Although none have heretofore focused fully on attitudes to OPR, they nonetheless have touched on issues germane to this study. These studies tend to show that although researchers believe peer review is necessary, there is a belief that the current model is sub-optimal. Ware's 2008 survey for the Publishing Research Consortium (PRC), for example, found that an overwhelming majority (85%) agreed that "peer review greatly helps scientific communication" and that even more (around 90%) said their own last published paper had been improved by peer review. Yet while almost two thirds (64%) declared that they were satisfied with the current system of peer review, less than a third (32%) believed that this system is the best possible (Ware, 2008a). A recent follow-up study by the same author reported a slight increase in the desire for improvements in peer review (Ware, 2016). The same studies found that the proportion agreeing that peer review holds back scientific communication had risen a little, from 19% in 2007 to 26% in 2015), and that the proportion who

believe peer review helps scholarly communication had fallen from 85% in 2007 to 75% in 2015 (Ware, 2016).

Given that most studies have been undertaken by publishers, it is perhaps understandable that incentivising and motivating reviewers has been a major feature of these surveys. Across studies, scholars' gave as their main reason for reviewing being part of a reciprocal critical community (Sense about Science, 2009; Taylor & Francis Group, 2016; Ware, 2008a). Yet in absence of financial rewards from the publishers for whom they deliver expert advice, and with no direct acknowledgement from their employing institutions, reviewers are often nonetheless reticent. Taylor & Francis' 2015 survey found that 60% of editors have difficulty in finding qualified reviewers (Taylor & Francis Group, 2016). Relatedly, Ware (2016) found that more than a quarter of respondents thought peer review unsustainable due to there being too few willing reviewers. A major reason for this is revealed by a July 2015 survey of 2,982 respondents by Wiley, which showed that reviewers strongly believed that reviewing is currently insufficiently acknowledged and should be better recognized in institutional evaluation processes, reporting that they would spend more time reviewing if this were the case (Warne, 2016). Against this background, questions of whether particular innovations might encourage or inhibit reviewers to review become pertinent.

Regarding attitudes to OPR, previous studies suggest a steadily growing enthusiasm. Ware (2008) asked respondents to state their preferred option amongst four kinds of review, including open identities and post-publication review. At that time he found a strong preference for double-blind review (56%), followed by single-blind (25%), with only 13% preferring open identities and 5% post-publication review. Indeed, many reviewers (47%) claimed open identities would make them less likely to review for a journal (Ware, 2008b). Sense About Science's 2009 survey found similar scepticism, with just 20% of respondents believing that open identities would be effective in improving peer review, with open reports and open identities performing only a little better (25%). Responses were similar across disciplines (Mulligan et al., 2013b).

However, Taylor & Francis Group's 2015 survey of 7438 researchers shows stakeholders becoming a little more "open" to OPR. It found that views of open identities ("open"), open identities plus open reports ("open and published") and open pre-review manuscripts ("post-publication review") were quite similar, often rated between 5 and 6 out of 10. Editors in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) were less supportive than those in science, technology and medicine (STM) subjects, and editors and reviewers were less supportive than authors. Fewer than half of respondents said that publishing their reports or making identities open would incentivize them to review. The strongest deterrents were publishing the reviewer's report, with anonymous publication only marginally less of a deterrent than publishing their named report (Taylor & Francis Group, 2016).

Running an updated survey for the Publishing Research Consortium in 2015, Ware found that attitudes towards OPR were changing and that support had grown such that 50–70% of researchers were either supportive of or neutral towards open identities review, with 35–55% also holding positive/neutral opinions of also publishing review reports. Ware noted that these levels of acceptance of open identities were in line with the experiences of journals offering reviewers the choice to opt into open identities review systems (Ware, 2016).

A very recent Elsevier survey of authors engaged in a pilot study of publishing review reports (with five journals involved and number of participants unknown) has found that of reviewers who accepted the invitation to review and publish reports, 76% said that open reports had no effect on the wording of their review. Of those who declined, the vast majority (91%) said their decision was not influenced by the open review. A third of editors involved in the pilot said they identified improvements in the overall quality of the review reports (Mehmani, 2016).

Finally, Nicholson and Alperin's small survey (n=79) of self-selected participants found that more than 75% of respondents believed that it would take no extra effort or only moderate extra effort to make their peer reviews suitable for public posting (Nicholson and Alperin, 2016). Amongst their key motivations for doing so would be if tenure/promotion committees explicitly valued them and if their peers also published theirs (Nicholson and Alperin, 2016).

3.3 Focus Groups

The focus groups were conducted as part of an international workshop entitled "Open Peer Review: Models, Benefits and Limitations", held at the University of Goettingen, Germany on 7th June 2016. The workshop aimed to further discussion of innovative models of peer review for scholarly publishing and was attended by 72 participants who represented a comprehensive group of stakeholders including publishers, journal editors, interested researchers (as authors, readers and reviewers), librarians / information specialists, and repository managers.

The groups consisted of interactive discussion groups which built upon themes discussed earlier in the day. Three different topics were open for discussion over two sessions, with each participant able to join two groups. The topics were: varieties of OPR, stakeholder engagement in OPR, and ethical challenges in OPR. Each group was chaired by a moderator who introduced the discussion themes. Participants then discussed structured questions in sub-groups before reporting back their opinions to the group. Participants were further asked to define new questions for the second group. In the next session, the second group was given an overview of the opinions of the first group and invited to build upon or disagree with them, as well as being asked to address the new questions defined by the first group. Each breakout group was assigned a note taker (Emilie Hermans, Frank Manista and Arvid Deppe), whose notes provide the basis for the summaries given here.

3.3.1 Focus Group 1: Varieties of OPR

This group worked towards a deeper understanding of what OPR entails and how its heterogeneity can be (intellectually, terminologically and practically) handled. It aimed to:

- Try to develop a joint understanding of peer review, OPR and the differences between them
- Bring together different forms of OPR and discuss them in their particularities, benefits and drawbacks
- Increase sensitivity for the heterogeneous nomenclature of OPR variants and identify the most crucial ambiguities

Q1: What is Peer Review? Participants defined peer review as a community process of quality control/assessment most closely associated with journals, but also applicable to monographs, grant applications and so on. Communities consist of people with an expertise in a given area. This expertise need not be just a matter of qualifications but also experience and hence peers are not limited to academia. Peers could also come from other practitioners in the field (industry), secondary education (teachers specializing in certain topics) or citizen scientists. This conversation then led to consideration of what quality assurance means. Participants argued that quality control in peer review means helping to improve an article and/or identify mistakes, but also a filtering function to help define what is important. This leads to the question of whether peers are really equipped to determine the significance of a piece of research. Finally, since it decides whether something should be part of the scientific dialogue or not, peer review also includes an aspect of power. One participant noted that peer review is also defined by its process and the control it exerts over the process of academic publication.

Q2. What is Open Peer Review? What forms of OPR (and what forms of openness) can you identify? Originally presented as two questions, the groups decided to answer these questions together. OPR was very roughly defined as being peer review with any “open” processes. The answers to what is or should be open were as heterogeneous as the field of OPR itself, and included concrete ideas like post-publication review, open discussion, open reviewer identities and possible interaction (“comment on the comments”). It also provoked questions about whether we meant openness to the author or to the public, openness of all the comments or just the decision letter, and openness during or after the peer review process. Some groups saw open identities of reviewers as crucial to the definition of OPR. Still others saw openly published reviews as a minimal characteristic, but another did not consider it necessary to disclose everything in a review, but only those aspects needed to see how a decision was reached. There was also an emphasis on open participation and the crowdsourcing of comments – OPR drew repeated comparison to websites like Airbnb or TripAdvisor. Finally participants noted that OPR should not be defined in isolation as it is only one part of a wider scholarly communications ecosystem. Other elements that participants felt should be included in a definition of OPR were citable reviews,

portable and cascading peer review, review of reviews, pre/post-publication review, filter vs. feedback functions, and the openness of process versus the openness of results.

Q3. What forms of OPR do you think are the most important? Participants agreed that there are many different forms of OPR which address different needs for differing communities. The most important criteria are that OPR should ensure scientific accuracy and produce good science. Additionally, there were two new beneficial aspects of OPR mentioned here: the educational benefit of transparent, open access processes for young researchers and the machine readability of review outputs/metadata.

Q4. Which forms of OPR could make peer review worse in your opinion? Why? Participants voiced concern about the potential for unconfirmed/unreviewed results to be cited prematurely as a result of post-publication review. Unreviewed scientific results might find their way into the media, to be misunderstood or misused and thus cause hysteria (for example in medical research). But one participant countered this argument by saying that the media would learn that pre-prints are not reviewed and thus not to be reported. This participant continued that in fact, such episodes of media hysteria can in fact educate the public to be skeptical about scientific results, to come to see that the scientific method is not infallible. Another major concern voiced about open identity OPR was the potential for early career researchers to risk a backlash from more senior researchers should they criticize them publicly. OPR also has the potential to be abused by, for example, “gaming the system” (authors reviewing their own or friends’ work) – although it was pointed out that although this might be true of an open participation system, where reviewers were self-selecting, it would not be true of an open identity and/or open reports system where reviewers would have to stand publicly by their words. Finally, coming back to open commentary, there was a fear of losing quality control standards due to social media-like commenting fields (“anarchy in commenting/decisions”).

3.3.2 Focus Group 2: Stakeholder Engagement in OPR

Attempts to open identities or publish review reports go against a well-established system and hence often face mistrust, lack of interest or active resistance. This group therefore sought to better understand the roles, motivations and fears of authors and reviewers, and to discuss ways to engage authors and reviewers in OPR processes. It aimed to discuss different functions and importance of mediation, understand what motivates author/reviewers to join OPR processes and to discuss incentives and arguments for participation in OPR.

Q1. How important do you think (e.g., editor) mediation is in OPR? Why? All groups considered mediation very important to support authors, reviewers and their interaction. Participants felt that support should not be limited to initiating and managing the interaction itself, but also giving technical help and advising on difficult situations such as guiding authors how to handle contradictory reviews. Additionally, mediation can include questions of ethics, solving conflicts or filtering comments on highly

contentious topics. There was some suggestion that mediators should also ensure quality control, but this was deemed controversial and others argued that it is debatable whether this classical editor function is still required in OPR. Nevertheless, participants noted that the need for mediation shall vary depending on the discipline and the type of content under review (results, data, software etc.). Finally, there was some suggestion that some of the mediation currently done by editors might be better achieved by automation (e.g. automatic selection of reviewers via citations), authors and/or the community.

Q2. What possible incentives can you think of to engage reviewers? Groups agreed that OPR potentially poses extra work for reviewers and might be more time-consuming than classical peer review. It therefore stands to reason to offer incentives for reviewing openly. Most suggestions were based on the idea of rewarding reviewers, financially or symbolically. This could be simply by offsetting reviewer work with contributions towards author article processing charges (APCs) for their future publications (as is currently done by [PeerJ](#), for example), or even by formally transferring APCs to RPCs (review processing costs). Another idea put forth was the potential to have funders/institutions officially contribute towards payments for review work to individuals or institutions. However, others felt strongly that the current system of social incentives should not be undermined by financial ones. Social incentives relate to career rewards focusing on recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, and so on. Recognition might be granted via altmetrics or informally via a social media. It was noted that such systems benefit from, if not require, persistent identifiers like ORCID, DOI etc. Such credit systems also have an aspect of the “gamification” of peer review. Other possible motivations mentioned were social pressure to review as well as policies/mandates by government or funders (as is apparently the case in Sweden). Open Reviews would also simplify collaborative review (where many reviewers each review a different section), which again reduces work for each reviewer. One participant argued that since OPR might be seen as an incentive itself, the focus should be on tackling the obstacles rather than creating new incentives.

Q3. What concerns do you think authors might have about OPR? Which argument could help against these fears? The groups identified the fear of being criticized publicly as the main impediment for authors, spurred on by fears of “washing dirty laundry in public” and the “abuse of power dynamics”. Further issues were the fear of having to share the limelight with reviewers making major points and of losing control over the – potentially never ending – peer review process. Finally, authors in OPR may miss the prestige of coming through the review process of a highly ranked journal. On the other hand, reviewers might also be afraid of being accused in public of making flawed criticism or misunderstanding a paper, and this may be a huge disincentive – especially for early career researchers. There were no particular arguments made against these fears. Participants’ preferred strategies seem rather to be to emphasize the benefits of OPR for authors, such as more constructive, less judgmental

reviews and the chance to interact, improve and thereby produce better science. Engagement accordingly needs education in OPR through good information and dissemination activities. It is especially about working on politeness and building trust, making OPR understood as a “chance to improve your work” or, more generally, changing the culture of review.

Q4. Do you think different disciplines will vary in their attitudes towards OPR? How? Discussions brought up a lot of disciplinary differences that participants think need to be taken into consideration when thinking about OPR. First of all disciplines seem to differ ideologically in their attitude towards openness in general, and so perhaps disciplines which are open or hostile to Open Access will hold similar views towards OPR. Further, there are differences in, for example, sensitivity to time taken, publication models, the culture of rejection (e.g. in medicine it is normal to have high number of rejections), special processes (e.g. scooping is a concern where research can be copied easily) and reviewing effort (science is easier to peer review than humanities). Disciplines also differ in size, which can have different effects. In small communities for instance researchers often know each other in person which may be problematic. On the other hand, small close-knit communities may foster a greater sense of duty. Participants were of one voice that despite these differences, OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

3.3.3 Focus Group 3: Ethical Challenges of OPR

A lot of the arguments made against closed peer review are of an ethical nature: reviewer bias, difficulties with authors/reviewer anonymity, opaqueness or subjectivity of reviews and even the question of whether any review was done at all. The differing forms of OPR may seem to address many of these problems, but it is no panacea. The idea of this group was to raise awareness of the ethical problems that OPR can raise and discuss ways of tackling them. It aimed to identify the most pressing ethical issues, discuss ethics in OPR in response to concrete challenges and to find suitable solutions, with a special focus on ethical considerations concerning early career researchers.

Q1. What in your opinion are the most pressing ethical issues in the context of OPR? Participants felt that ethical concerns around OPR encompassed diverse aspects. First of all, with open identity peer review, there is the question of whether it is of higher ethical priority to let the author know who is judging him or not to force the reviewer to reveal his identity. Another aspect is the possibility of disadvantages for authors. For instance, does rejection at one journal foster hasty judgement and influence the chances of gaining acceptance at another journal? One participant noted that the first opinion stated in a public discussion can often inordinately influence the direction of the ensuing discussion. Although participants recognized that there might be potential conflicts in some specific cases where reviewer and author identities were open, it was generally agreed that radical

transparency would solve more problems on the whole than it would produce. Another important issue is that OPR opens the door for potentially unethical behaviours. In post-publication OPR, for instance, if an author's ideas are made public in advance of full publication, others might appropriate those ideas without giving due credit. Another scenario concerning open commenting platforms is reviewer identification. How can we be sure a person is who they claim to be? In addition to these questions of how to formulate new workflows and codes of conduct for new ethical issues raised by OPR, participants emphasized the need to communicate the ethical benefits of OPR.

Q2. Consider this case: An author is unhappy with a very critical pre-publication OPR. He/she demands their work be withdrawn from the process and the OPR taken offline completely. Would you agree to the author's demands? Why/why not? Groups' opinions tended to depend on the circumstances but the dominant answer was that in such a situation, openness should prevail:

- The answer would be NO if the content of the review were considered fair scientific discussion. Additionally, it needs to be considered that the controversy might be interesting for the future development of science – controversy often attends radical ideas, but radical ideas push science forwards. It was concluded that the point of OPR would be missed completely if only positive reviews were allowed to be open.
- The answer could be YES if there were no scientific benefit/interest in keeping the review available. This could be the case for unscientific discourse or personal/insulting comments. Special consideration could also be taken to protect young researchers.

Furthermore the answer would naturally depend on the specific conditions of the peer reviewing process. One participant suggested that a solution to this problem could be to invite another independent reviewer to give a new point of view. Participants were clear that this case and the discussions around it show the importance of (1) a code of conduct, including an explicit statement and even legal agreement that provides clarity on the conditions under which the OPR will be conducted for author, reviewer and editor, and (2) the need for ongoing human mediation in OPR.

Q3. What ethical concerns do you have about (1) editors selecting reviewers, (2) authors selecting reviewers? The groups agreed that editors usually have too little knowledge of specific sub-disciplines to choose reviewers with a maximum of competence in the field. Authors, on the other hand, know their peers but may be biased in their choices. A solution could be an algorithm-based selection. Most ideas of solving or reducing the problem focused on transparency and self-regulation: as OPR opens the whole reviewing process, conflicts of interest can be identified, biases can be recognized and arguments can be scrutinized by community. This can be supported by additional oversight measures such as the review of reviews. If the reviewing system is participatory or based on self-selecting reviewers, the problem of selection would of course disappear, although replaced by new specific challenges.

Q4. Are there special issues to be considered regarding young researchers? Participants raised several ethical issues that specifically affected young researchers. First of all, young researchers might be afraid of publicly criticizing senior researchers, fearing negative consequences for their careers. On the other hand, seniors might be worried young researchers might not review to their standards of critique. Although young researchers might bring a fresh perspective, have more time and be more motivated and precise in their reviewing, they may not have enough experience to fulfil the task. This may be seen as a problem when reviews are open, but on the other hand, OPR can also work as an educational tool for young reviewers on reviewing, reviewing processes and potentially on ethical issues as well.

3.3.4 Focus group conclusions

Discussion across all areas showed that variety and experimentation are key to the success of OPR. Participants were in broad agreement that the differing kinds of OPR have a lot of potential to improve peer review, but they were also united that no one model will fit all disciplines or overcomes all obstacles. Therefore different OPR initiatives and approaches are to be welcomed for the shared goal of producing better science through openness and transparency. Let a thousand flowers bloom, so to speak.

Yet as these variants crop up, it is important that we are able to distinguish readily between them, and to recognize what actually works in which contexts. The heterogeneity of views on what OPR is that came up during the focus groups just drive home the fact that we need a better overview of the different models, including perhaps agreement on what minimum levels of openness are necessary to categorize a process as open, and – most importantly – a common, community-agreed taxonomy of OPR should be developed.

OPR is a process which involves many different stakeholder groups, and the unease of some reviewers, authors and editors toward OPR is legitimate and must be faced with evidence of its effectiveness and advocacy regarding its benefits. This will be helped by efforts to reward the work of peer review (but “socially” via citation credit and such rather than financially). Introducing OPR requires cultural change, which is notoriously difficult. Participants were of one voice, however, that OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

On the ethical side, it is clear that OPR is no panacea and that while it may resolve some ethical issues regarding accountability and bias with classical peer review, it nonetheless poses new problems. Discussions indicated the importance of agreeing on common ethical rules and committing them bindingly. Our participants generally agreed that OPR promises to improve peer review, and made plain

that its ethical benefits – transparency, accountability, openness – should be made a key part of arguments in its favour.

To draw general conclusions, we can say:

- OPR processes need to be made transparent and comparable.
- A common terminology is needed as a basis of comparing (effectiveness of) OPR models.
- Different modes of mediation need to be tested.
- Ways to acknowledge and reward reviewers appropriately need to be found.
- Development of mandates and policies should be supported.
- Differences and particularities of disciplines must be acknowledged and taken into account.
- A common code of conduct should be created, especially taking into account the needs of young researchers.

3.4 OpenAIRE OPR Survey

Between 8th September and 7th October 2016, OpenAIRE held a survey designed to aid the development of appropriate OPR approaches by providing evidence about the attitudes of authors, editors and reviewers towards OPR, their reservations and needs, as well as to gauging current levels of experience and reservation with different types of OPR. A supplementary aim was to collect feedback on a provisional definition of OPR as created during another strand of work.

3.4.1 Methodology

The survey was conducted via an openly accessible online questionnaire (using the scientific survey platform SoSci, www.soscisurvey.de). Questions for the survey were developed in line with the concerns expressed in the workshop focus groups, with additional input crowdsourced via Twitter. The key survey foci were: attitudes to OPR, levels of experience with OPR, and definitions of OPR (including feedback on our OPR terminology/definition).

The survey was open online from 8th September to 7th October 2016 and received a total of 3062 complete responses (a further 635 responses were discarded as incomplete). The survey was open to all wishing to take part and distributed via social media, scholarly communications mailing lists, publisher newsletters and, in one case, a publisher internal mailing list (Copernicus Publications). The latter, which directly targeted around 41000 authors, reviewers and editors, created a significant spike in responses (cf. Figure 7), generating almost a third of the total responses in a single day. Given this mode of dissemination, it is likely that the sample is somewhat skewed towards those with more experience of and interest in open access publishing and new publishing models than would otherwise

would have been the case in a randomized trial. Overall, we consider 3062 responses for the analysis, constituting all complete survey responses.

FIGURE 7: RESPONSES TO THE SURVEY OVER TIME (8TH SEPTEMBER TO 7TH OCTOBER 2016)

The data is available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.439531>

3.4.2 Demographics

Age: The majority of respondents provided information about their age group (n=3049): 15 were under 24 (0.5%), 555 between 25 and 34 (18.2%), 918 between 35 and 44 (30.1%), 738 between 45 and 54 (24.2%), 573 between 55 and 64 (18.8%), and 250 over 65 years old (8.2%).

Region: Respondents residing in Europe comprised 61.0% of total responses, followed by America (22.4%), Asia (9.9%), Oceania (4.0%), and Africa (2.6%).

Discipline: Responses by discipline were heavily skewed towards the natural sciences, which is due to the chosen mode of dissemination of the survey (cf. Table 1 and Figure 2). Overall, there were 90.0% (2757 responses) responses from science, technology and medical (STM) disciplines versus 8.1% (249 responses) responses from the social sciences and humanities (SSH), and 1.8% belonged to other disciplines (56 responses). When comparing STM and SSH responses we will leave out the cohort of other disciplines.

TABLE 1: RESPONSES BY DISCIPLINE

Discipline	Frequency	Percentage
Earth and Environmental Sciences	1274	41.61
Biology	447	14.6
Health Sciences	444	14.5
Physics	165	5.39
Technology and Engineering	137	4.47
Social Sciences	112	3.66
Computer Sciences / IT	80	2.61
Chemistry	73	2.38
Mathematics and Statistics	63	2.06
Agriculture and Food Sciences	60	1.96
Other disciplines	56	1.83
Psychology and Philosophy	50	1.63
Languages and Literature	35	1.14
History	23	0.75
Economics	18	0.59
Arts and Architecture	14	0.46
Law and Political Sciences	11	0.36

FIGURE 8: RESPONSES BY DISCIPLINE (HSS DISCIPLINES CLUSTERED)

ROLES IN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION AND EXPERIENCE WITH OPR

Our respondents reported having strong experience of academic authorship and reviewing. Of all respondents, when asked about their roles in scholarly communication (multiple choices were allowed, on average about 2.4 options were selected) 2923 as author (95.5%), 2681 as reviewer (87.6%), 1326 had acted as editor (43.3%), 137 as publisher (4.5%), and 92 in other roles (3%).

Of all respondents, when asked about their experience with OPR (multiple choices were allowed, on average about 1.9 options were selected) 594 had acted as editor (19.4%), 1930 as author (63%), 68 as publisher (2.2%), 1808 as reviewer (59%), and 35 in other roles (1.1%) (cf. Figure 9). Overall, over three out of four (76.2%, n=2333) of all respondents reported having some experience with OPR as an editor, author or reviewer.

FIGURE 9: EXPERIENCES WITH OPR BY ROLE

Comparing respondents with STM vs. HSS backgrounds different levels of experience with OPR could be observed (cf. Fig. 10). Almost 2/3 (1812 respondents, 65.7%) of all STM respondents had experience with OPR as an author, four out of five as a reviewer (1697 resp., 61.6%), about 1 out of five (542 resp., 19.7%) as an editor, and a few as a publisher (48 resp., 1.7%). In HSS subjects, levels of experience with OPR as authors and reviewers was substantially lower: about two out of five HSS respondents had OPR experience as an author (99 resp., 39.8%) and just over a third as a reviewer (92 resp., 37%). However, the share of respondents with OPR experience as an editor was at almost the same level (44 resp., 17.7%) and somewhat higher as a publisher (13 resp., 5.2%).

FIGURE 10: EXPERIENCES WITH OPR - SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE (STM) VS. HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES (HSS)

Regarding particular OPR traits, a majority (55.8%) had had experience with open reports, but high numbers also reported experience with open identities (45.4%) and open participation (44.2%). Overall, 72.1% of all respondents had contributed to one of these OPR activities (cf. Figure 11 and Table 2).

FIGURE 11: LEVELS OF EXPERIENCE WITH OPR AS AUTHOR AND/OR REVIEWER

TABLE 2: LEVEL OF EXPERIENCE WITH OPR AS AUTHOR AND/OR REVIEWER

		Overall	Open reports	Open identities	Open participation
yes	Freq	2207	1712	1389	1354
	Perc	72.1%	55.9%	45.4%	44.2%
no	Freq	848	1350	1673	1708
	Perc	27.9%	44.1%	54.6%	55.8%

3.4.3 Results

GENERAL ATTITUDES TO OPEN SCIENCE

We began by asking respondents to state how satisfied they were with the current peer review system. Although there is no single monolithic peer review process, we here assume respondents understood this to mean “traditional” peer review as identified in section 2 (single/double blind, unpublished review reports, closed participation procedures, etc.). This question was chosen to replicate a question asked in several previous studies (Ware, 2015). In part this was done to monitor if and to what extent our data collection method may have skewed our sample towards an audience more receptive to innovations in peer review. Although our respondents were generally in favour they were markedly less enthusiastic than those in previous studies, which together present a remarkably consistent picture of general attitudes towards peer review. All three studies found that between 65-69% of respondents were either satisfied or very satisfied with the current system, while just 9-12% reported being dissatisfied or very dissatisfied. This contrasts with our sample, where 56.4% reported being satisfied/very satisfied, while 20.6% were dissatisfied/very dissatisfied.

When asked about the current state of scholarly communication there seems to be a reasonable level of satisfaction: of those who expressed an opinion almost every second respondent believed that scholarly communication works well (45.1%), while almost a third disagreed (31.6%).

FIGURE 12: OVERALL SATISFACTION WITH PEER REVIEW: WARE (2015, N=2004) VS. OPENAIRE STUDY (2016, N=3001)

TABLE 3: OVERALL SATISFACTION WITH PEER REVIEW: WARE (N=2004) VS. OPENAIRE STUDY (N=3001)

		Very satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied
Ware 2015	Freq	160	1162	501	160
	Perc	8.0	58.0	22.2	8.0
OpenAIRE 2016	Freq	218	1474	691	503
	Perc	7.3	49.1	23.0	16.8

Our sample was heavily in favour of Open Access to publications (88.2% agreed while only 4.1% disagreed) and research data (80.3% agreed, 7.8% disagreed), and a majority was in favour of OPR. Although enthusiasm was lower for the latter, still 60.3% (1733 respondents) believed that OPR should be common scholarly practice, while just 18.1% (518 respondents) disagreed. The questions on general attitudes to Open Science provoked decisive responses, with fewer than 50 “don’t know” responses for three out of the four questions; the “don’t knows” for the fourth question, on OPR, were higher, however (6.3%, 194 respondents, not considered for Figure 6).

FIGURE 13: GENERAL ATTITUDES TOWARDS ASPECTS OF OPEN SCIENCE

We combine the negative (strongly disagree / disagree), neutral and don't know vs. positive (strongly agree / agree) attitudes for the views on open access, open access to research data and OPR. The contingency tables indicate that these preferences may not be independent, positive attitudes often seem to come together, e.g. nearly three quarters (73.9%, n=2264) of all respondents support both open access to publications and research data (cf. Tables 3 a,b,c). Based on this observation we test the following hypothesis: Attitudes towards open access (OA) to publications and towards open access to research data are independent. A Chi-square test of independence shows that this hypothesis can be rejected ($X^2=322.46$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). Similarly, the hypothesis that the variables of attitudes towards open access to publications and OPR are independent can be rejected ($X^2=322.46$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$), and finally also for open access to research data and OPR ($X^2=279.27$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). It must be noted that although the variables are related this relationship is not necessarily causal.

**TABLE 4: CONTINGENCY TABLE OF OPEN ACCESS TO PUBLICATIONS
VS. OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA**

OA to publ. / OA to data	negative	neutral / don't know	positive
negative	56	23	43
neutral / don't know	37	120	113
positive	140	266	2264

**TABLE 5: CONTINGENCY TABLE OF OPEN ACCESS TO PUBLICATIONS
VS. OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA**

OA to publ. / OPR	negative	neutral / don't know	positive
negative	73	24	25
neutral / don't know	77	132	61
positive	368	655	1647

TABLE 6: CONTINGENCY TABLE OF OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA VS. OPR

OA to data / OPR	negative	neutral / don't know	positive
negative	111	60	62
neutral / don't know	89	170	150
positive	318	581	1521

We next asked about attitudes to particular aspects of OPR (see above for description of the meaning of each of these traits). Our respondents on the whole tended to think that most aspects would improve peer review (cf. Fig. 7). The clear exception is open identities, with 50.8% (1461 of 2878 respondents who expressed an opinion) of our respondents believing that open identities will make peer review worse or much worse. Given that open identities is the trait most commonly found in definitions of OPR (present in 110 of 122 definitions we studied), this is highly surprising and perhaps reflects persistent concerns that opening reviewer identities will lead to a lack of control. In particular, protection from undue influence may not be given, making it more difficult for particularly junior

researchers to give candid feedback for fear of possible reprisals from aggrieved authors (whether this actually happens or not is another matter, of course).

Also of interest is the observed level of enthusiasm for a secondary aspect of OPR, namely open interaction where direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged. This aspect is supported by over two thirds of all respondents (68.0%, 1976 of 2904 expressing an opinion). Given that open interaction is a fairly incremental change compared to other more radical elements of OPR, this level of support suggests that this is presently the easiest route to “open” peer review processes.

Further aspects which were supported by about every second respondent are the publication of peer review reports (58.8%, 1722 of 2928 respondents), the ability to comment on the final version of record (55%, 1471 of 2676 respondents) and the wider participation of the community in peer review processes (51%, 1463 of 2870 respondents).

Statements on how peer review may be modified

FIGURE 14: "WILL "X" MAKE PEER REVIEW BETTER, WORSE, OR HAVE NO EFFECT?"

It must be noted that for some of these aspects the level of indecision was rather high, in particular for open platforms, where about a quarter of respondents opted for “don’t know” (cf. Table 4).

TABLE 7: NUMBER OF RESPONSES TO STATEMENTS ON HOW PEER REVIEW MIGHT BE MODIFIED (SDV=STANDARD DEVIATION)

	mean, sdv		much worse	worse	neutral	better	much better	don't know
Open reports	3.51	Freq	139	469	598	1201	521	134
	1.10	Perc	4.5	15.3	19.5	39.2	17.0	4.4
Open identity	2.73	Freq	512	949	508	615	294	184
	1.26	Perc	16.7	31.0	16.6	20.1	9.6	6.0
Open participation	2.28	Freq	222	582	603	1094	369	192
	1.15	Perc	7.3	19.0	19.7	35.7	12.1	6.3
Open interaction	3.68	Freq	119	353	456	1385	591	158
	1.06	Perc	3.9	11.5	14.9	45.2	19.3	5.2
Open pre-review manuscripts	3.08	Freq	354	655	640	729	430	254
	1.27	Perc	11.6	21.4	20.9	23.8	14.0	8.3
Open final-version commenting	3.48	Freq	98	342	765	1127	344	386
	0.99	Perc	3.2	11.2	25.0	36.8	11.2	12.6
Open platforms	3.27	Freq	157	354	729	677	298	847
	1.10	Perc	5.1	11.6	23.8	22.1	9.7	27.7

ATTITUDES TO OPEN IDENTITIES

On the whole, the pushback against open identities that we observed above continued throughout respondents' answers to questions on this theme (cf. Figure 8). They strongly believed (73.9% agree/strongly agree, 2175 of 2944 respondents) that reviewers should be allowed to choose whether or not to make their identities open and that potential reviewers would be less likely to review for journals that practiced such peer review (67.2% agree/strongly agree, 1858 of 2767 respondents). Almost two thirds also believed that open identities would lead to reviewers being less likely to deliver strong criticisms (65.2% agree/strongly agree, 1909 of 2926 respondents).

However, our respondents did, on the whole, seem to believe that making reviewer identities open would increase review quality (44% agree/strongly agree vs. 35% disagree/strongly disagree, n=2908). Moreover, roughly the same numbers believed that open reviewer identities was fairer to authors (44% agree/strongly agree vs. 30% disagree/strongly disagree, n=2915). This indicates that although our respondents see worth in open identities peer review, they remain skeptical about its effects and advocate choice in its implementation.

FIGURE 15: ATTITUDES TOWARDS OPEN IDENTITIES

ATTITUDES TO OPEN REPORTS

Respondents generally see worth in publishing review reports (cf. Figure 9). Almost 2 out of 3 respondents (65.4%, 1933 out of 2956 respondents) agree or strongly agree that they provide useful information for the reader, and 3 out of 5 respondents (60.2%, 1765 out of 2930 respondents) believe publishing reports will increase review quality. Respondents largely rejected the idea that open reports would be a disincentive for authors. However, similar to open identities (although with a less pronounced effect), they believe that publishing reviews might disinhibit reviewers and lead to less strong criticisms.

FIGURE 16: ATTITUDES TO OPEN REPORTS

ATTITUDES TO OPEN PARTICIPATION

Attitudes to open participation were mixed (cf. Figure 10). Although only 27.7% (772 out of 2789 respondents) disagreed that close circles of reviewers hold back innovative research, respondents were not wholly enthusiastic about opening participation. There was a fairly even split to the suggestion that everybody, regardless of qualifications or background, should be able to participate in the review process (45% agree/strongly agree vs. 38% disagree/strongly disagree, n=2913 responses). The recurrent concern about whether people will voluntarily participate was also present for our respondents, 85% (2460 out of 2902 respondents) of whom thought that reviewers are more likely to review if invited.

FIGURE 17: ATTITUDES TO OPEN PARTICIPATION

ATTITUDES TO OTHER OPR TRAITS

A more positive attitude towards open interaction was reflected in the belief of three out of four respondents (76.5% agree/strongly agree, n=2257 responses) that increased interaction between authors and reviewers will result in better publications (cf. Figure 11).

Regarding making peer review processes more open in terms of time, support was less pronounced. Modest support was observed for making manuscripts openly available before peer review begins (32%, 919 responses). Just over a quarter of respondents, meanwhile, believe that post-publication commentary (online commentary such as blog articles, journal clubs and social media commentary) forms a legitimate part of peer review (28.8%, n=807 responses).

FIGURE 18: ATTITUDES TOWARDS OTHER ASPECTS

SOME DISCIPLINARY DIFFERENCES

Overall satisfaction with the peer review system used by scholarly journals seems to strongly vary across disciplines (cf. Figure 12). Some disciplines seem to be rather satisfied while for some a high

degree of dissatisfaction was expressed. However, it is possible that there was some self-selection, with those more critical of the current system choosing to participate in the survey. In addition for some disciplines there were only few responses, e.g. in several humanities research areas (see Table 1). For the STM research areas a majority of respondents seem to be satisfied, e.g. respondents from the earth and environmental sciences (64.3% very satisfied / satisfied vs. 14.3%), agriculture and food science (61.4% vs. 14.1%), physics and astronomy (55.5% vs. 19.5%) and health sciences (57% vs. 19.6%). Exceptions were mathematics and statistics where only about one third of respondents (35.5%) seem to be satisfied while over one fourth (25.8%) are not satisfied, and similarly computer sciences / IT with only every third respondent satisfied, with a similar amount not satisfied (38.1% vs. 34.2% respectively). High levels of dissatisfaction were expressed by respondents from arts and architecture, history and archeology and psychology and philosophy (between 40 and 45% very dissatisfied / dissatisfied).

FIGURE 19: DEGREE OF SATISFACTION WITH THE PEER REVIEW SYSTEM ACROSS SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES

When asked if OPR should be a common scholarly practice for most research areas a majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed (cf. Figure 13), while much less pronounced than views on open access to publications or research data. Support was particularly high from economics, social sciences, psychology and philosophy, arts and architecture and other disciplines with over 2/3 of all respondents. The strongest reservations towards opening up peer review could be observed from agriculture and food sciences, languages and literature, biology and life sciences, physics and astronomy as well as mathematics and statistics with about one out of four respondents disagreeing or strongly disagreeing.

Open Peer Review should be common scholarly practice.

FIGURE 20: VIEWS ON OPR BY SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE

For almost all research areas a majority of respondents felt that making reviewer identities open will make reviewers less willing to review for such journals (between about every second and over 3 out of 4 respondents, cf. Figure 14). In a very few disciplinary areas, this perception was a little less

pronounced: e.g., for the law and political sciences about every third respondent agreed or strongly agreed with this view.

Potential reviewers are less likely to agree to review for journals that make reviewer identities open.

FIGURE 21: PERCEPTION OF REVIEWER’S WILLINGNESS TO REVIEW FOR JOURNALS WHICH MAKE REVIEWER IDENTITIES OPEN

GENERATIONAL DIFFERENCES

When asked if the current system of scholarly communication works well, there was significantly less agreement in the younger generation of researchers, in particular when comparing the under 35 year-olds with the generations 45 and older. For a MANOVA significance analysis we clustered the under 25 year-olds with the generation 25-34 as there were only very few responses for the younger cohort.

Overall, the younger generations provided somewhat stronger support for the general statements on openness practices. There was a significantly stronger support for open access amongst those aged 35 and under compared with the generations 45-54 ($p < 0.001$), 55-54 ($p < 0.001$) and 65 and over

($p < 0.001$). Also the generation 35-44 expressed somewhat stronger support for open access than the generations 45-54 ($p = 0.011$) and 55-64 ($p < 0.001$).

Making research data open access was significantly more strongly endorsed as a common scholarly practice by the under 35s compared to the generations 45 and older ($p < 0.05$ in all three cases) and the 35-44 year-olds compared to the 55-64 year-olds ($p < 0.01$). In addition, OPR was significantly stronger supported as a common scholarly practice when comparing the under 35 with all other age groups ($p < 0.05$ in all cases) and when comparing the 35-44 and 45-54 and 55-64 year-olds ($p < 0.05$ in both cases). For an overview see also Figure 15.

FIGURE 22: OPR AS A COMMON SCHOLARLY PRACTICE - VIEWS BY AGE GROUP

3.4.4 Discussion and Future Developments

Our results suggest that OPR is currently moving to the mainstream, with high levels of experience amongst authors, reviewers and editors, most of whom have positive attitudes toward it. A clear majority (60.8%) of respondents believe that OPR should be common scholarly practice. Support for OPR is not as strong as for other areas of Open Science. Almost 9 in 10 of our respondents thought

Open Access to publications should be common scholarly practice, while four fifths of respondents thought the same of open research data. That OPR is not as favoured as Open Access and Open Data is unsurprising, since the latter two are more established in the scientific conversation. Nonetheless, our findings reveal that being in favour of OPR is correlated to being in favour of Open Access and Open Data, suggesting that researchers are increasingly in favour of the Open Science agenda as a whole. Hence, it might be postulated that as knowledge about and experience with OPR grows, it will come to have similar support as these more established elements of Open Science. Certainly, there is a generational element, with significantly stronger levels of support for OPR amongst younger generations.

Our sample demonstrated a very high level of familiarity with OPR - more than three out of four respondents reported having some experience with OPR as an editor, author or reviewer (19% as editors, 63% as authors and 59% as reviewers). As might be expected of what are (in relation to scholarly communication) often perceived to be more conservative disciplines, levels of experience with OPR as authors and reviewers was substantially lower amongst those from Humanities and Social Sciences. Regarding particular OPR traits, a majority (55.8%) had experience with open reports, but high numbers also reported experience with open identities (45.4%) and open participation (44.2%). While admittedly our open method of distribution likely skews towards those with more experience of and interest in open access publishing and new publishing models than would have been the case in a randomized trial, and hence these levels of experience can be assumed to be somewhat higher than in the general population of researchers, these are still impressive results which demonstrate emphatically that OPR is no longer a fringe phenomenon. Moreover, the fact that our sample was perhaps more experienced with OPR than the average population lends extra credence to respondents' reported views of OPR their attitudes, which are then more likely to be based on *a posteriori* experience than *a priori* supposition. Our respondents' general enthusiasm for OPR was not uniform to all the traits of OPR, however. Asked to rate whether individual traits would make peer review better or worse, six traits found a majority of respondents in favour, with open interaction (68% in favour) the most popular. The least popular trait amongst our sample by a wide margin, and the only one which the majority believe will actually make peer review worse, was open identities (51% against, 31% in favour). In the remainder of this discussion we will address attitudes to each of these traits in turn.

Open identities: Perhaps the most surprising finding in the survey was respondents' negative reaction of open identities peer review, where authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identities. As just stated, this was by far the most negatively perceived OPR trait, with a majority believing it would make peer review worse. This is especially surprising since open identities is often the hallmark trait of OPR within existing definitions within the literature (see sec. 2.5.1). This pushback continued

throughout respondents' answers to questions on this theme, with strong beliefs that reviewers should be allowed to choose whether or not to make their identities open (74%) and that potential reviewers would be less likely to review for journals that practiced such peer review (67%). This was so despite seeming recognition of the potential benefits of open identities: asked whether making reviewer identities open would increase review quality, 44% agreed whereas 35% disagreed, and asked whether open reviewer identities was fairer to authors, 44% agreed whereas only 30% disagreed. That respondents should reject open identities despite seeing its ethical advantages probably relates to their views on a final question, whether reviewers would be less likely to deliver strong criticisms were their identities known to authors. 65% of respondents thought that open reviewer identities would lead to less strong criticisms. While some perhaps thought this a positive (in that unduly harsh criticisms would be tempered), others undoubtedly were reflecting common concerns that open identities will diminish review by compromising reviewers. As one respondent put it "if a junior scientist is asked to review a document by a more senior scientists, one who may at some point in her/his career become her/his supervisor/boss, she/he might be inclined not [to] be too harsh". A related concern is that reviewers who do not pull their punches shall suffer retribution from vengeful colleagues later. The extent to which these concerns are real or imagined is open to question. To date studies (e.g., McNutt et al., 1990; van Rooyen et al., 2010, 1999) have failed to show any great effect in this direction. However, perceptions are hugely important here - especially where they may disincentivize reviewers. Hence, not only is more research required into how open identities affects the reviews themselves, but a more precise investigation of attitudes to open identities is necessary to help separate facts from perceptions and better inform researchers about the advantages and disadvantages of open identities peer review. This is especially so since, in addition to the fact that researchers do seem to see ethical worth in open identities, incentivizing reviews through making them citable products rely upon reviewers committing their names to these products.

Open reports: Respondents were very favourable towards publishing review reports alongside research outputs, with around 3 in 5 believing this will improve peer review and only a fifth thinking that it will make it worse. Almost 2 out of 3 believe review reports provide useful information for the reader. 3 out of 5, meanwhile, think that publishing reports will increase review quality. This perception is interesting, but whether or not open reports actually lead to improvements in review quality remains an open question. What evidence there is on this question, is inconclusive: Van Rooyen et al.'s (2010) empirical study of the reviews themselves found no improvement in quality, while in Elsevier's currently ongoing pilot study with open reports, for which interim results are available, a third of editors reported an improvement in the overall quality of review reports (Mehmani, 2016). On a less positive note, respondents to our survey thought that publishing reviews might lead to less strong criticisms (46% agreeing) and disinhibit reviewers (52% agreeing). Our finding chimes with Taylor & Francis Group's (2016) survey whose reviewers similarly thought open reports would deter

reviewers, but not with Elsevier's open reports pilot where more than 9 in 10 reviewers who declined to take part said their decision was not influenced by the open review (Mehmani, 2016). Why should open reports potentially deter reviewers? In addition to simply not wishing to publish their reviews, it may be that some believe that making reviews suitable for publication will take longer and hence make each review more time-intensive. Van Rooyen et al. (2010) found that this is indeed the case. However, more than 75% of the respondents to Nicholson and Alperin's small survey thought it would take no extra effort or only moderate extra effort to make their peer reviews suitable for public posting (Nicholson and Alperin, 2016).

Open participation: Just over half of respondents think allowing the wider community to contribute to the review process will improve peer review, versus 28% who believe it will make it worse. Similar numbers agreed that that close circles of reviewers and editors hold back innovative research" (47%) and that all those with sufficient knowledge should be able to review, regardless of background (45%). This last point divided opinions sharply, however, with almost as many (38%) expressing disagreement. This sharp division of opinions is reflective of strong beliefs on both sides, with strong opposition between those who think opening participation can resolve possible conflicts associated with editorial selection of reviewers (e.g., biases, closed-networks, elitism) and possibly improve the reliability of peer review by increasing the number of reviewers on the one hand, and on the other, those who see open participation as opening the gates to unqualified reviewers whose credentials and motives remain opaque. Perhaps the most fundamental question for open participation remains, however, whether people will take it upon themselves to review voluntarily. Our respondents agreed heavily (85%) with the common sense proposition that reviewers are more likely to review if they are invited.

Open interaction: Our respondents were heavily in favour of open interaction – peer review where direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged – with more than two thirds of respondents believing it will improve peer review and a scant 16% thinking it will make it worse. Faced with the statement that "increased interaction between authors and reviewers will result in better publications", respondents were equally emphatic in their approbation: more than three quarters agreed, while fewer than one in ten disagreed. Given that in comparison to some other more radical elements of OPR, open interaction presents a fairly incremental change, this level of support suggests that this is presently the easiest route for journals wishing to experiment with "open" peer review processes.

Open pre-review manuscripts: Respondents were almost evenly split on the question of whether manuscripts being made immediately available (e.g., via pre-print servers like ArXiv) in advance of any formal peer review procedures would improve peer review, with 36% against and 41% in favour. However, on the question of whether pre-review manuscripts *should* be made available in this way,

45% were against while less than a third (32%) were in favour. This view seems to be consistent across all research disciplines. A majority from the social sciences (54.5%), mathematics and statistics (62.1%), law and political sciences (60%), computer sciences / IT (60.8%) and other disciplines (52%) believe open manuscripts would improve peer review, while the disciplines that believe it would actually make peer review worse are agriculture and food sciences (62.8%) and health sciences (51.4%), chemistry (43.4%). While there are strong objections from the health sciences (66.1%), agriculture and food sciences (58.9%), biology and life sciences (54.4%), chemistry (48.5%) and psychology and philosophy (50%). Hence, although the plurality of respondents see *potential* for improving peer review through open pre-review manuscripts, the plurality are nonetheless against actually making manuscripts openly available. That the results should be reversed in this way is somewhat puzzling, but probably suggests that while respondents saw the advantages of open manuscripts for peer review, they believed that advantage to be outweighed by other disadvantages (e.g., fear of getting scooped).

Open final-version commenting: Respondents were strongly in favour of allowing readers to review or comment on final “version of record” publications via comment sections, blog articles, online journal clubs or social media, with 55% for and just 16% against. But despite this, only a minority consider such commenting to be a formal part of peer review (29% agreeing and 51% disagreeing). This suggests that respondents still see peer review as a publication sub-process, with peer review existing to vet and improve manuscripts for publication.

Open Platforms: Respondents tended to be more in favour than not of the proposition that open platforms (de-coupled review that is facilitated by a different organizational entity than the venue of publication) would improve peer review. However, it must be noted that more than half of all those who responded to this question either proclaimed themselves neutral (23.8%) or said they didn’t know (27.7%), indicating that this element is either poorly understood, or that respondents found its effects difficult to judge.

3.4.5 Summary and Future Developments

The findings of the study show the majority of respondents to be in favour of OPR becoming mainstream scholarly practice, as they also are for other areas of Open Science, like Open Access and Open Data. We also observe surprisingly high levels of experience with OPR amongst our sample: three out of four (76.2%) of our respondents said that they had taken part in an OPR process as either author or reviewer or editor (although note again our provisos regarding the ways in which our sample may be skewed).

However, there seems to be a rather strong pushback against open identities, with 47.7% (n=1461) of our respondents believing that open identities will make peer review either worse or much worse. This is surprising because open identities is the OPR trait most commonly included in definitions (present in

110 of 122 definitions studied). Respondents see value in open identities but want reviewers to be able to choose whether or not to make their identities open.

Finally, respondents are strongly in favour of open interaction between reviewers and authors. As this is, in some respects, an incremental change to peer review processes, this might be the first option for those journals looking to experiment with aspects of OPR. OPR is an evolving phenomenon and hence future studies are to be encouraged, especially to further explore differences between disciplines and monitor the evolution of attitudes.

Specific areas for future investigation include:

- Are these findings of levels of experience with and attitudes towards OPR consistent across studies?
- Which specific OPR systems (run via journals or third-party services) do users most prefer?
- Cost: Are OPR systems more or less cost effective than traditional systems? If the latter, do their benefits outweigh any extra costs?
- What measures might further incentivize the uptake of OPR? How fixed are attitudes to the various facets of OPR and how might they be changed?
- What about OPR for research outputs other than journal articles? Would users welcome OPR for data, software, conference submissions, project proposals, etc.?
- What disciplinary differences regarding attitudes to OPR exist?

4 | OPEN PEER REVIEW EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Introduction

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Section 2 showed that the evidential basis for many of the claims for and arguments against open peer review (OPR) is largely thin and unconvincing. Hence, OpenAIRE has played host to three innovative experiments that aim at promoting OPR and studying its effects in the context of digital infrastructures for open scholarship. The main aims of these activities were to:

- Encourage experimentation in OPR.
- Provide case studies for evaluation.
- Investigate ways in which OPR technologies might integrate with OpenAIRE's infrastructure, including the repository [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org) as well as other content aggregated, inferred, and interlinked by OpenAIRE.

To address these issues, in mid-2015 OpenAIRE ran an open call for tenders for OPR prototypes/experiments, with two grants of up to 25,000 Euros each available. Twelve bids were received. After a thorough evaluation process, the awards were granted to (1) a consortium of organizations led by Open Scholar CIC (lead investigator Pandelis Perakakis), and (2) The Winnower (lead investigator Joshua Nicholson). In addition, a third experiment was already specified in the OpenAIRE2020 project proposal, led by (3) OpenEdition (lead investigator Julien Bordier). The three experiments, whose results are presented in the following sections of this chapter, were diverse in their aims and methods:

- Open Scholar** and its consortium aimed to turn repositories into functional evaluation platforms by building an OPR module for integration with Open Access repositories and then implementing this module in two high-profile institutional repositories.
- The Winnower** sought to integrate the Winnower platform with repositories like Zenodo via DOIs and APIs to facilitate OPR of repository objects, as well as offering financial incentives to encourage open participation in the sharing of 'journal club' reviews and documenting user experiences via survey.
- OpenEdition** aimed to use open services such as the annotation software hypotheses.org and OpenEdition's platform for academic blogs to model a workflow (selection, review and revision) that would develop blog articles into peer reviewed publications in the Humanities and Social Sciences. Note: An extended version of this report is available: <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01302597/document>.

4.2 Experiment 1: Open Peer Review Module (OPRM) for Open Access Repositories

Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar CIC), Agnes Ponsati (DIGITAL.CSIC), Isabel Bernal (DIGITAL.CSIC), Concha Mosquera de Arancibia (e-IEO), Carles Sierra (IIIA-CSIC), Nardine Osman (IIIA-CSIC), Emilio Lorenzo (ARVO)

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Project consortium:

- [Open Scholar CIC](#) — An open organization of research scholars
- [DIGITAL.CSIC](#) — The Institutional Repository of the Spanish National Research Council
- [e-IEO](#) — The Repository of the Spanish Oceanographic Institute
- [ARVO](#) — A company of DSpace professional development and services
- [IIIA](#) — The Artificial Intelligence Research Institute
- [SECABA](#) — A multidisciplinary laboratory of Library and Computer Sciences

4.2.1 Introduction

Research productivity is increasing at an unprecedented rate. Technological innovations, a surge in available computing power, and the ease with which digital information is stored and communicated are all helping researchers to cross experimentation boundaries, to increase data availability, and to facilitate the transfer of knowledge. As a result, traditional research is being transformed into a dynamic and globally interconnected effort where ideas, tools and results can be made instantly accessible to the entire academic community. Institutional and multidisciplinary open access repositories play a crucial role in this emerging landscape by enabling immediate accessibility to all kinds of research output.

One important element still missing from open access repositories, however, is a quantitative assessment of the hosted research items that will facilitate the process of selecting the most relevant and distinguished content. Common currently available metrics, such as number of visits and downloads, do not reflect the quality of a research work, which can only be assessed directly by peers offering their expert opinion together with quantitative ratings based on specific criteria.

To address this issue we developed an Open Peer Review Module (OPRM) to be installed on existing open access repositories and offered as an overlay service. Any digital research work hosted in a compliant repository can then be evaluated by an unlimited number of peers who offer not only a

qualitative assessment in the form of text, but also quantitative measures that are used to build the reputation of the research work and its authors. Crucially, this evaluation system is open and transparent. By open we mean that the full text of the peer reviews are publicly available along with the original research work. By transparent we mean that the identity of the reviewers is disclosed to the authors and to the public. In our model, openness and transparency are two elemental aspects we consider necessary to address the issue of biased or non-expert opinions, which is inherent in the anonymous peer review model, characterized by the unaccountability of reviewers.

Importantly, the OPR module includes a reviewer reputation system based on the assessment of reviews themselves by other peer reviewers. This allows a sophisticated scaling of the importance of each review on the overall assessment of a research work, based on the reputation of the reviewer.

The implementation of a peer review layer on top of institutional repositories could have the potential to transform the current academic publication landscape by introducing new scholarly workflows where a research item can be openly evaluated by the world's experts right at the institutional repository of its authors, before being submitted to an academic journal. This workflow challenges the current practices of peer review research evaluation. In most cases, journals, acting as brands in a competitive market, foster academic competition for a limited number of publication slots, instead of promoting open scholarship and collaboration. The integration of peer review in repositories will enable direct and transparent academic collaboration between authors and reviewers. In addition, the use of the OPRM will produce novel metrics directly reflecting the perceived quality of a research work by expert peers, contrary to current available altmetrics that only indirectly account for quality through usage statistics.

4.2.2 Open Peer Review Module

TECHNICAL IMPLICATIONS

The OPRM can be considered as an add-on or plug-in for the DSpace platform. Detailed instructions on how to install the plug-in on top of DSpace JSPUI or XMLUI are provided at the module's webpage on Github: <https://github.com/arvoConsultores/Open-Peer-Review-Module/wiki/Installation>

The module is built around the following components and elements:

- Invitations subsystem
- Reviews subsystem
- Comments subsystem
- Object data model
- Reputation engine

Invitations subsystem: The system allows the author to send review requests to select peers. The submission-item-interface has been extended to specify the email addresses of the proposed reviewers. The system sends a customized email including a token that grants the reviewer access to the research object and to the reviews subsystem.

Reviews subsystem: The reviewer accesses the reviews subsystem acting with sufficient privileges granted by the token. The evaluation forms are then presented to the reviewer, together with relevant terms and conditions regarding the whole review process. The proposed forms can be configured using standard data types when applicable, although an additional schema has been added to accommodate specific model's metadata. The submission-item interface, already available in Dspace, is used to support this step, covering metadata declaration and attaching license attributions. The submission workflow can assign the review object to the repository administrators, with a single Accept/Reject/Edit Metadata step or just deposit the review in a specific collection. Following this step, specific background tasks are attached to the process, via consumer events, to perform automatic validation of the metadata, linking reviews and reviewed objects, and calling the reputation submodules to calculate new numeric values (for authors and research objects) and automatically incorporate them into the reviewed object and into the review.

Comments subsystem: This subsystem is complemented with the judgments subsystem, a specialization of the reviews subsystem that allows reviewers to judge other reviews of the same research object.

Object data model: The object data model has been extended to incorporate relevant metrics as well as the back-and-forth relations between research objects and their reviews. In order to process information about the reputation of the authors, and make this information persistent, the system uses extensions to the author's data-model (DSpace-CRIS and other extensions). However, the module can be used without these extensions, although in this case the consolidation and visualization of the reputation of authors and reviewers is not available.

Reputation engine: The Digital object's reputation submodule bundles the functions to invoke, calculate and retrieve a digital object's reputation. This submodule obtains information about the digital object and its reviews, calculates reputations based on the submitted parameters and updates reputations with the new calculated values. In order to maximize its evolution and reuse across platforms, this submodule is an independent plugin, facilitating the installation and deployment process and even its substitution by any other set of algorithms. The Author/reviewer reputation submodule exposes the functions of obtaining reputation information from objects, including reviews, calculate the author's reputation and update the reputation with the new calculated values.

REPUTATION ASSESSMENT MODEL

The reputation assessment model is based on peers evaluating (quantitatively, in addition to qualitatively) each other's research works as well as each other's reviews. The latter allows for a sophisticated scaling of the importance of each review on the overall assessment of a research work, based on the reputation of the reviewer. We note that our model assumes that evaluations may be done on a number of dimensions (e.g. originality, technical soundness, predicted impact, etc.), however, an 'overall quality' dimension is needed for computing the general reputation of the research work. This is because aggregating the reputation for all dimensions into a single index may depend on a number of issues that are outside the scope of this work.

The model quantifies a reputation for articles (or any other research object hosted by the repository), authors, reviewers, and reviews. The reputation of an article is the weighted aggregation of the reviews it receives, where the weight depends on the reputation of the reviewer (discussed below). A single metric is provided for each evaluation dimension: overall quality, expected impact in the field, expected impact for society, etc. A scholar's reputation as an author is an aggregation of the reputation of their papers. Again, this reputation is computed for each dimension separately. The reputation of a reviewer is essentially a weighted aggregation of the judgements over her reviews by other reviewers who evaluated the same research works. The weight in this case is the reputation of reviewers who offer an opinion. Finally, the reputation of a review is similar to the one for articles, but using judgements instead of reviews. Extensive information about the model, including the code for its implementation, is provided in the published conference paper (also attached in this report):

- Osman, N. & Sierra, C. (2016). Reputation in the Academic World. In Proceedings of the 18th International Workshop on Trust in Agent Societies (TRUST @ AAMAS 2016) (pp. 1--17). CEUR Workshop Proceedings.

4.2.3 Implementation and Preliminary Results

As part of this project, the OPRM was implemented in two Open Access repositories: the Institutional Repository of the Spanish National Research Council (DIGITAL.CSIC), and the Institutional Repository of the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (e-IEO). What follows is a description of the implementation process and a report of preliminary results from these two repositories.

DIGITAL.CSIC

DIGITAL.CSIC has taken part in the OPRM project through different working lines. First, the repository has participated in discussions about the design and workflow of the module to be integrated with DSpace software. DIGITAL.CSIC runs on the DSpace-CRIS 4.3 version which means that besides developing an OPRM module that is interoperable with the standard DSpace system, the ARVO partner needed to consider some characteristics inherent to the DIGITAL.CSIC specific DSpace version, in particular the DSpace-CRIS author module. In addition, the DIGITAL.CSIC team worked closely with

ARVO so as to customize the OPRM module in line with general item submission workflow and metadata records visualization on the repository. Last but not least, the repository team has contributed to preparing the support guides to help authors and reviewers with all elements of the OPRM.

The OPRM went live in DIGITAL.CSIC in April 2016 and in preparation for its release the repository team launched a preliminary internal campaign to attract CSIC researchers to test the module. The strategy was based on a one-to-one approach where selected researchers across all scientific areas were contacted to invite them to take part in the role of authors willing to receive open peer reviews. The selection of researchers took into account several considerations: in the first place, the repository team contacted researchers with a well-known OA-friendly attitude and a long record of item submissions into DIGITAL.CSIC. Second, the repository produced a list of CSIC researchers with a public profile on the reviewer-based platforms Publons and PubPeer and with publications in the open peer review F1000Research journal. In total, the repository collected around 60 potential candidates and amongst them 20 researchers in Humanities and Social Sciences, Chemistry, Natural Resources, Biology and Biomedicine, Food Science and Physics were briefed on the OPRM project and invited to participate. It is worth mentioning that except for 2 researchers who openly declined the invitation all the others showed interest in the module and committed to participate in its pilot phase.

Without being exhaustive, below is a list of selected comments gathered during this process. This preliminary feedback by scientists can shed light on the sort of issues that caught their attention the most when understanding the goals and functioning of the module in this first phase. This process is also explained in the DIGITAL.CSIC presentation (<http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131576>) at the OPRM official launch at the end of April.

First feedback from CSIC researchers:

“A long awaited service in the repository.”

“It is a great idea that merits success as currently peer review is not credited in researchers CVs at all due to its anonymity. But researchers will not have time to review and comment on other peers’ works as long as this activity remains outside of CVs recognition and lacks strong support from the research institutions.”

“The functionality may be also used to evaluate, accept and comment on conference contributions before the event.”

“The project seems very interesting, but I decline to participate right now due to lack of time and current demands [preparation of proposals for a national research call].”

“I have contacted 3 reviewers: one has no time available, another is against any type of peer review as reviewing is a subjective activity in such a reduced scholarly discipline and the third one has accepted to do it.”

“The service should promote spontaneous discussion by anybody willing to send comments.”

“Inviting peers to an open evaluation may place people in an uncomfortable situation, the module should work 100% open.”

“The service is great for preprints and other unpublished works but has limited applicability for works that have been already evaluated and published. Moreover, the service has a difficult application for very recent publications as publishers reserve an exclusive exploitation for a period of time.”

“How does open peer review operate in relation to “finished” pieces of work (i.e., a book)?”

“How will the service compete with Academia.edu open review/comments?”

To date, DIGITAL.CSIC hosts five open peer reviews: two in the area of Natural Resources/Biology, one in Physics and two in Bibliometrics and Documentation Studies: they are all accessible from the Open Peer Review Collection in the repository: <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131210>).

As a general consideration, it may be useful to note that (1) even for those researchers supportive of this new service on the repository, finding the time to select works to be reviewed, invite peers and comment on the reviews received was reported to be an issue that can slow down the uptake of the module, and (2) in all the real cases already available in the repository, as well as in those that are underway, the authors decided to select works that have already been peer-reviewed (i.e., published papers and conference contributions), with the exception of a policy paper waiting to be reviewed.

These factors may be a major deterrent for the wide and timely applicability of the module. Further, it remains a challenge to convince authors to use the module for their article preprints, as fears of later journal rejection still prevail. In addition, it is paramount to design an effective and attractive campaign to reach out to the wider institutional community in order to consolidate the service as an active one on the repository in upcoming months. Without such a campaign, reticence concerning the lack of linkages with institutional assessment exercises and rewards system, limitations associated with an invitation-based module and misunderstandings about the OPRM reputation sub-module and what type of OPR it supports are expected to be potential stumbling blocks.

E-IEO

With the OPRM, the IEO aims to foster scientific collaboration among its research community via peer discussion. With the OPRM, the IEO enhances its policy of providing added value, further to already implemented functionalities, such as authority control and author profiles.

The OPRM was set up and launched in e-IEO in March 2016. Its release was accompanied by an official announcement (<http://hdl.handle.net/10508/9996>) and an internal communication to all scientific staff of the IEO, via e-mail, and preceded by the OPRM Project at e-IEO (<http://hdl.handle.net/10508/9990>) one week earlier.

The OPRM runs at e-IEO on DSpace version 5.2, with user interface xmlui and authority control system in which the authority values are stored in the solr indexing system and search engine. e-IEO has also implemented the author profiles, where author reputation and reviewer reputation are shown.

Following the module's release, the e-IEO team carried out a pilot study evaluating three published works, one for each IEO scientific area (Fisheries, Aquaculture and Marine Environment and Environmental Protection). We had the full collaboration of nine IEO scientists who responded in three weeks: three of them as authors to be evaluated and six as reviewers to provide reviews and comments. IEO authors also commented on the reviews of their works.

In summary, the pilot resulted in:

- 6 reviews (2 reviews per work)
- 12 comments (2 comments per review, one by the author and one by the other reviewer)
- weighted reputation metrics for the works, authors, reviews and reviewers

At the repository, a work's page displays the work's reputation value ("Publication reputation"), and provides links to related reviews and their quality ratings given by each reviewer. A review's page displays: the review (pdf), the overall quality of the work, the reputation of the particular review, and links to the related work (with its reputation value), and to related comments with their corresponding quality ratings. A comment's page displays: the comment, the overall review quality and a link to the related review with the corresponding reputation value. Author reputation and reviewer reputation are shown at the author profile, if available. All reviews and comments are grouped in a new community at the repository called OPRM.

A list of reviewed works at the e-IEO:

- <http://hdl.handle.net/10508/8123> (Fisheries: article published in Journal of Marine Biology, 2011).
- <http://hdl.handle.net/10508/2494> (Aquaculture: poster, abstract published in Aquaculture Europe 14 Congress, 2014).

- <http://hdl.handle.net/10508/7818> (Marine Environmental and Environmental Protection: article published in Marine Ecology Progress Series, 2009).

Examples of researcher profiles:

- [García-Rodríguez, M. \(Mariano\)](#)
- [Jerez, S. \(Salvador\)](#)
- [Orejas, C. \(Covadonga\)](#)
- [Rodrigues-dos-Santos-Domingues, P.M. \(Pedro Miguel\)](#)

The Open Peer Review Module at the Spanish Institute of Oceanography is also available at the e-IEO presentation <http://hdl.handle.net/10508/10124> (from OPRM official launch, 27 April 2016).

Some initial feedback from IEO researchers suggests that the Open Peer Review Module (OPRM) could be a useful objective tool to evaluate scientific papers as it is intuitive and easy to use. Comments suggest it is a very good idea because it may lead to a future of open collaboration fostering research, development and innovation. By knowing the reviewers' identity, authors can ensure that the review of their works has been made by experts in the field. Moreover, revealing the texts of the reviews and the comments of other referees, an exchange of information among experts is possible, thereby avoiding, as far as possible, subjectivity by the reviewers. This open peer discussion facilitates the evaluation by the reviewer. Nevertheless, the current peer review journals system is so integrated in the scientific community that the OPRM implementation will take a long time to really change researcher behaviors on a larger scale. Some researchers suggest that a negative assessment of a colleague's work could create an uncomfortable situation among colleagues. However, many researchers expect the OPRM to unveil its full potential in the future and say that everyone should support this initiative to ensure full open science as soon as possible. Regarding future prospects, in order to encourage researchers to use the module, it seems essential that the OPRM should become a cross-platform evaluation system whose advantages are widely disseminated, resulting in comparable platform-independent metrics.

4.2.4 Deliverables and dissemination

- The OPRM source code: <https://github.com/arvoConsultores/Open-Peer-Review-Module/wiki>
- OPRM launch event (organized and hosted by DIGITAL.CSIC on the 27th of April 2016) website: http://proyectos.bibliotecas.csic.es/digitalcsic/oprm/programa_eng.html
- Blog posts and press releases:
 - <http://www.openscholar.org.uk/developing-the-first-open-peer-review-module-for-institutional-repositories/>
 - <http://www.openscholar.org.uk/institutional-repositories-start-to-offer-peer-review-services/>
 - <http://www.repositorio.ieo.es/e-ieo/handle/10508/9996>

- <http://www.repositorio.ieo.es/e-ieo/handle/10508/9990>
- <http://digital.csic.es/dc/noticias/listarNoticias.jsp?pos=10&locale=en>
- Presentations:
 - Open Peer Review Module for Open Access Repositories:
<http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131572>
 - The Open Peer Review Module – some technical details:
<http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131573>
 - Reputation in the Academic World: <http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131575>
 - OPRM Pilot Project in Digital. CSIC: first experience and thoughts:
<http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/131576>
 - The Open Peer Review Module at the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO):
<http://www.repositorio.ieo.es/e-ieo/handle/10508/10124>
 - Dissemination material (logos): <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/129662>
 - Poster presentation: <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/136937>
- FAQs: <http://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/135982>

4.3 Experiment 2: The Winnower

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THE WINNOWER IS AN OPEN ACCESS ONLINE SCHOLARLY PUBLISHING PLATFORM THAT EMPLOYS OPEN POST-PUBLICATION PEER REVIEW. IT BELIEVES THAT TRANSPARENCY FROM START TO FINISH IS CRITICAL IN SCIENTIFIC COMMUNICATION. ITS AIM IS TO REVOLUTIONIZE SCIENCE BY BREAKING DOWN THE BARRIERS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNICATION THROUGH COST-EFFECTIVE AND TRANSPARENT PUBLISHING FOR SCHOLARS.

4.3.1 Overview

Peer review is an integral part of scientific communication. Traditionally, journal editors solicit reviews from two to four subject experts to assess whether the work is suitable for publication. While this process remains the norm in scholarly publishing, new models of review have emerged, including online discussion via social media and informal meetings amongst scholars known as journal clubs.

In our project, we sought to test whether publishing post-publication peer reviews can be incentivized by elevating peer reviews to the same level as original research, with all the affordances and services of scholarly publications.

In efforts to answer this core question, this project carried out three activities, all of which are described in further detail below:

- The integration between The Winnower and OpenAIRE through the development of an open source tool that identifies metadata from a DOI or a URL
- The incentivizing and publishing of student journal club proceedings
- A survey of Winnower users and Twitter followers about their attitudes towards social publishing peer reviews.

Although the project has formally come to a close, some of the activities of the project remain ongoing, as they have become part of The Winnower's core functionality.

4.3.2 Activities

INTEGRATION BETWEEN THE WINNOWER AND OPENAIRE

In order to integrate the two platforms, we developed an open source tool called "[Terrier](#)" to extract metadata from scholarly articles published across publishers (via DOI or URL). In cases where work was available on the Zenodo repository, Terrier also fetches the article itself, as well as the metadata.

On The Winnower, Terrier is used so that when users want to publish a review, they can easily import the article metadata (and in the case of Zenodo, the articles themselves). As a result, The Winnower actively promotes the publishing of reviews, and does so by following best-practices (referring to the reviewed work).

Since the tool was developed as a Ruby Gem and released to the community on Github, it has been possible for others (researchers, platforms, etc.) to reuse the work. It was immediately recognized as a useful tool, as can be seen from the following Tweets:

"AWESOME! I'VE BEEN SLOWLY TRYING TO BUILD THE SAME THING IN PYTHON. TRICKY PROBLEM!" -DAN LURIE, ([HTTPS://TWITTER.COM/DANJLURIE/STATUS/707267395908337664](https://twitter.com/danjlurie/status/707267395908337664))

"THANKS, THAT'S JUST WHAT I WAS LOOKING FOR TODAY!" --BASTIAN GRESHAKE ([HTTPS://TWITTER.COM/GEDANKENSTUECKE/STATUS/705169901795844096](https://twitter.com/gedankenstuecke/status/705169901795844096))

"I KNEW TERRIER WAS GOING TO COME IN HANDY. USING IT NOW TO RESOLVE METADATA FOR ~70,000 PAPERS. THANKS" 😊 - CHRIS HARTGERINK ([HTTPS://TWITTER.COM/CHARTGERINK/STATUS/721625578500132864](https://twitter.com/chartgerink/status/721625578500132864))

INCENTIVIZING AND PUBLISHING JOURNAL CLUB PROCEEDINGS

Prior to and concurrent with the development of Terrier, we launched an online-campaign to solicit participants to publish their journal club discussions with us. We searched for groups via Google that advertised their meetings online and invited them to participate in the pilot. We emailed these groups to invite them to our pilot and offered to pay them to publish their journal clubs should they publish five journal club proceedings over the course of our pilot.

A total of 12 groups agreed to participate, but very few proceeded to post reviews in spite of the financial incentive. Even those that did publish reviews failed to meet the 5 proceedings minimum.

This small sample suggests (although not in a conclusive way) that small financial incentives are insufficient to motivate the publishing of journal clubs. This is further reinforced by comments from most participants that their desire to participate was not financially motivated. In fact, traditional hierarchies seemed to be at play, with more senior researchers advising their students to write the journal clubs.

There were blog posts created to recruit participants. Additionally, the same text was circulated via email to Winnower users.

As a result of this activity, The Winnower published only 6 journal club proceedings over the course of 2 months, although several more were expected. This number represented the participation of two groups led by a senior researcher (professor or postdoc) with the content being written by individual

students. Despite commitment from more groups, there have been delays in actual submissions, in part caused by our own delays in integrating Terrier, and in part caused by the natural schedule of journal clubs (which tend not to meet very often). While this number may seem small, it is in line with numbers of publications received when new journals are launched. We are optimistic that some of the other journal clubs who expressed interest will publish proceedings, as we continue to reach out to them periodically with reminders. We also expect that as new users discover The Winnower, and as researchers become more accustomed to publishing different article types beyond the traditional research article, this will become a valuable resource for groups meeting to publish journal clubs.

SURVEY ON ATTITUDES TOWARDS OPEN PEER REVIEW

We invited scholars to take part in our survey by invitation through Twitter and The Winnower emailing list. Although this type of convenience sampling is unlikely to be representative of a larger population, we believe it reflects an audience that is likely more willing to consider Open Review than the average researcher, particularly because our community of users and followers tend to be biased towards individuals who are interested in new models of publishing and scholarly communication (because of our own model of publication and review). We received seventy-nine responses over the course of a few weeks of solicitation. The results of this survey are published on The Winnower online: <https://thewinnower.com/papers/4659-a-brief-survey-on-peer-review-in-scholarly-communication>.

4.3.3 A brief survey on peer review in scholarly communication

INTRODUCTION

Peer review, the process by which subject experts evaluate a piece of work, is an integral part of scholarly publishing. In most cases peer review is coordinated by an editor at a scholarly journal and is performed privately amongst two to three peers. There is often no standard report that peer reviewers complete, however, they are generally asked to make a decision if the paper is acceptable for publication or not based on the merits of the paper. The traditional process of peer review, while widely regarded as being crucial in scholarly publishing, has become increasingly criticized for its shortcomings. Strikingly, tests on the veracity of peer review have shown that most major errors are not detected during peer review (Smith 2010, Godlee, Gale, and Martyn 1998, Baxt et al. 1998). These findings have called for new ways of improving peer review to be explored. One suggestion is to make peer review more transparent (i.e. reports are open to the public) and for it to occur post-publication (Smith 2010). Post-publication peer review is organized similarly to pre-publication peer review except that it occurs after a paper has been published or made public. Post-publication peer review has also been used to describe blogging, journal clubs, and other forms of review that occur on the Internet or in private. To better understand how researchers view traditional peer review versus open peer review, and other new forms of peer review we surveyed the scholarly community via an informal survey.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

We invited scholars to take part in our survey by invitation through Twitter and The Winnower emailing list. We acknowledge that our methods of recruitment may represent a population of researchers biased towards new models of publishing and scholarly communication, given The Winnower's model of publication and review. We received seventy-nine responses over the course of a few weeks of solicitation. Of these seventy-nine, 70% (55) were faculty, librarian, or researcher, including early career researcher with the remainder made up of PhD students, Master students, and other, at 18% (14), 4% (3), and 8% (6) respectively. Those identifying as "other" in the survey included publishers, independent scholars, and retired professors. In agreement with this, 61% of respondents identified as being at University.

FIGURE 23: EMPLOYMENT LEVEL OF 79 RESPONDENTS

70% (55) were faculty, librarian, or researcher, including early career researcher. The remainder was made up of PhD students, Master students and other, 18% (14), 4% (3), and 8% (6) respectively.

FIGURE 24: EMPLOYER/ORGANIZATION OF 79 RESPONDENTS

The respondents polled came from a diverse background of study with Biology and the Life sciences making up the largest percentage of the group (Table 1). Most respondents had previously had their own work peer reviewed (92%) and had performed peer review of others work before (94%).

TABLE 8: FIELDS OF STUDY

Field of Study	% of respondents
Agriculture and Food sciences	0%
Arts and Architecture	1%
Biology and Life sciences	30%
Chemistry	0%
Earth and Environmental Sciences	8%
Health Sciences	12%
History and Archeology	1%

Languages and Literature	3%
Law and Political science	0%
Mathematics and Statistics	1%
Physics and Astronomy	7%
Social Sciences	16%
Technology and Engineering	11%
None of these	10%

In general the survey showed that most believe peer review to be beneficial, both to give and to receive. While the merit of reviews was recognized amongst researchers the poll showed most believed that peer review did not aide greatly in the advancement of their career (below Table).

TABLE 9: BENEFITS OF PEER REVIEW

Question	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I benefit from being peer reviewed	0.0	6.3	3.1	34.4	56.3
Others benefit from my reviews of their work	1.5	3.1	4.6	40.0	50.8
Reviews DO count for career advancement in my current position (salary reviews and/or tenure and promotion)	36.9	16.9	24.6	18.5	3.1
Reviews should count for career	4.6	4.6	21.5	38.5	30.8

advancement in my
current unit (salary
reviews and/or
tenure and
promotion)

Because peer reviews are currently closed and thus hard to measure as an output by promotion and tenure committees and others, it is possible that open reviews may rectify this. Moreover, would making peer reviews open change their content or tone? When asked if peer reviews were made public, would they change? Most respondents answered yes, but to varying degrees (below Figure). When asked how, many seemed to suggest that reviews may improve in various aspects from tone to better justification of critiques.

FIGURE 25: DO YOU THINK THE REVIEW WOULD HAVE BEEN DIFFERENT IF IT HAD BEEN PUBLISHED FOR PEOPLE TO SEE?

Most respondents believe that making their reviews open would not require a significant amount of more work to be undertaken. If peer reviews were open and could consequently be counted by various evaluators from grant agencies to promotion and tenure, where would researchers list their reviews? The majority responded that they would list them on their curriculum vitae under “professional service”.

FIGURE 26: ASSUMING YOU WANTED TO: HOW MUCH MORE TIME/EFFORT DO YOU THINK IT WOULD TAKE TO MAKE YOUR PEER REVIEW SOMETHING THAT COULD BE POSTED PUBLICLY?

FIGURE 27: IF PUBLISHED, RESEARCHERS WOULD LARGELY CONSIDER REVIEWS AS PROFESSIONAL SERVICE

Thus, based on our survey researchers see value in peer review, believe that open review would generally improve reviews, and that peer reviews should count for career advancement. However, most reviews remain private. When asked what change would need to happen for reviewers to make their reviews public, most said if tenure and promotion committees explicitly valued them and if their peers also published theirs (Figure below).

FIGURE 28: REASONS THAT WOULD INCENTIVIZE SCHOLARS TO MAKE THEIR PEER REVIEWS PUBLICLY AVAILABLE

Respondents selected two reasons that would make them more likely to take the effort to make their reviews public.

Given the value of openly reviewing work amongst peers, many labs participate in a semi-regular meeting called “journal club.” In our survey 56% of respondents participate in journal clubs at varying frequencies (Figure 7 below). Although the majority of those we surveyed participate in journal clubs, the large majority of them do not publish them (67%). Again, when polled what would change this most pointed their promotion and tenure committees explicitly valuing them and their peers also publishing theirs (Figure 8 below).

Figure 7. Do you or any of your peers participate in a "journal club" (meet informally to discuss published academic papers)?

Figure 8. Reasons that would incentivize scholars to make their journal club discussions publicly available

4.4 Experiment 3: OpenEdition - Experimenting with Open Peer Review and Open Peer Commentary

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OPENEdition SERVES THE HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES RESEARCH COMMUNITIES THROUGH FOUR PUBLICATION AND INFORMATION PLATFORMS: OPENEdition BOOKS (BOOKS SERIES), REVUES.ORG (SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS), HYPOTHESES (RESEARCH BLOGS), AND CALENDAs (ACADEMIC ANNOUNCEMENTS).

4.4.1 Introduction

In this section we describe an experiment conducted by OpenEdition in the framework of the European project OpenAIRE2020, in partnership with the digital and open access journal of environmental sciences Vertigo and the Couperin consortium. This analytic description of the experiment will lead to model operational workflows for open peer review (OPR) and open peer commentary (OPC).³ The qualitative approach adopted here – with first-person participant observation narration from the mediating-editor involved in coordinating the OPR activities – aims to describe the experimental workflow in order to draw out the significant elements of the system. Since the experiment took place over a short time and with a limited corpus of preprints (five preprints subjected to OPR and five to OPC), its results cannot be considered conclusive. However, it is hoped that these observations will inform the development of future OPR and OPC systems. In any case, the choice of a qualitative approach is justified because it seems safe to assume that issues related to peer review are closely related to the character and the subjectivity of authors, contributors and referees. The scientific community is a human community, shaped in part by personalities meeting and interacting. Thus, taking advantage of an approach based on specific examples, we want to express the need for case-by-case analysis before risking over-generalization. A prior hypothesis was that OPR protocols require specific human facilitation. This hypothesis was confirmed, as will be seen in the remainder of this report.

This is a socio-anthropological study about an editorial innovation, on a reduced corpus, in a representative environment. This participant observation is enriched by feedback on the experiment collected from most participants (authors, referees and contributors). It also relies on verbal and written informal discussions that helped to clarify the purpose and context of scientific publishing and reviewing processes. In addition, two scholars in social sciences and humanities (who did not otherwise

³ Protocol in situation : <http://vertigo.hypotheses.org/evaluations-et-commentaires-ouverts> (consulted on the 08/02/2016).

participate in the experiment) were interviewed to collect their thoughts and opinions about the experiments.

The following description and analysis of this experiment is organized in three sections:

- **Background and methodology:** describes briefly the two kinds of experiments, with open peer review and open commentary, as well as their editorial and technological contexts.
- **Results:** focuses on the limits of the workflows employed and the proposal of possible ways to improve the system.
- **Recommendations:** gives concrete advice on the implementation of open peer review and open commentary workflows.

4.4.2 Context for the experiments

PLATFORMS AND EDITORIAL CONTEXT

The experiments used OpenEdition's existing platforms for journals (Revue.org) and academic blogs (Hypotheses.org). The venues chosen were the French language journal Vertigo: The digital journal of environmental sciences⁴ (hosted on Revues.org) and Vertigo's research blog⁵ (hosted on Hypotheses). Although journals hosted on Revues.org need not necessarily be linked to a scientific blog hosted on Hypotheses, the latter platform is promoted as a kind of research notebook, to enable the rapid dissemination of research results. The relationship between a journal and a research notebook hosted on two platforms managed by the same structure was thought to create an editorial consistency that would be beneficial to the development and progress of the experiment.

SCIENTIFIC CONTEXT: VERTIGO, ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

The social sciences and humanities have traditionally been less enthusiastic than the STEM subjects in embracing OPR experimentation. Given that the environmental sciences operate at the border between biological and human approaches, they offer an interesting area for experimentation with OPR and OPC. Vertigo therefore creates a fertile interdisciplinary ground for experimentation. It is also a linguistically interesting venue since it is based in Montreal, at the crossroads of linguistic areas and therefore also at the crossroads of different traditions of scientific communications. Vertigo's research blog provided a low-technology solution to the implementation of OPR. The research blog already functioned as a public space for the discussion of preliminary research results. Hence, it makes a

⁴ www.vertigo.revues.org.

⁵ www.vertigo.hypotheses.org.

natural home for the public evaluation of journal articles. VertigO's research blog is usually used by the journal for several purposes (e.g. calls for contributions, opening published articles to comments, and reporting journal activities and publication).

4.4.3 Description of the experiments

The experiment took place over five months, with the first month devoted to desk research, and developed along two distinct branches inspired by the existing multitude of forms taken by OPR. This choice was also shaped by the types of articles' proposals available by VertigO's editorial board, some of which were spontaneous contributions that the journal was having difficulty dealing with due to their number and variable quality (particularly issues with their language).

OPEN PEER REVIEW WORKFLOW

Five texts were selected for the OPR workflow. Review was conducted according to the same table of reviewing criteria as is used in the journal's classical 'blind' review.⁶ These criteria cover the different levels and features of the text, with some criteria to be quantified (rated from one to four), while others allow for free text. The reviewing document concludes with sections for the referee's opinion on the relative strengths and weaknesses of the paper, their publication recommendation (accept, accept with major/minor revisions, or reject) and comments addressed to the author.

Within this experiment, the review process is open because it is transparent and open to public visibility (open reports) and both authors and reviewers are known to each other (open identities). To createArticles were uploaded as blog posts and reports were submitted using the blog's commenting function just below the article text. Texts were uploaded online once at least one referee agreed to review the preprint. Hence, the content of the submitted article was also published from an early stage in the review process (post-publication review). Potential referees were assigned by the journal, with the authors having previously given their consent to participate in the experiment.

At the end of the reviewing process, the respective blog page (with the article's first version, reviews, annotations and answers from authors) remains online. Where the text was accepted for publication, the published version carries an editorial note indicating that the article was openly peer reviewed and crediting the referees (with a link to the relevant blog page). A link to the published version was also added to the blog page, with text indicating that the article was subject to OPR, and that this process is now complete. Where a text was not accepted, however, the article text and reviewer comments were

⁶ This document is public, available among the "Instructions for authors": <https://vertigo.revues.org/5401> (accessed on the (2.02.2016)).

deleted, and only the article's title, the names of authors and referees, and a note that the text had been subject to unsuccessful open peer review remained online.

Up: draft

Down: reports

EVALUATION OUVERTE

“Synoptique et impacts d’un événement hydrométéorologique : les inondations du 6-7 octobre 2014, Grabels (France méditerranéenne)” par T. Rey, S. Defossey, F. Vinet et L. Boissier

PAR TONY REY - 6 NOVEMBRE 2015

Cet article est soumis à une évaluation ouverte par les pairs. Les rapports d'évaluation sont ou seront postés à la suite du texte. Pour consulter les annotations faites sous [hypothes.is](#), le plug-in est activable en cliquant sur ce lien.

Tony REY, Maître de Conférences en Géographie, UMR GRED/Université Paul-Valéry-Montpellier 3.
Stéphanie DEFOSSEY, Maître de Conférences en Géographie, UMR GRED/Université Paul-Valéry-Montpellier 3.
Freddy VINET, Professeur des Universités en Géographie.
Laurent BOISSIER, Docteur en Géographie, Chercheur associé, UMR GRED/Université Paul-Valéry-Montpellier 3.

Résumé : Dans la nuit du 6 et 7 octobre 2014, une crue éclair frappe le nord de Montpellier et notamment la commune de Grabels. Au cours de ce bref épisode pluviométrique, les ruissellements de versants, les cours d'eau -du petit ruisseau au fleuve de la Mosson- sont entrés en crue et sortis de leur lit endommageant près de 500 habitations. Pour reconstituer au plus près la synoptique de la crue rapide et ses impacts, nous avons mené un retour d'expérience dès le lendemain de la catastrophe. A partir des indicateurs morpho-sédimentaires et des dégâts observés, nous avons reconstitué l'enveloppe de la zone inondable ; caractérisé les hauteurs d'eau maximales atteintes ; identifié la cinématique des écoulements de crue ; estimé les débits de pointe et la puissance spécifique et caractérisé les modifications morpho-sédimentaires. Le retour d'expérience, réalisé à l'échelle locale, a mis en lumière les dynamiques hydrogéomorphologiques et leurs effets, comme l'existence de deux ondes de crue, la sous-estimation à certains endroits de la zone inondable, l'inadaptation de certains aménagements, ou encore des effets de site ou la forte capacité d'incision des matériaux. Il a en outre permis d'estimer les dommages sur la zone urbanisée.

4 RÉPONSES

Commentaires 4 Pingbacks 0

Yves Guermont 14 décembre 2015 à 10:20
Evaluation ouverte par Yves Guermont, CNRS/UPRESA 6063 IDEES, Université de Rouen, France

Appréciation du sujet
Moyenne

Appréciation générale
L'information contenue dans l'article est à jour, mais manque de précision technique. Son contenu est appuyé par des recherches valides et soutenu par une bibliographie. Les statistiques utilisées sont valides. Les arguments présentés sont logiques. L'article est pertinent pour la revue *Vertigo*, le lectorat de la revue, ses mandats et ses objectifs.

Appréciation concernant les articles de résultats de recherche et de réflexion théorique
Concernant la valeur scientifique: acceptable, demande de modifications mineures.
Concernant la qualité méthodologique: acceptable, demande de modifications mineures.

Appréciation concernant les articles de transfert de connaissance (synthèse)
Concernant l'exhaustivité: acceptable, demande de modifications mineures. Concernant la qualité de synthèse: acceptable, demande de modifications majeures (une localisation insuffisante des aires inondées et de leur relation avec l'urbanisation, ce qui est pourtant le cœur de l'article).

Appréciation concernant la correction de la langue, l'écriture et le style
Acceptable, demande de modifications mineures.

Appréciation concernant l'élégance de la présentation, l'organisation et la structure du texte
Acceptable, demande de modification majeure.
Le plan est un peu fouillis, ce qui entraîne de fréquentes redites. Pourquoi ne pas adopter un plan, certes classique, mais plus clair et convaincant. Par exemple:
- 1 Le contexte hydrogéologique et météorologique
- 2 Cinématique de l'écoulement de crue et calculs des débits
- 3 La péri-urbanisation non contrôlée vecteur d'exposition aux risques

Commentaires généraux
Points forts: une analyse sérieuse des données hydrologiques.
Lacunes ou faiblesses: un lien mal explicité avec les conséquences sur l'habitat.
Compréhensibilité: un plan un peu fouillis.

VEILLES
RADAR
changem
RADAR
RADAR

FIGURE 29: A REPORT PUBLISHED BELOW A PREPRINT

4.4.4 Open peer commentary workflow

The second experimental workflow did not aim to review articles for publication but rather to use crowdsourced commentary to help authors to improve their initial drafts before submitting for review. Five texts were published within this open commentary condition. The texts were contributions which were felt by *Vertigo's* editors to have significant problems and to be not yet ready for peer review. These texts were open to substantive and formal comments from any member of the public (open participation). This part of the experiment is henceforth referred to as the open peer commentary (OPC) workflow; those who post comments and annotations will be called *contributors*.

In this experiment, editorial content was not published at the end of the process, but the blog page did remain online, indicating just the article's title, along with the names of the authors and contributors. Where an article is eventually submitted and published (after a traditional peer review process), authors are asked to add the contributor's names to the *Acknowledgements* section of the article. A link refers back to the page of the blog where comments and annotations would then again be made available.

FIGURE 30: A CONTRIBUTOR ANNOTATES AN INITIAL DRAFT

4.4.5 Technical modalities for review and commentary

The experiment was conducted on Hypotheses, OpenEdition's blogging platform operating on WordPress. This blog platform's commenting feature was used for both the review and commentary

workflows. However, the blogging platform does not include the ability to annotate, i.e., to publish comments inside the text itself. For this purpose Hypothes.is⁷, a free Web browser plug-in based on the open-source JavaScript library Annotator⁸, was chosen. It allows users to easily annotate editorial content online by overlaying an annotation layer on a webpage (cf. Illustration 2).

4.4.6 Results

INTEREST IN EXPERIMENTATION WITH OPR AND OPC

The first element to note is the almost unanimous enthusiasm for the experiments from participating authors, referees and contributors, as well as in various informal discussions about the experiment. This enthusiasm was felt even during the search for referees/contributors. As in classical peer review, many peers declined the invitation to review. Yet, even those who declined to take part expressed an interest in this experiment. The recurring reason given for not participating was lack of time. This observation applies to both potential referees and contributors. This same enthusiasm toward the experiment was expressed in feedback from participating authors, referees and contributors. All were positive, save for one example from the “review” condition (described and analyzed later).

OPEN INTERACTION: POTENTIAL DISCUSSION BETWEEN AUTHORS AND REFEREES

Our workflow for OPR enabled interactive discussion between authors and referees/contributors. Interactive discussion took place in only about half of cases, however, even with mediational intervention in the form of inviting authors to answer reports. Generally, even where interactive discussion did not take place, reviewer and contributor comments were still taken into account during revisions.

Where discussion did take place, it generally took the form of a single detailed response by the author. However, some discussions developed into long exchanges, with new answers raising new questions. A basic typology of these discussions can be drawn:

- Modification: the author notes the observation and proposes a modification or announces that a modification will occur.
- Precision: the author asks for precision over the observation or the requested modification.
- Justification: the author justifies his/her position regarding a point of criticism.

⁷ <https://hypothes.is>.

⁸ <http://annotatorjs.org>.

At the end of the process, the record of this discussion can be a useful tool for an editor, enabling the arbitration of differing points of view and more precise requests for modifications. Although interactive discussion was undertaken in only about half of the cases, feedback from participants suggests that this did not represent a rejection of the idea of interactive discussion, but rather reflected a lack of time on the participants' behalf or a wish to wait for the results of the final review before addressing the requested modifications. This seemed to be the case in the "open commentary" condition, where articles were simultaneously under traditional review. Had these articles only been subject to open commentary, conditions would have likely been more favorable to discussions between authors and referees.

Studies suggest that openness encourages a better quality of comments in their contents and form^{9,10}. This may be because openness leads to a greater consideration of these factors: open identities personalize the process and open reports lead reviewers and contributors to take into account that their words will be exposed to an open audience for potential criticism of their own. In these experiments, these factors led to four reviewers and contributors reporting experiencing difficulties in finding the right tone and language for their observations. A concern in OPR is that these factors blunt the critical edge of reviews, but the experience in these experiments was that they led to constructive and relevant discussion where lack of clarity could be questioned. This recalls a "seminar effect", where the discursive possibilities enable a kind of "orality", with some of the benefits of face-to-face conversation enabling a critical but cordial exchange. Moreover, the review reports were longer and more detailed than is usually the case for the journal in question. This cordiality required facilitation, however. Three reviewers and contributors directly approached the mediating editor for advice regarding language, and one case in the open review condition resulted in the breakdown of communication between author and reviewer, necessitating intervention.

This latter case encapsulates many of the difficulties of OPR. Conflict began when the preprint appeared online, as it seems that the author had not understood the conditions of the OPR. This demonstrates the need for clarity amongst all participants as to the terms under which the peer review is to be conducted before the beginning of the process. The author's preprint accrued a negative review which advised that the article should be rejected. The author immediately requested that their text be removed from the Web and from the experiment. After some explanatory mediation regarding

⁹ Which is a common preoccupation, see for example: <http://blogs.plos.org/everyone/2015/05/01/plos-one-update-peer-review-investigation> (accessed on the 2/02/2016).

¹⁰ As for example: WALSH Elizabeth, ROONEY Maeve, APPLEBY Louis, WILKINSON Greg, "Open peer review: a randomized controlled trial", in *The British Journal of Psychiatry* 176, 2000, doi: 10.1192/bjp.176.1.47.

the OPR workflow, the author was persuaded to continue with the experiment and to express these objections directly to the referee via the review protocol. The author rejected out of hand each of the reviewer's negative comments and in the end again requested that their text be removed from the process. As it had not been agreed beforehand what would happen in such a case (whether the text would remain online or not), we agreed to the author's wishes. This points again to the need for the clear description of the OPR process so that authors and reviewers are aware of the consequence of the process ahead of time.

This case is not representative of the whole experiment, however. Another author of a text negatively reviewed (text 3), accepted critique and was ready to reply in order to get their work published. Indeed, the possibility for an author to answer referees' observations is a central advantage to OPR. In an OPR process, the referee's point of view need not be fixed, insofar as the author is able to directly question or counter criticisms they regard as illegitimate.

Furthermore, the authors' open answers can be a way for both the journal and readers in general to evaluate the relevance of the referee's objections and the efficacy of author revisions in answering reviewers' concerns. Authors can also investigate their referees' specializations and have a better understanding of their observations and better evaluate their relevance. As one referee put it, "the referee is reviewed". Indeed, the referee's hegemony, usually mediated by the journal behind the curtain of anonymity, is open to question. Thus, openness introduces reciprocity into the peer review process, which is publicly performed under the scrutiny of the community.

OPEN PEER COMMENTARY: MOTIVATING DISCUSSION

The five texts open to commentaries were chosen because of their formal problems. The goal was not to review them for publication, but rather to help authors improve their preprints until they were ready for submission. In practice, it transpired that this novel condition was not sufficiently clear for participating commentators accustomed to traditional review. Again, clearer information regarding the relevant processes, in particular regarding the differences between the two conditions was perhaps necessary. However, the "commentary" branch proved useful in opening an international space where researchers could discuss and develop their work. Within this condition, all texts came from authors from Sub-Saharan Africa, perhaps indicating its efficacy for scholars with fewer chances for exchange with the wider international academic community.

As with previous experiments with open commentary, it proved difficult to find contributors for this condition. On Vertigo's blog, where a section is dedicated to commenting on articles published in the journal, it is quite rare that readers post comments. Of 29 post-prints open to commentary, only 9

received comments, with two comments the maximum any article received.¹¹ Hence, different strategies were employed to find contributors. The first was the sending of semi-targeted emails to scholars found via university webpages. This strategy failed to bring in contributors, despite about ten percent of recipients responding positively to the emails with comments like “exciting”, “totally interesting”, “practice that should be developed”, “very relevant”, and “very interesting principle”. Once again, the issue was often lack of time, but also a professed lack of expertise, with answers like “I’m not specialist at all in this field”, “I feel far away from these issues”, and “I’m not sure to have the proper competences”. Given that commentators were only being asked to comment on purely formal elements such as language and structure, which requires no disciplinary specialism, this again shows the difficulties of communicating the conditions of such novel experiments, but also the fact that for some academics it is difficult to separate issues of form and content.

As this first strategy failed to attract contributors, a second wave of communication sent targeted emails to scholars based on their specialisms inviting them to comment on a specific text relevant to their interests. This strategy increased the number of contributors from two to ten, indicating that contacting scholars to invite comments on specific texts works to generate open-commentary interaction.

This strategy showed another interesting result. About twenty persons from outside of academia were invited to comment on the preprints based on their professional profiles – in particular for texts about water and water treatment. Despite each being contacted twice, no responses from this group were received. Here, as well as an issue of time, we can ask whether this was because those contacted did not feel themselves able to comment or if it indicates a deeper schism between industry and academia and the need for work to increase interaction between the scientific community and non-academic experts.

To sum, the open commentary condition was a success. All texts received comments and/or annotation, although their distribution was unequal. This fact separates the articles treated in this experiment from most open commentary trials, which struggle to attract commentators. The main factor in this success was the mediational activity of targeted requests sent to experts based on their familiarity with an individual article’s topic.

All the authors from the open commentary condition who gave feedback about the experiment (three of five) reported appreciated submitting their text to open commentary and asserted that they would do so again if given the chance in order to improve their preprints. Five texts were commented upon,

¹¹ At the end of January 2016.

four of them had their modified versions sent back within the time of the experiment, which proves the authors' interest in and commitment to the exercise.

Most contributors to the open commentary condition preferred to use the blog commentary feature rather than the annotation function, even where the latter would have been more effective in enabling comments on specific portions of text. This was despite the provision of specific tutorial materials for users. Here it seems participants were inhibited by being unfamiliar with the Hypothes.is Annotator plug-in software. Hypothes.is requires extra work to create a user's account, to activate this account, to activate the browser plug-in, to understand how to write an annotation, to type the annotation and finally to click to publish the annotation. Annotation would have perhaps found greater use had it been directly implemented on the blog rather than externally.

4.4.7 Conclusions

These experiments reveal OPR and commentary as both social and technical challenges. The OPR and OPC workflows were enabled via relatively simple web technologies. Although these technologies functioned surprisingly well, their limitations nonetheless can be seen to have inhibited uptake of, for example, the annotation feature. However, although OPR undoubtedly faces technological challenges, these seem overshadowed by the social problems of training, outreach and engagement required to bring users to take up these in novel processes.

TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The experiments showed the suitability of a simple blog platform like Hypotheses as a platform for OPR and open peer commentary. This suitability derives from its relative ease-of-use for administrators and its intrinsic commenting feature¹². There remain a few technical modifications that could improve its operational processes, however:

- Enable users to easily export texts to read offline before commenting or reviewing and enable users to easily export annotations and comments. (In fact, in the “review” condition, the referees were also provided with a file containing the text. This possibility could be generalized and automated.)
- Enable the numbering of the paragraphs (as is done in Revues.org) to allow referees and contributors to easily refer to specific parts of the text that they want to comment. These

¹² For more on utilization and appropriation of the blog-form by the scientific community see: DACOS Marin et MOUNIER Pierre. “Les carnets de recherche en ligne, espace d'une conversation scientifique de centrée”, in *Lieux de savoir, T.2, Gestes et supports du travail savant*, 2010, Albin Michel, Paris, pp.333-352 (disponible sur HAL: <sic_00439849>).

modifications concern the WordPress theme that is employed. The CommentPress Core¹³ plug-in developed by WordPress could be an alternative.

- Integrate the annotation tool directly into the blog. As described above, annotation was under-used. This could be rectified if instead of a web-browser plug-in, annotations were built directly into the blogging platform itself. Such an integrated tool would also enable the attribution of annotations to individual authors/referees/contributors.

HUMAN MEDIATION

The experiments demonstrated that enabling open peer review and open commentary are not merely technical problems. Their success depends upon mediation in its various stages. Firstly, clear tutorial/introductory materials to clearly explain the workflows are necessary. Secondly, mediation seems necessary to motivate the community to comment. Thirdly, the relative novelty of such forms of peer review means that there is an initial period of familiarization during which mediators can help orient participants. Finally, there is sometimes a need to guide discussions or mediate disputes.

OPR often requires human mediation to help the protagonists to find the proper tone to interact. In order to improve and control the quality of the language employed by protagonists, specific good behavior charters for open review and commentary could be proposed. Such rules could be a way to guide authors, and could be a reference for a journal in order to know who is an efficient referee or contributor to contact. Such facilitation activities are also necessary for technical support. Although the commenting function was clear for all protagonists, use of the more complex annotation tool had to be specifically supported. Hence, it is important to note that setting up OPR and open commentary workflows is unlikely to remove the need for editorial mediation. Opening reviewing processes modifies the tasks of the editor but does not render them unnecessary – especially as long as such workflows remain novel.

- **Facilitating OPR:** For the “review” workflow it is was necessary to guide authors as much as referees. In a classical review process, the main task is to make sure that referee will send back their review in time. In an interactive OPR process, both referees and authors must be tracked, especially to encourage interaction around the review. In the frame of this experiment, it appeared necessary to invite authors to react to the reviews.
- **Facilitating OPC:** For the “commentary” workflow, just publicizing the implementation of the experiment was clearly not sufficient to attract contributors. Instead it was necessary to invite

¹³ For example, see: futureofthebook.org/commentpress, or its utilization for open peer review on <http://adareview.fembotcollective.org> (accessed the 2/02/16).

specialists to comment. In addition, the experiment noted that even where scholars accept an invitation to participate in the commentary process, they must still be encouraged to remain effectively involved in the experiment. Finally, as in the “review” condition, it is necessary to invite authors to react to comments.

ESTIMATION OF THE NECESSARY WORKING-TIME

It is not easy to precisely determine the necessary working-time that has to be granted to OPR and OPC workflows. But such devices obviously continue to require efficient editorial mediation¹⁴. Achieving the level of engagement around the ten texts described here, with a reduced review period of one month, required the activity of a mediating editor for the period of four months. The mediating editor did not work full-time here, as this time was also occupied by background research into OPR. Nevertheless, the investment of time in implementing and mediating the workflows was substantial. We estimate that the time invested in bringing the 10 pre-prints through the review/commentary process required around 17 hours a week.¹⁵ We can then further divide this into 7 hours for the “review” condition and 10 hours for the “commentary” condition, including the search for contributors, making an estimated time and cost per text of 17 hours (~448€) for an open peer reviewed text, and 24 hours (~638€) for a preprint open to commentaries, which is not excessive compared to average article processing charges (though this does not include type-setting and operational costs).

CREDITING REFEREES AND CONTRIBUTORS

The difficulty in motivating open participation in OPR can potentially be offset by the new incentives enabled by open identities and open reports. Making review reports and reviewer identities open, enables reviewers to gain credit for their peer review activities. This issue is at the core of initiatives like Publons, which index review activities in collaboration with reviewers and publishers. Enabling reviewers to gain the symbolic reward of credit for reviews is seen as a key way of incentivizing review activities. One issue arising for publishers from this is the need for formal review citation practices, in order to enable reviewer credit that does not rely on a third-party service such as Publons or Reviewer Page. For us the best solution seems to be to integrate all information linked to the reviewing process in the metadata of preprints and postprints.

¹⁴ CONTAT Odile et GREMILLET Anne-Solweig, “Publier : à quel prix? Étude sur la structuration des coûts de publication pour les revues françaises en SHS”, in *Revue française des sciences de l’information et de la communication*, 7, 2015, (accessed on the 11/02/16), URL: <http://rfsic.revues.org/1716>.

¹⁵ Considering that this task occupied half of the working-time during this experiment, which means 17 to 20 hours a week.

4.4.8 Final words

This experiment was remarkable for the level of enthusiasm with which it was greeted, and hence the eagerness of the scientific community to bring innovation to reviewing processes. Yet it is also remarkable for the difficulties faced during implementation, especially in motivating potential reviewers. As well as facilitating the understanding of the openness and the technical aspects of the process, much time was required to facilitate the contact and the discussion modalities. Opening up peer review is just making public some necessary and routine parts of the scholar's work, but it seems that traditional processes and the conventions of invited, anonymous review are deeply engrained in research cultures. We should not forget, however, that what is done in OPR is common practice in seminars, conferences and colloquies. Perhaps what is required is the gradual introduction of such novel practices – this, at least, was the message from the interviews conducted for this study.

4.5 Experiments Conclusion

These experiments aimed at promoting OPR and studying its effects in the context of digital infrastructures for open scholarship. The main goals were to encourage experimentation, investigate ways OPR might integrate with OpenAIRE's infrastructure, and provide case studies for evaluation. All of these goals have been met:

- Open Scholar and partners aimed to enable direct and transparent academic collaboration between authors and reviewers by turning repositories into functional evaluation platforms through the development of an Open Peer Review Module (OPRM) to be installed in open access repositories. The OPRM's reputation system allows the quantification of a reputation for repository-hosted research objects, authors, reviewers, and reviews, and thereby integrates an element often said to be an incentive for open review: bringing the work of peer review into the scholarly reputation system. The OPRM was implemented in two repositories as part of this initial experiment. Selected researchers from all scientific disciplines were invited to have their work reviewed. First results indicate that such processes take time to develop and that some authors remain reluctant to take part. Hence the OPRM will likely continue to require human mediation to coordinate and motivate reviews. Nonetheless, the OPRM is ground-breaking in demonstrating the potential for incorporating peer review workflows into public, participatory scientific infrastructures.
- The Winnower looked to incentivize the publication of post-publication peer reviews through three activities: (1) Integration of the Winnower platform with repositories like Zenodo via DOIs and APIs to facilitate OPR of repository objects through the development of an open source tool called "Terrier" to extract metadata from scholarly articles (and in the case of Zenodo, the articles themselves). Terrier proved a good technical solution for connecting articles/metadata with the reviewing platform, which not only became part of The Winnower's core functionality but is also reusable and open for other purposes; (2) an online-campaign to solicit participants

to publish their journal club discussions. This proved less successful: While a total of 12 groups agreed to participate, The Winnower published only 6 journal club proceedings over the course of two months, even with small financial incentives on offer; (3) a survey of Winnower users and Twitter followers about their attitudes towards the publication of peer review reports. The survey showed that the strongest incentives for researchers to take part in OPR are the behaviors of other members of the academic community and the possibility of garnering reputational rewards.

- Finally, OpenEdition focused on developing and evaluating workflows for OPR (OPR) and open peer commentary (OPC) using the existing infrastructure of hypotheses.org, OpenEdition's platform for academic blogs, and the annotation tool hypothes.is. The experiment was successful in showing that OPR need not require technologically-elaborate solutions, and can be implemented (with some hiccups) successfully across openly available social platforms. It showed quite starkly, however, the extent to which OPR is a social challenge. The systems invited open interaction and open participation, but a great deal of human mediation was required to motivate participants, as well as to introduce the workflow, guide discussions and mediate disputes.

These experiments created innovative, open-source technical solutions for realizing OPR beyond traditional publishing infrastructures in the OPRM and Terrier". Open Edition's workflow showed the possibilities for re-purposing freely available online tools like blogging and annotation software for the similar purposes. At the same time, however, they also showed the social challenges of implementing OPR. All three experiments had difficulties in motivating authors and/or reviewers to take part. Hence, the role of human mediation, in educating users in new systems, motivating participation, guiding discussion and mediating disputes, cannot be understated.

The multitude of ways in which the various traits of OPR like open identities, open reports, and open participation can be configured, alongside the relative scarcity of research into how effective these various possible OPR configurations are in addressing the perceived deficiencies of traditional peer review, mean that experiments such as OpenAIRE has here supported are much needed. But these experiments point to further questions that urgently require further research and practical experimentation, effective incentives, reputation metrics for works, reviews, authors and reviewers across different platforms, ways of acknowledging reviewing activities, disciplinary differences, ethical issues, relative costs, and much more.

5 | SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has aimed to bring consensus on what open peer review (OPR) is, to add to our knowledge regarding what researchers, editors and reviewers want from OPR, and create empirical evidence to show what actually works in which contexts. These aims have been fulfilled through the following activities.

5.1 Definition

We have seen that the term “open peer review” is contested ground. Our aim here has been to provide some clarity as to what is being referred to when we use this term. By analyzing 122 separate definitions from the literature we have identified seven different traits of OPR which all aim at resolving differing peer review problems. Amongst our corpus of definitions we identified 22 unique configurations of these traits – literally 22 distinct definitions of OPR in the literature. Given such a contested concept, in our view the only sensible way forward is to acknowledge the ambiguity of this term, accepting that it is used as an umbrella concept for a diverse array of peer review innovations. The theme that unifies these diverse traits is Open Science. Factors like opening identities, reports and participation all bespeak the ethos of Open Science in trying, in their differing and overlapping ways, to bring greater transparency, accountability, inclusivity and flexibility to the restricted traditional model of peer review. Based on this work, we propose the following pragmatic, community-endorsed definition:

Open peer review is an umbrella term for a number of overlapping ways that peer review models can be adapted in line with the ethos of Open Science, including making reviewer and author identities open, publishing review reports and enabling greater participation in the peer review process.

The full list of traits are:

- Open identities:** Authors and reviewers are aware of each other’s identity.
- Open reports:** Review reports are published alongside the relevant article.
- Open participation:** The wider community to able to contribute to the review process.
- Open interaction:** Direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged.
- Open pre-review manuscripts:** Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g., via pre-print servers like ArXiv) in advance of any formal peer review procedures.

- **Open final-version commenting:** Review or commenting on final “version of record” publications

5.2 Attitudes to OPR

Our qualitative focus group sessions show that variety and experimentation are key to the success of OPR. Participants were in broad agreement that the differing kinds of OPR have a lot of potential to improve peer review, but they were also united that no one model will fit all disciplines or overcomes all obstacles. Yet as these variants crop up, stakeholder made clear that it is important that we are able to distinguish readily between them, and to recognize what actually works in which contexts. OPR is a process which involves many different stakeholder groups and the unease of some reviewers, authors and editors toward OPR is legitimate and must be faced with evidence of its effectiveness and advocacy regarding its benefits. This will be helped by efforts to reward the work of peer review (but “socially” via citation credit and such rather than financially). Introducing OPR requires cultural change, which is notoriously difficult. Participants were of one voice, however, that OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

The largely positive, yet balanced, view of OPR garnered via our focus groups is also reflected in the data gathered via our online stakeholder survey of 3062 editors, authors and reviewers. The findings of the study showed the majority of respondents to be in favour of OPR becoming mainstream scholarly practice, as they also were for other areas of Open Science, like Open Access and Open Data. We also observed surprisingly high levels of experience with OPR amongst our sample: three out of four (76.2%) of our respondents said that they had taken part in an OPR process as either author or reviewer or editor. Surprisingly, there was a rather strong pushback against open identities, with 51.1% of respondents believing that open identities will make peer review either worse or much worse. This is surprising because open identities is the OPR trait most commonly included in definitions (present in 110 of 122 definitions studied). Respondents see value in open identities but want reviewers to be able to choose whether or not to make their identities open. However, respondents are strongly in favour of open interaction between reviewers and authors. As this is, in some respects, an incremental change to peer review processes, this might hence be the first option for those journals looking to experiment with aspects of OPR.

5.3 Experiments with OPR

To improve OPR’s evidential basis, encourage experimentation in OPR and investigate ways OPR technologies might integrate with OpenAIRE’s infrastructure, OpenAIRE played host to three innovative experiments:

- **Open Scholar** and partners aimed to enable direct and transparent academic collaboration between authors and reviewers by turning repositories into functional evaluation platforms through the development of an OPR Module (OPRM) to be installed in open access repositories. The OPRM's reputation system allows the quantification of a reputation for repository-hosted research objects, authors, reviewers, and reviews, and thereby integrates an element often said to be an incentive for open review: bringing the work of peer review into the scholarly reputation system. The OPRM was implemented in two repositories as part of this initial experiment. Selected researchers from all scientific disciplines were invited to have their work reviewed. First results indicate that such processes take time to develop and that some authors remain reluctant to take part. Hence the OPRM will likely continue to require human mediation to coordinate and motivate reviews. Nonetheless, the OPRM is ground-breaking in demonstrating the potential for incorporating peer review workflows into public, participatory scientific infrastructures.
- **The Winnower** looked to incentivize the publication of post-publication peer reviews through three activities: (1) Integration of the Winnower platform with repositories like Zenodo via DOIs and APIs to facilitate OPR of repository objects through the development of an open source tool called "Terrier" to extract metadata from scholarly articles (and in the case of Zenodo, the articles themselves). Terrier proved a good technical solution for connecting articles/metadata with the reviewing platform, which not only became part of The Winnower's core functionality but is also reusable and open for other purposes; (2) an online-campaign to solicit participants to publish their journal club discussions. This proved less successful: While a total of 12 groups agreed to participate, The Winnower published only 6 journal club proceedings over the course of two months, even with small financial incentives on offer; (3) a survey of Winnower users and Twitter followers about their attitudes towards the publication of peer review reports. The survey showed that the strongest incentives for researchers to take part in OPR are the behaviors of other members of the academic community and the possibility of garnering reputational rewards.
- Finally, **OpenEdition** focused on developing and evaluating workflows for open peer review (OPR) and open peer commentary (OPC) using the existing infrastructure of hypotheses.org, OpenEdition's platform for academic blogs, and the annotation tool hypotheses.is. The experiment was successful in showing that OPR need not require technologically-elaborate solutions, and can be implemented (with some hiccups) successfully across openly available social platforms. It showed quite starkly, however, the extent to which OPR is a social problem. The systems invited open interaction and open participation, but a great deal of human mediation was required to motivate participants, as well as to introduce the workflow, guide discussions and mediate disputes.

These experiments created innovative, open-source technical solutions for realizing OPR beyond traditional publishing infrastructures in the OPRM and Terrier. Open Edition's workflow showed the possibilities for re-purposing freely available online tools like blogging and annotation software for the similar purposes. At the same time, however, they also showed the social challenges of implementing

OPR. All three experiments had difficulties in motivating authors and/or reviewers to take part. Hence, the role of human mediation, in educating users in new systems, motivating participation, guiding discussion and mediating disputes, cannot be understated.

5.4 Future Work

We have seen that a huge variety of possible configurations of the traits of OPR are possible, and many innovative publishers are already implementing these systems. Our surveys have shown that authors, editors and reviewers are positive towards OPR systems and have a surprisingly high level of experience with such systems. Yet our discussions here have highlighted some basic issues which remain to be addressed in future work.

- **Evidence:** As we saw in section 2, the evidence for the efficacy of the individual traits of OPR is often vanishingly thin. Although this fact goes for peer review generally, arguing for innovation in the peer review system obligates that we provide evidence to show what works in which circumstances. Given the strikingly different attitudes to OPR witnessed between differing disciplines, research must take these disciplinary differences into account.
- **Levels of mediation:** Although some advocates of Open Participation seem to imagine a future where reviewers and authors interact without mediation, low-levels of take-up for Open Participation and Final-version Commenting suggest that the editor or similar intermediary will continue to be required to find, engage and motivate reviewers. How might reviewers be motivated to engage in Open Participation processes without such mediation? In what ways is mediation in OPR processes different to that of traditional peer review?
- **Aversion to open identities:** Our survey respondents were clear in rejecting peer review where reviewer identities would be known to authors – seemingly reflecting common fears that either reviewers will hold back valid criticisms for fear of offending (especially senior) peers, or that forthright reviewers will be subject to future reprisals. To what extent are such fears valid? Do researchers act in such ways in OPR systems? If so, how could this be avoided?
- **Peer review and repositories:** An important element missing from open access repositories is functionality for the qualitative assessment of their contents. The open source Open Peer Review Module for Repositories (OPRM) developed as part of this research, addresses this gap. However, although this plug-in works as proof-of-concept, its repository-specific implementation suffers from obvious shortcomings: review communities remain “siloes”, specific to each repository. For institutional repositories and cross-disciplinary repositories (e.g., Zenodo), this is a particular problem since the individual disciplinary communities they serve are likely too small to reach the “critical mass” needed for OPR systems to work. A further problem is that review content cannot currently be federated (e.g., to be displayed alongside the same work is hosted elsewhere). A possible solution to this problem is to build an OPR module as an external 3rd party platform which hosts reviews and (1) Pulls OA publications (or links via metadata) to the platform, AND/OR (2) publishes reviews in a standardised, harvestable format that means that repositories themselves will be able to pull the reviews across to be able to display them alongside the content. A unified peer review platform, with federated access

procedures will overcome the silo-problem and bring review communities around distributed repository objects. This will further embed repositories as a viable alternative to journals for the dissemination of scientific results, a movement which is already gathering pace with overlay journals and Wellcome Trust's recent Open Research platform (<https://wellcomeopenresearch.org/>).

6 | REFERENCES

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7 | APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP REPORT: OPEN PEER REVIEW: MODELS, BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS, GÖTTINGEN, GERMANY 7 JUNE 2016

7.1 Introduction

7.1.1 Background

OpenAIRE, the European digital infrastructure for open scholarship, brings together more than 50 institutions to foster and further the implementation of open science across Europe. It is a sociotechnical initiative, comprised of both technical and human support activities. Among the latter, OpenAIRE runs regular workshops to provide outreach, support and training about all aspects of open scholarship, including open access, open data and open scholarly processes. One aspect of OpenAIRE's broad research activities into how openness and transparency can improve scientific processes is its investigation of new models of peer review to literature and beyond.

To further discussion of innovative models of peer review for scholarly publishing, OpenAIRE organized workshop entitled "Open Peer Review: Models, Benefits and Limitations" in Göttingen, 7th June 2016. The Workshop was attended by 72 participants who represented a comprehensive group of stakeholders including publishers, journal editors, interested researchers (as authors and readers), librarians / information specialists, repository managers. A full list of participants (including affiliations) can be found in Appendix A at the end of this document. Short biographical information on the speakers, panelists and moderators see Appendix D.

7.1.2 Workshop Theme

Digital networked technologies are reshaping scholarly communication, yet the predominant model of peer review remains the one which has been in place since the 1950s. As this model is subject to increasing criticism for being, for example, slow, unaccountable, wasteful of resources, and lacking in incentives, it makes sense to test and examine the ways in which new technologies enable new models of peer review. While a variety of initiatives, led in the main by publishers and researchers, have to date been implemented or proposed, the academic literature around open peer review remains under-developed and the various differing forms of open peer review often ill-defined.

Open peer review (OPR) can be seen as an umbrella term for a variety of ways in which the traditionally closed processes of peer review can potentially be reshaped by networked digital technologies. In response to a variety of critiques of traditional peer review (e.g., that it takes too long, is

unaccountable, is wasteful of resources, lacks incentive etc.), different forms of “openness” take shape, including post-publication review, online peer commentary, the publication of review reports as legitimate research outputs in themselves, disclosure of reviewer identities, and so on. These differing forms of openness, designed to address differing deficiencies in traditional peer review, will in turn be of interest to differing research communities and disciplines. It is perhaps safe to say that no one model of OPR will be suitable for all disciplines.

The workshop aimed to bring together different stakeholders to identify, discuss and work on current and future issues of OPR. Its goals were to critically analyze OPR from a variety of stakeholder perspectives and equip participants with a fuller theoretical understanding of OPR models, a critical overview of the practical implementation of OPR models, raise awareness of the advantages and disadvantages of OPR and the potential links between OPR and open access/open data, the EU’s Open Science agenda and institutional and thematic repositories.

7.1.3 Agenda

The workshop aimed to inform participants on key current issues in open peer review while also acting as a forum to move this discussion forward. Hence the first half of the day was given over to invited presentations detailing current open peer review activities from Tony Ross-Hellauer (OpenAIRE), Ulrich Pöschl (Max Planck/Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics) and Joshua Nicholson (The Winnower), as well as a structured panel discussion, chaired by Pierre Mounier (OpenEdition) in conversation with Stephanie Harriman (BioMed Central), Alexander Grossmann (ScienceOpen) and Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar). The second half of the day was then devoted to interactive break-out groups on three different topics: (1) Varieties of open peer review (moderated by Tony Ross-Hellauer), (2) Engaging stakeholders (authors/reviewers) in open peer review (moderated by Josh Nicholson), and (3) Ethical challenges in open peer review (moderated by Xenia van Edig of Copernicus Publications).

7.2 Workshop

7.2.1 Welcome and Introduction

Following a short welcome by Göttingen’s University Librarian Wolfram Horstmann, Tony Ross-Hellauer introduced the workshop’s aims and gave an overview of OpenAIRE’s open science activities and especially its work regarding OPR [[video](#)]. As Ross-Hellauer explained, in OpenAIRE’s definition, OPR is an umbrella concept which covers a host of novel approaches that aim to loosen the constraints of elements of traditional peer review like anonymity, selectivity and opacity. OpenAIRE aims to encourage experimentation in these areas through desk research, stakeholder engagement and through funding small-scale OPR experiments with OpenEdition, The Winnower and Open Scholar. Regarding the future of OPR, Ross-Hellauer highlighted the possibility of decoupling peer review from

the publishing process signaled by the Open Peer Review Module for repositories (<https://github.com/arvoConsultores/Open-Peer-Review-Module/wiki>) produced as a result of these experiments, as well as the need for standardization of terms in order to bring more clarity to debates about OPR, to assist in the standardization of OPR experimentation and to standardize metadata.

7.2.2 Keynotes

First Keynote: “Multi-stage open peer review integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation”, Ulrich Pöschl [[video](#)]

Ulrich Pöschl focused on “Multi-Stage Open Peer Review” and how it integrates the strengths of traditional Peer Review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation.

Pöschl, director of the Multiphase Chemistry Department at the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry and professor at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany, was an initiator of this approach with the open access journal Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics. While the main dilemma in traditional publishing is often thought to be the necessary trade-off between rapid publication and thorough review and discussion, a multi-stage OPR process can provide both speed and quality according to Pöschl. Rapidly-published discussion papers offer speedy, citable publication. What Pöschl terms Public Peer Review and Interactive Discussion then offers many of OPR’s benefits such as direct feedback, public recognition, preventing bias, fostering and documenting scientific discourse and so on. Through this approach, argues Pöschl, the final paper maximizes quality assurance and information density. Pöschl ended by offering several thought-provoking ideas for the further development of “Multi-Stage Open Peer Review”, including integration with repositories, living reviews, rankings and tiers, article-level metrics and virtual journals. For more information, see: Pöschl, U., 2012. Multi-stage open peer review: scientific evaluation integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* 6, 33. doi:10.3389/fncom.2012.00033

Second Keynote: “Grey Literature as Open Review”, Joshua Nicholson [[video](#)]

Joshua Nicholson’s presentation discussed “grey literature” (e.g., blogs, mailing lists) and social media as platforms for OPR. Nicholson, founder of The Winnower, an innovative open access publishing platform, began by pointing out that there has traditionally been a separation between public venues and scientific ones, where the public is usually excluded from the discussion. This has changed with the advent of social media argues Nicholson, where discussions via non-traditional channels has enabled a kind of grey literature peer review. Nicholson highlighted the ways in which some research communities came together to discuss and debate research results via social media platforms like Reddit, Facebook and Twitter.

Social media platforms specifically aimed at academia are also on the rise, with commercial platforms like ResearchGate and Academia.edu introducing discussion mechanisms. Meanwhile, the online journal club PubPeer facilitates post-publication discussion by enabling (open or anonymous) commenting on articles. Nicholson pointed out that we need to find a way to preserve and validate these comments. He then turned to some findings from a Winnower survey (run in conjunction with OpenAIRE) on opinions on peer review, which showed that most scientists feel they benefit from peer

review. Survey respondents reported that they felt making review reports open would not require much more work. The two most important incentives that respondents reported would encourage them to engage in OPR were recognition for their work and whether their peers did the same. The Winnower tries to mix the social, participatory and open elements of social media with traditional publishing type tools like DOI and archiving, making grey literature citable and accessible for the future.

Nicholson concluded by making a plea to better use the available infrastructure and furnish repositories with a more attractive design and some of the features of social media to make them more appealing platforms for scientific discussion.

7.2.3 Panel Discussion

Panel Discussion: “The Challenges of Open Peer Review”, Pierre Mounier (Chair), Stephanie Harriman, Pandelis Perakakis, Alexander Grossman [video]

Panelists began the discussion by each introducing what they see as the main challenge in OPR:

- Stephanie Harriman (BioMed Central) identified the biggest challenge to be the differing extent to which open peer review is accepted/embraced by communities in different fields and how to best dispel some of the concerns and misconceptions around open peer review (e.g. no one will agree to review, reviewers won't be able to review honestly if their identities are known). This is compounded by a lack of research into peer review, particularly into the ways in which different models work best for different fields.
- Alexander Grossmann (ScienceOpen) saw the main challenge as that of establishing more openness and transparency in peer review without affecting the quality of scholarly

communication. This also includes the question of whether or not the editorial assignment of reviewers is needed to maintain a maximum level of quality.

- Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar) focused on the challenges of serving the quality of research, establishing an appropriate level of openness, and developing a public, open source, interoperable and community governed infrastructure

The ensuing discussion was structured around four main topics: (1) defining OPR, publicness and openness, (2) relationship between transparency and quality, (3) OPR and the scholarly communication system, and (4) uptake of OPR in communities & incentivization of reviewers

Theme 1: Defining OPR, publicness and openness

An important challenge for OPR is to properly define it. It is an umbrella term referring to various practices. How can OPR be defined? Under what conditions can an “open” commenting framework be considered as OPR and a peer reviewing process as “open”?

Stephanie Harriman began by pointing out the importance of knowing what people mean by OPR. While for her it means open reviewer identities, Pandelis Perakakis prefers a more liberal idea of OPR which incorporates openness in time and open participation. This last aspect was picked up by Alexander Grossmann, calling it the “second dimension of OPR”, i.e., being open to all experts to submit a review, which is completely contradictory to classical peer review, where reviewers are selected by editors. The difference between open peer review and open peer commentary was also seen differently. While Pandelis Perakakis saw the difference to lie in the level of engagement involved (with review making a greater contribution to the article), Stephanie Harriman acknowledged commentaries as important forms of OPR. Alexander Grossmann pointed out that closed peer reviews can also often be incomplete, resembling commentaries more than full reviews. From the audience,

Ulrich Pöschl agreed that there are different forms of review, but sees the contribution to the finished article as a good criterion for distinguishing reviews from commentaries. Another remark by a member of the audience brought up the fact that reviews are usually guided by common rules for procedure and criteria, whereas commentary is freer. Following up on this, Perakakis added that reviews usually end

with a recommendation (i.e., to publish, request revisions or reject), whereas commentaries usually require no such thing.

Theme 2: Relationship between transparency and quality

The evaluation of research publications is based on the assumption that anonymity during the evaluation process guarantees the evaluator's neutrality and independence of judgment. How exactly is OPR challenged by that assumption? How can we establish more openness and transparency in peer review without affecting the quality of scholar communication? What are the means needed to achieve it? More specifically: do we need editorial assignment of reviewers?

Alexander Grossmann pointed out that quality assurance is the most important aspect of peer review for most researchers, referring to research that suggests that the majority of researchers who would be willing to review openly expect more quality by openness. In Grossman's own experience across many journals, reviews differ a lot in scope, effort and quality and he is sure that a lot of the low quality reviews would not be submitted in an OPR model. Stephanie Harriman agreed, referring to an experiment: comparing quality of reviewer reports of [BMC Infectious Diseases](#) (OPR) and [BMC Microbiology](#) (CPR) using the "reviewer quality index". A slightly better quality of reviews could be found with OPR (particularly in politeness and substantiating arguments). Stephanie Harriman further emphasized integrity: Although double blind review appears to assess a lot of problems OPR wants to address (removal of biases and providing more objective reviews), since fully double blind reviews are often not feasible (because academic fields are so small that authors will often be identifiable from their style and subject), they become *de facto* single blind reviews. Thus, Harriman considers OPR the best way to answer integrity issues.

Pandelis Perakakis then mentioned two general problems regarding quality assurance in closed peer review that both derive from the fact that closed models strengthen monopolies. Firstly, Perakakis argued that closed review shields highly-ranked journals from scrutiny. They maintain a reputation for high quality peer review, but the general community is unable to verify this as they would be in an open system where review reports were published. Secondly, in a closed model, closed academic circles make decisions about acceptance and rejection, blocking critique from the wider community.

Finally, from the floor, Ulrich Pöschl called for priority-setting to be determined by quality issues when establishing OPR systems: we should consider allowing anonymity for reviewers, as there are still good reasons for keeping this option, and focus on the lowest common denominator, i.e. opening review reports. Jean-Claude Guedon countered that reviews are contributions to the academic conversation and as such should be signed, with reviewers standing by their words publicly.

Theme 3: OPR and the scholarly communication system

At present most of the reviewing process is under the control of publishers, mostly commercial. In fact, it's the most important part of their added value and power over the communication system: they organize (but don't actually do) the evaluation. Services like the Open Peer Review Module (<http://duraspace.org/node/2824>) show a way forward to disentangle peer review from journals/publishers/private platforms, and reorganize it around a next generation of open access repositories with overlay services. What kind of infrastructure is needed, how can we make it sustainable and how could a repository-based author and reviewer reward system work?

Pandelis Perakakis explained that what researchers need is a place to meet and debate each other's works. For him, the internet is the basic infrastructure and communities/societies can organize such meetings themselves. The most important factor is to not build walls around these communities and to allow ample room in the debate for *all* interested experts. Perakakis believes that repositories can provide this space, but that it is crucial to maximize their interoperability in order to centrally connect different infrastructures, e.g. institutional repositories. Such infrastructures can function for relatively little cost in comparison to the current system of scholarly communication.

Stephanie Harriman pointed out that there are already different initiatives that decouple peer review from journals, such as [Peerage of Science](#) and [Axios Review](#), so it is already true that peer review does not necessarily have to happen within journals. However, Harriman emphasized editors' crucial mediational role in ensuring that peer review meets sufficient quality criteria – especially for medical journals which can shape clinical decisions. In addition, she stressed that exciting or buzz-worthy articles will always find willing reviewers, but there must also be a system in place to ensure that all research receives adequate peer review, regardless of how buzz-worthy.

Alexander Grossmann, however, sees no added value in publishers or journals in the digital age. Both made sense in the time of printed journals, when they organized the printing process and provided the technical interface. The added-services they still offer, like copy- or language-editing, are actually already outsourced. Instead Grossman likes the idea of repositories enriched by an overlay structure that offers communication, quality assessment and discourse to help improve the manuscript (similar to that offered by ScienceOpen).

From the audience, Erik Jan Van Kleef of 1Science.com countered by arguing that such systems have no viable financial models: who will pay for the relevant services in such a system? Alexander Grossmann conceded that there of course there will continue to be costs, but that these could in principle be covered, for example, by scholarly societies or funding organizations, although such a system would

need a sustainable basis. Pandelis Perakakis, however, argued that publishing costs are too often inflated, and that in fact services like typesetting, copy/language-editing, producing figures and so on are already available outside the publication system. This raised the issue of publishers as service providers: Ulrich Pöschl sees a place for commercial publishers if they reorient themselves as providers of specific, decoupled publishing

services.

Theme 4: Uptake of OPR in communities & incentivization of reviewers

One of the biggest challenges of OPR adoption by scholars is the differing extent to which it is accepted or embraced by communities in different fields and how to best answer some of the concerns and misconceptions around open peer review. How can this be improved? Additionally: Why should researchers want to review openly at all? What incentives are there for reviewers to review in the open?

According to Stephanie Harriman, researchers are usually very much against giving up their anonymity to sign their reports. She advocated three pragmatic ways in which to alter this: (1) perform further research on OPR, especially to show its potential to enhance the quality of not only reviews but of the articles themselves; (2) introduce OPR gradually by keeping open identities optional to first normalize the publication of reports; and (3) incentivize reviewers by making them satisfied with the way OPR systems work, but also by enabling recognition or reward. Open review reports enable that reward by allowing reviewers to gain credit for their work. Alexander Grossmann agreed, as the opacity of the work done in closed review systems can act as a disincentive – some reviewers don't invest effort in their reviews because that work cannot be proved. Making review reports more open and citable would be a great step forward in incentivizing reviewers. Grossman also mentioned the possibility of paying reviewers, which he considers infeasible due to the actual cost of the expertise involved. Finally, Pandelis Perakakis called for a shift in our way of thinking about peer review: it shouldn't be seen as

the reviewer doing someone a favour. Rather, reviewers should choose to review an article because they believe they can improve its quality. For Perakakis, there is no better incentive than being recognized by your peers and bringing new quality to research.

7.3 Breakout Groups

The second part of the workshop consisted of interactive discussion groups, designed to build on themes discussed earlier in the day by allowing all participants to engage in deeper discussion. Three different topics were open for discussion over two sessions, with each participant able to join two groups. Each group was chaired by a moderator who introduced the discussion themes. Participants then discussed structured questions in sub-groups before reporting back their opinions to the group. Participants were further asked to define new questions for the second group. In the next session, the second group was given an overview of the opinions of the first group and invited to build upon or disagree with them, as well as being asked to address the new questions defined by the first group. The themes for the breakout groups were: (1) varieties of OPR, (2) stakeholder engagement in OPR, and (3) ethical challenges in OPR. For the full lists of questions see Appendix C. Each breakout group was assigned a notetaker (Emilie Hermans, Frank Manista and Arvid Deppe), whose extensive records of each discussion have been used to provide the summary and conclusions given here.

7.3.1 Breakout Group 1: Varieties of OPR

As addressed in the earlier panel discussion, the first challenge that OPR presents is to ensure that when we talk about OPR we are talking about the same aspect(s), whether open identities, open reports, open participation, or other aspects. Is there a minimal definition of openness in peer review? The idea of this group was to make one step towards a deeper understanding of what OPR can be and how the heterogeneity can be (intellectually, terminologically and practically) handled. It aimed to

- Try to develop a joint understanding of peer review, open peer review and the differences between them
- Bring together different forms of OPR and discuss them in their particularities, benefits and drawbacks
- Increase sensitivity for the heterogeneous nomenclature of OPR variants and identify the most crucial ambiguities

Q1: What is Peer Review?

Participants defined peer review as a community process of quality control/assessment most closely associated with journals, but also applicable to monographs, grant applications and so on. Communities consist of people with an expertise in a given area. This expertise need not be just a matter of qualifications but also experience and hence peers are not limited to academia. Peers could

also come from other practitioners in the field (industry), secondary education (teachers specializing in certain topics) or citizen scientists. This conversation then led to consideration of what quality assurance means. Participants argued that quality control in peer review means helping to improve an article and/or identify mistakes, but also a filtering function to help define what is important. This leads to the question of whether peers are really equipped to determine the significance of a piece of research. Finally, since it decides whether something should be part of the scientific dialogue or not, peer review also includes an aspect of power. One participant noted that peer review is also defined by its process and the control it exerts over the process of academic publication.

Q2. What is Open Peer Review? What forms of OPR (and what forms of openness) can you identify?

Originally presented as two questions, the groups decided to answer these questions together. Open peer review was very roughly defined as being peer review with any “open” processes. The answers to what is or should be open were as heterogeneous as the field of OPR itself, and included concrete ideas like openness after the process, open discussion, open reviewer identities and possible interaction (“comment on the comments”). It also provoked questions about whether we meant openness to the author or to the public, openness of all the comments or just the decision letter, and openness during or after the peer review process. Some groups saw open identities of reviewers as crucial to the definition of OPR. Still others saw openly published reviews as a minimal characteristic,

but another did not consider it necessary to disclose everything in a review, but only those aspects needed to see how a decision was reached. There was also an emphasis on open participation and the crowdsourcing of comments – OPR drew repeated comparison to websites like Airbnb or TripAdvisor. Finally participants noted that OPR should not be defined in isolation as it is only one part of a wider scholarly communications ecosystem. Other elements that participants felt should be included in a definition of OPR were citeable reviews, portable and cascading peer review, review of review, pre/post-publication review, filter vs. feedback functions, and the openness of process versus the openness of results.

Q3. What forms of OPR do you think are the most important?

Participants agreed that there are many different forms of OPR which address different needs for differing communities. The most important criteria are that OPR should ensure scientific accuracy and produce good science. Additionally, there were two new beneficial aspects of OPR mentioned here: the educational benefit of transparent, open access processes for young researchers and the machine readability of review outputs/metadata.

Q4. Which forms of OPR could make peer review worse in your opinion? Why?

Participants voiced concern about the potential for unconfirmed/unreviewed results to be cited prematurely as a result of post-publication review. Unreviewed scientific results might find their way into the media, to be misunderstood or misused and thus cause hysteria (for example in medical research). But one participant countered this argument by saying that the media would learn that pre-prints are not reviewed and thus not to be reported. This participant continued that in fact, such episodes of media hysteria can in fact educate the public to be skeptical about scientific results, to come to see that the scientific method is not infallible. Another major concern voiced about open identity OPR was the potential for early career researchers to risk a backlash from more senior researchers should they criticize them publicly. OPR also has the potential to be abused by, for example, “gaming the system” (authors reviewing their own or friends’ work) – although it was pointed out that although this might be true of an open participation system, where reviewers were self-selecting, it would not be true of an open identity and/or open reports system where reviewers would have to stand publicly by their words. Finally, coming back to open commentary, there was a fear of losing quality control standards due to social media-like commenting fields (“anarchy in commenting/decisions”).

7.3.2 Breakout Group 2: Stakeholder Engagement in OPR

Attempts to open identities or publish review reports go against a well-established system and hence often face mistrust, lack of interest or active resistance. This breakout session therefore sought to

better understand the roles, motivations and fears of authors and reviewers, and to discuss ways to engage authors and reviewers in Open Peer Review processes. It aimed to discuss different functions and importance of mediation, understand what motivates author/reviewers to join OPR processes and to discuss incentives and arguments for participation in OPR.

Q1. How important do you think (e.g., editor) mediation is in OPR? Why?

All groups considered mediation very important to support authors, reviewers and their interaction. Participants felt that support should not be limited to initiating and managing the interaction itself, but also giving technical help and advising on difficult situations such as guiding authors how to handle contradictory reviews. Additionally, mediation can include questions of ethics, solving conflicts or filtering comments on highly contentious topics. There was some suggestion that mediators should also ensure quality control, but this was deemed controversial and others argued that it is debatable whether this classical editor function is still required in OPR. Nevertheless, participants noted that the need for mediation shall vary depending on the discipline and the type of content under review (results, data, software etc.). Finally, there was some suggestion that some of the mediation currently done by editors might be better achieved by automation (e.g. automatic selection of reviewers via citations), authors and/or the community.

Q2. What possible incentives can you think of to engage reviewers?

Groups agreed that OPR potentially poses extra work for reviewers and might be more time-consuming than classical peer review. It therefore stands to reason to offer incentives for reviewing openly. Most suggestions were based on the idea of rewarding reviewers, financially or symbolically. This could be simply by offsetting reviewer work with contributions towards author article processing charges (APCs) for their future publications (as is currently done by [PeerJ](#), for example), or even by formally transferring APCs to RPCs (review processing costs). Another idea put forth was the potential to have funders/institutions officially contribute towards payments for review work to individuals or institutions. However, others felt strongly that the current system of social incentives should not be undermined by financial ones.

Social incentives relate to career rewards focusing on recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, and so on. Recognition might be granted via altmetrics or informally via a social media. It was noted that such systems benefit from, if not require, persistent identifiers like ORCID, DOI etc. Such credit systems also have an aspect of the “gamification” of peer review. Other possible motivations mentioned were social pressure to review as well as policies/mandates by government or funders (as is apparently the case in Sweden). Open Reviews would also simplify collaborative review (where many reviewers each review a different section), which again reduces work for each reviewer. One participant argued that since OPR might be seen as an incentive itself, the focus should be on tackling the obstacles rather than creating new incentives.

Q3. What concerns do you think authors might have about OPR? Which argument could help against these fears?

The groups identified the fear of being criticized publicly as the main impediment for authors, spurred on by fears of “washing dirty laundry in public” and the “abuse of power dynamics”. Further issues were the fear of having to share the limelight with reviewers making major points and of losing control over the – potentially never ending – peer review process. Finally, authors in OPR may miss the prestige of coming through the review process of a highly ranked journal. On the other hand, reviewers might also be afraid of being accused in public of making flawed criticism or misunderstanding a paper, and this may be a huge disincentive – especially for early career researchers. There were no particular arguments made against these fears. Participants’ preferred strategies seem rather to be to emphasize the benefits of OPR for authors, such as more constructive, less judgmental reviews and the chance to interact, improve and thereby produce better science. Engagement accordingly needs education in OPR through good information and dissemination activities. It is especially about working on politeness and building trust, making OPR understood as a “chance to improve your work” or, more generally, changing the culture of review.

Q4. Do you think different disciplines will vary in their attitudes towards OPR? How?

Discussions brought up a lot of disciplinary differences that participants think need to be taken into consideration when thinking about OPR. First of all disciplines seem to differ ideologically in their attitude towards openness in general, and so perhaps disciplines which are open or hostile to Open Access will hold similar views towards OPR. Further, there are differences in, for example, sensitivity to time taken, publication models, the culture of rejection (e.g. in medicine it is normal to have high number of rejections), special processes (e.g. scooping is a concern where research can be copied easily) and reviewing effort (science is easier to peer review than humanities). Disciplines also differ in

size, which can have different effects. In small communities for instance researchers often know each other in person which may be problematic. On the other hand, small close-knit communities may foster a greater sense of duty. Participants were of one voice that despite these differences, OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines –

preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

7.3.3 Breakout Group 3: Ethical Challenges of OPR

A lot of the arguments made against closed peer review are of an ethical nature: reviewer bias, difficulties with authors/reviewer anonymity, opaqueness or subjectivity of reviews and even the question of whether any review was done at all. The differing forms of OPR may seem to address many of these problems, but it is no panacea. The idea of this group was to raise awareness of the ethical problems that OPR can raise and discuss ways of tackling them. It aimed to identify the most pressing ethical issues, discuss ethics in OPR in response to concrete challenges and to find suitable solutions, with a special focus on ethical considerations concerning early career researchers.

Q1. What in your opinion are the most pressing ethical issues in the context of OPR?

Participants felt that ethical concerns around OPR encompassed diverse aspects. First of all, with open identity peer review, there is the question of whether it is of higher ethical priority to let the author know who is judging him or not to force the reviewer to reveal his identity. Another aspect is the possibility of disadvantages for authors. For instance, does rejection at one journal foster hasty judgement and influence the chances of gaining acceptance at another journal? One participant noted that the first opinion stated in a public discussion can often inordinately influence the direction of the

ensuing discussion. Although participants recognized that there might be potential conflicts in some specific cases where reviewer and author identities were open, it was generally agreed that radical transparency would solve more problems on the whole than it would produce. Another important issue is that OPR opens the door for potentially unethical behaviours. In post-publication OPR, for instance, if an author's ideas are made public in advance of full publication, others might appropriate those ideas without giving due credit. Another scenario concerning open commenting platforms is reviewer identification. How can we be sure a person is who they claim to be? In addition to these questions of how to formulate new workflows and codes of conduct for new ethical issues raised by OPR, participants emphasized the need to communicate the ethical benefits of OPR.

Q2. Consider this case: An author is unhappy with a very critical pre-publication OPR. He/she demands their work be withdrawn from the process and the OPR taken offline completely. Would you agree to the author's demands? Why/why not?

Groups' opinions tended to depend on the circumstances but the dominant answer was that in such a situation, openness should prevail:

- The answer would be NO if the content of the review were considered fair scientific discussion. Additionally, it needs to be considered that the controversy might be interesting for the future development of science – controversy often attends radical ideas, but radical ideas push science forwards. It was concluded that the point of OPR would be missed completely if only positive reviews were allowed to be open.
- The answer could be YES if there were no scientific benefit/interest in keeping the review available. This could be the case for unscientific discourse or personal/insulting comments. Special consideration could also be taken to protect young researchers.

Furthermore the answer would naturally depend on the specific conditions of the peer reviewing process. One participant suggested that a solution to this problem could be to invite another independent reviewer to give a new point of view. Participants were clear that this case and the discussions around it show the importance of (1) a code of conduct, including an explicit statement and even legal agreement that provides clarity on the conditions under which the OPR will be conducted for author, reviewer and editor, and (2) the need for ongoing human mediation in OPR.

Q3. What ethical concerns do you have about (1) editors selecting reviewers, (2) authors selecting reviewers?

The groups agreed that editors usually have too little knowledge of specific sub-disciplines to choose reviewers with a maximum of competence in the field. Authors, on the other hand, know their peers but may be biased in their choices. A solution could be an algorithm-based selection. Most ideas of solving or reducing the problem focused on transparency and self-regulation: as OPR opens the whole reviewing process, conflicts of interest can be identified, biases can be recognized and arguments can be scrutinized by community. This can be supported by additional oversight measures such as the review of review. If the reviewing system is participatory or based on self-selecting reviewers, the problem of selection would of course disappear, although replaced by new specific challenges.

Q4. Are there special issues to be considered regarding young researchers?

Participants raised several ethical issues that specifically affected young researchers. First of all, young researchers might be afraid of publicly criticizing senior researchers, fearing negative consequences for their careers. On the other hand, seniors might be worried young researchers might not review to their standards of critique. Although young researchers might bring a fresh perspective, have more time and be more motivated and precise in their reviewing, they may not have enough experience to fulfil the task. This may be seen as a problem when reviews are open, but on the other hand, OPR can also work

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as an educational tool for young reviewers on reviewing, reviewing processes and potentially on ethical issues as well.

7.4 Outcomes, recommendations & lessons learnt

Discussion across all areas showed that variety and experimentation are key to the success of open peer review. Participants were in broad agreement that the differing kinds of OPR have a lot of potential to improve peer review, but they were also united that no one model will fit all disciplines or overcomes all obstacles. Therefore different OPR initiatives and approaches are to be welcomed for the shared goal of producing better science through openness and transparency. Let a thousand flowers bloom, so to speak.

Yet as these variants crop up, it is important that we are able to distinguish readily between them, and to recognize what actually works in which contexts. The heterogeneity of views on what OPR is that occurred during the workshop just drive home the fact that we need a better overview of the different models, including perhaps agreement on what minimum levels of openness are necessary to categorize a process as open, and – most importantly – a common, community-agreed taxonomy of OPR should be developed.

OPR is a process which involves many different stakeholder groups. The workshop showed that the unease of some reviewers, authors and editors toward OPR is legitimate and must be faced with evidence of its effectiveness and advocacy regarding its benefits. This will be helped by efforts to reward the work of peer review (but “socially” via citation credit and such rather than financially). Introducing OPR requires cultural change, which is notoriously difficult. Participants were of one voice, however, that OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

On the ethical side, it is clear that OPR is no panacea and that while it may resolve some ethical issues regarding accountability and bias with classical peer review, it nonetheless poses new problems. Discussions indicated the importance of agreeing on common ethical rules and committing them bindingly. Our workshop participants generally agreed that OPR promises to improve peer review, and made plain that its ethical benefits – transparency, accountability, openness – should be made a key part of arguments in its favour.

To draw general conclusions, we can say:

- OPR processes need to be made transparent and comparable.
- Participants agreed that a common terminology, such as is offered in the previous chapter, is needed as a basis of comparing (effectiveness of) OPR models.
- Different modes of mediation need to be tested.
- Ways to acknowledge and reward reviewers appropriately need to be found.
- Development of mandates and policies should be supported.
- Differences and particularities of disciplines must be acknowledged and taken into account.

- A common code of conduct should be created, especially taking into account the needs of young researchers.
- Binding agreements regarding the terms of OPR procedures for authors, reviewers, editors and publishers should be in place ahead of time.

7.5 Documentation

All keynotes and the panel discussion were recorded. The videos are available at:

- <https://vimeo.com/channels/openaireworkshop6>

The slides of all presentations can be found at Slideshare:

- http://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu

Photos of the workshop are available on Flickr:

- <https://www.flickr.com/groups/openaire>

Further documentation:

- Workshop announcement and programme on openaire.eu:
<https://www.openaire.eu/events/eventdetail/388/53|54|55|56|57|58/workshop-open-peer-review-models-benefits-and-limitations>

- Workshop report on blog.openaire.eu: <https://www.openaire.eu/open-peer-review-models-benefits-and-limitations>
- Workshop report on openaccess.si (Slovenian): <http://www.openaccess.si/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/28-Porocilo-Odprto-recenziranje-13.6.2016.pdf>
- Workshop report on BioMed Central blog: <http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/bmcblog/2016/06/15/challenges-open-peer-review/>

7.6 Sub-appendices

7.6.1 A. Participants list

Name	Institution
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Gurinovich, Roman	CONZL OÜ, Estonia
Görögh, Edit	University of Debrecen, Hungary
Hafner, Georg	Göttingen University, Germany
Harriman, Stephanie	Biomed Central, United Kingdom
Heber, Joerg	Nature Communications, United Kingdom
Hermans, Emilie	Ghent University, Belgium
Hoffman-Sommer, Marta	University of Warsaw, Poland
Hoffmann, André	Universität Zürich, Switzerland
Hornig, Christoph	Germany
Jones Nelson, Alissa	De Gruyter, Germany

Kacherki, Umeshreddy	Indian Institute of Science Education & Research, Pune, India
Kluyver, Thomas	University of Southampton, United Kingdom
Kosanovic, Biljana	University of Belgrade, Serbia
Koskinen, Kimmo	University of Helsinki, Finland
Kotar, Mojca	University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Koukounidou, Sylvia	University of Cyprus, Cyprus
Kuchma, Iryna	Stichting eIFL.net (EIFL), Lithuania
Larsen, Asger Væring	University of Southern Denmark, Denmark
Linde, Peter	Blekinge Institute of Technology, Sweden
Loizides, Fernando	University of Wolverhampton, United Kingdom
Manista, Frank	JISC, United Kingdom
Marti, Zafiro	University of Cyprus, Cyprus
Medves, Maud	Inria, France
Mimkes, Julika	University of Göttingen, Germany
Montenegro, Eva	FECYT, Spain
Mounier, Pierre	CNRS CLEO EHESS, France
Nicholson, Joshua	The Winnower, United States
Oberländer, Anja	University of Konstanz, Germany
Perakakis, Pandelis	University of Granada, Spain
Pöschl, Ulrich	Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Germany
Príncipe, Pedro	University of Minho, Portugal
Rank, Sven	Göttingen University, Germany
Ross-Hellauer, Tony	Göttingen University, Germany
Rozenberga, Gita	University of Latvia, Latvia
Schirrwagen, Jochen	University of Bielefeld, Germany
Schuller, Dorothea	Göttingen University, Germany
Sipria-Mironov, Elena	University of Tartu, Estonia
Stojanovski, Jadranka	University of Zadar, Croatia
Stone, Graham	United Kingdom
Tate, Dominic	University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom
Tautkeviciene, Gintare	Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
Tavares, Richard	PRACE AISBL, Belgium
Tennant, Jon	ScienceOpen, Germany
Thorsteindottir, Solveig	Landspítali Univ Hospital, Iceland
Tiggre, Antanina	Belarusian State University, Belarus
Tkacikova, Daniela	VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic

Tobias, Regine	KIT Scientific Publishing, Germany
Valikonytė, Dalia	Vilnius university, Lithuania
van Edig, Xenia	Copernicus GmbH, Germany
van Kleef, Erik Jan	1science, Belgium
Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge	Ghent University, Belgium
Verdicchio, Dirk	Universität Bern, Switzerland
Weilenmann, Anne-Katharina	Switzerland
Wennström, Sofie	Stockholm University, Sweden
Wintz, Elise	Germany
Woutersen-Windhouver, Saskia	University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Šimukovič, Elena	University of Vienna, Austria

7.6.2 B. Detailed Programme

09.00	Registration
09.30 - 09.40	Wolfram Horstmann: Welcome
09.40 – 10.00	Tony Ross-Hellauer (OpenAIRE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop aims; overview of Open Peer Review and OpenAIRE
10.00 - 10:30	Keynote 1: Ulrich Poeschl (ACP): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stage open peer review integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation
10.30 - 11.00	Keynote 2: Josh Nicholson (The Winnower): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grey Literature as Open Review
11.00 - 11.20	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:20 - 12:40	Panel Discussion: The Challenges of Open Peer Review <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panel participants: Pierre Mounier (Chair) (Open Edition), Stephanie Harriman (BMC), Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar), Alexander Grossmann (Science Open)
12.40 - 13.40	Lunch

13.40 - 14.50	Moderated Breakout 1 (parallel sessions) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Varieties of OPR• Stakeholder engagement in OPR• Ethical challenges of OPR
14.50 - 15.10	<i>Coffee Break</i>
15.10 - 16.00	Moderated Breakout 2 (parallel sessions) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Varieties of OPR• Stakeholder engagement in OPR• Ethical challenges of OPR
16.00 - 17.00	Reporting back and final discussion

7.6.3 C. List of Questions (Breakout Groups)

<p>Varieties of OPR (Moderator: Tony Ross-Hellauer)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What is peer review?2. What is open peer review?3. What forms of OPR can you identify?4. What forms of OPR do you think are the most important?5. Which forms of OPR could make peer review worse in your opinion? Why?
<p>Stakeholder engagement in OPR (Moderator: Joshua Nicholson)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. How important do you think (e.g., editor) mediation is in OPR? Why?2. What possible incentives can you think of to engage reviewers?3. What concerns do you think authors might have about OPR? Which argument could help against these fears?4. Do you think different disciplines will vary in their attitudes towards OPR? How?
<p>Ethical challenges of OPR (Moderator: Xenia van Edig)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• What in your opinion are the most pressing ethical issues in the context of OPR?• Consider this case: An author is unhappy with a very critical pre-publication OPR. He/she demands their work be withdrawn from the process and the OPR taken offline completely. Would you agree to the author's demands? Why/why not?• What ethical concerns do you have about (1) editors selecting reviewers, (2) authors selecting reviewers?• Are there special issues to be considered regarding young researchers?

7.6.4 D. Biographical information

Alexander Grossmann studied Physics in Aachen and holds a PhD from the Research Center Jülich. He worked for several publishers (Wiley-Blackwell, Springer, de Gruyter). He is Professor of Publishing Management at HTWK Leipzig University of Applied and Co-Founder of ScienceOpen.

Stephanie Harriman is the Medical Editor at BioMed Central and has a degree in Medicine from Brighton and Sussex Medical School. She is also co-Editor-in-Chief of Research Integrity and Peer Review.

Pierre Mounier holds Masters in Classical Studies and in Anthropology from Sorbonne and Nanterre University. He is research engineer at the School for Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences (Paris, France) and associate director of the Center for open electronic publishing (Cléo).

Joshua Nicholson received his PhD in 2015 from Virginia Tech studying the role of the karyotype in cancer initiation and progression in the lab of Dr. Daniela Cimini. In addition to his work on the bench he has authored numerous articles on scientific funding and publishing. He is CEO and Co-founder at The Winnower “The Winnower”, an open access online scholarly publishing platform that employs open post-publication peer review.

Pandelis Perakakis has a PhD in clinical psychophysiology from the University of Granada, Spain. He works as a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Granada and is co-founder of Open Scholar CIC that he currently serves as director. Open Scholar is an organization of 120 volunteer research scholars from 17 different countries that actively promote an open model of scientific evaluation and dissemination.

Ulrich Pöschl is director of the Multiphase Chemistry Department at the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry and professor at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany. His current scientific research and teaching are focused on the effects of multiphase processes in the Earth system, climate, life & public health. Pöschl is actively engaged in the promotion open science, and is the initiator of interactive open access publishing with public peer review and interactive discussion (multi-stage open peer review) as established with the international scientific journal Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics (ACP, <http://www.atmospheric-chemistry-and-physics.net>) and the European Geosciences Union (EGU, <http://www.egu.eu>).

Tony Ross-Hellauer is Scientific Manager for the OpenAIRE2020 project at Georg-August-University Göttingen. He has a PhD in Information Studies (University of Glasgow, 2012), in addition to MA (Philosophy) and MSc (Information and Library Studies) degrees. He is an enthusiastic advocate of Open Access and Open Science whose research interests include repositories, metadata, and the philosophy/history of technology.

Xenia van Edig, PhD in Agricultural Sciences, is responsible for Business Development at Copernicus Publications, the largest open access publisher in the Geo- and Earth system sciences and known as one of the first publishers to embrace public peer review.

8 | APPENDIX 2: OPR SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Welcome to OpenAIRE's survey on Open Peer Review. Thank you for participating.

The survey should take about 15 minutes to complete - please answer all the questions as this will enable us to derive the most value from your responses. If needed, you can pause the survey by pressing the “pause the interview” button. You’ll then be able to resume at any time.

Participation in the survey is voluntary. All data will be kept confidential and evaluated anonymously in compliance with the principles of the European Data Protection Directive. In accordance with the EC’s Open Research Data Pilot, the anonymized data will be made openly accessible.

1. Please tell us your age *[one answer]*

- under 24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- Over 65

2. What region are you living in? *[one answer]*

- Africa
- America
- Asia
- Europe
- Oceania / Australia

3. What subject discipline are you specialized in *[one answer]*

- Choose the most suitable category
- Agriculture and Food sciences
- Arts and Architecture
- Biology and Life sciences
- Chemistry
- Computer Sciences / IT
- Earth and environmental Sciences
- Economics
- Health Sciences
- History and Archeology
- Languages and Literature
- Law and Political science
- Mathematics and Statistics
- Physics and Astronomy
- Psychology and Philosophy
- Social Sciences
- Technology and Engineering
- None of the above

4. In which scholarly communication roles do you have experience? [*multiple answers incl. freetext + none*]

(Tick as many as apply)

- Editor
- Author
- Publisher
- Reviewer
- Other(s), please specify: *free text*
- None of the above [*exclusive*]

5. Do you have personal experience of open peer review as [*multiple answers incl. freetext + none*]

(Tick as many as apply)

- Editor
- Author
- Publisher
- Reviewer
- Other(s), please specify: *free text*
- None of the above [*exclusive*]

6. Overall, how satisfied are you with the peer review system used by scholarly journals? [*one answer*]

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied
- Don't know

7. There are many ways peer review processes can be modified. Here we define some of these innovations. [*one answer*]

Do you think they will make peer review better, worse, or have no effect?

- *Much worse*
- *Worse*
- *Neither better nor worse*
- *Better*

- *Much better*
- *Don't know*

1. Open Reports: Peer review where review reports are published alongside the relevant article.
2. Open Identity: Peer review where authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity.
3. Open Participation: Peer review that allows the wider community to contribute to the review process.
4. Open Interaction: Peer review that allows and encourages direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, as well as between reviewers.
5. Open pre-review manuscripts: Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g., via pre-print servers like ArXiv) in advance of any formal peer review procedures.
6. Open final-version commenting: Review or commenting on final "version of record" publications.
7. Open platforms: Peer review that is de-coupled from publishing in that it is facilitated by a different organisational entity than the venue of publication.

8. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements. [one answer]

- *Strongly disagree*
- *disagree*
- *neither agree nor disagree*
- *agree*
- *strongly agree*
- *Don't know*

1. The overall current system of scholarly communications works well.
2. Making research publications open access should be common scholarly practice.
3. Making research data open access should be common scholarly practice.
4. Open Peer Review should be common scholarly practice.

In this section, we'd like to go deeper into your attitudes towards open identities, open reports and open participation.

9. We defined "Open Reports" as peer review where review reports are published alongside the relevant article. [multiple answers]

Have you taken part in a review process with open reports as a

- reviewer
- author

- neither *[exclusive]*

10. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements. [one answer]

- *Strongly disagree*
- *disagree*
- *neither agree nor disagree*
- *agree*
- *strongly agree*
- *Don't know*

1. Published review reports provide useful information for the reader.
2. Publishing review reports will make reviewers less likely to make strong criticisms.
3. Publishing review reports will increase the quality of reviews.
4. Potential reviewers are less likely to agree to review for journals that publish review reports.
5. Potential authors are less likely to submit to journals that publish review reports.

11. We defined “Open Identity” as peer review where authors and reviewers are aware of each other’s identity [multiple answers]

Have you taken part in a review process with open identities as a

- reviewer
- author
- neither *[exclusive]*

12. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements. [one answer]

- *Strongly disagree*
- *disagree*
- *neither agree nor disagree*
- *agree*
- *strongly agree*
- *Don't know*

1. Making reviewer identities open will make reviewers less likely to make strong criticisms.
2. Making reviewer identities open will increase the quality of reviews.
3. Reviewers should be allowed to choose whether or not to make their identities open.
4. Making reviewer identities open is fairer to authors.
5. Potential reviewers are less likely to agree to review for journals that make reviewer identities open.
6. Potential authors are less likely to submit to journals that make reviewer identities open.

13. We defined “Open Participation” as peer review that allows the wider community to contribute to the review process. [multiple answers]

Have you taken part in a review process with open participation as a

- reviewer
- author
- neither [exclusive]

14. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements. [one answer]

- *Strongly disagree*
- *disagree*
- *neither agree nor disagree*
- *agree*
- *strongly agree*
- *Don't know*

1. Everybody with sufficient knowledge should be able to participate in the review process regardless of their formal qualifications or area of work.
2. Close circles of reviewers and editors hold back innovative research.
3. Reviewers are more likely to review if they are invited.

15. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements. [one answer]

- *Strongly disagree*
- *disagree*
- *neither agree nor disagree*
- *agree*
- *strongly agree*
- *Don't know*

1. Increased interaction between authors & reviewers will result in better publications
2. Manuscripts should be made openly accessible before peer review begins.
3. Blog articles, online journal clubs and social media commentary on final-version publications are part of peer review.

16. Do you agree with this definition of Open Peer Review *[one answer]*

An umbrella term describing a variety of innovations which “open up” the traditional peer review process by modifying one or more aspects to make it more inclusive, transparent and/or accountable. Primary aspects are Open Identities, Open Reports and Open Participation (possession of one of these traits is usually sufficient to qualify a system as “Open Peer Review”). Secondary characteristics include Openness in Time, Open Interaction, Open Platforms and others (these aspects are usually insufficient in themselves to qualify a system as “Open Peer Review”, but are often included in many definitions nonetheless).

- Yes, I agree
- No, I don't agree

17. If you do not agree, why? *[free text]*

18. Do you have any other comments? *[free text]*

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

For questions regarding OpenAIRE or its Open Peer Review activities please contact [Dr. Tony Ross-Hellauer](#)

Your answers have now been received by OpenAIRE, you may now close your browser tab or window.